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Erasmus Mundus Joint Master's Degrees: Exploring *Third Space* Settings to Address the Staff 'Divide'

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Abstract

ERASMUS MUNDUS JOINT MASTER'S DEGREES:
EXPLORING *THIRD SPACE* SETTINGS TO ADDRESS THE STAFF 'DIVIDE'

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My dissertation explores the collaboration between professional staff and academics in Erasmus Mundus Joint Master's Degree (EMJMD) consortiums. As complex international projects, the EMJMDs, launched in 2004, require the know-how of different staff categories to succeed. For this reason, the EMJMD setting creates a space, a *Third Space*, in which professional staff, academics, and a new category, blended professionals, work together as a group of experts for a common goal of designing a successful Master's degree.

The current academic literature on EMJMDs focuses mainly on student experiences, successful stories, institutional visibility or the educational content of the degrees without considering the expertise and knowledge needed to develop these programmes or the relationships among those involved in the development of an EMJMD. This lack of academic knowledge on the people working behind the scenes prevents higher education institutions from understanding importance of good working relationships among staff categories for successful international projects, precluding the replication of good practices in other institutional settings. My research questions aimed to understand the collaboration within an EMJMD in terms of: (i) its characteristics, (ii) the key factors shaping those characteristics, (iii) the added value of this collaboration for the people and institutions involved, and (iv) whether the relationships within the consortium facilitated the recognition and role of professional staff.

To investigate these questions, I used a mixed-method research design composed of a quantitative and qualitative phase in 26 EMJMD consortiums. My findings suggest that in most consortiums, staff relationships were based on solid Team Effectiveness, creating a supportive space for all participants and promoting a non-hierarchical approach. Consequently, there was no 'divide' between staff categories because it was overcome due to egalitarian relationships and a constructive working atmosphere.

Dedication

To my children, Federica, Gianluca and my grandchild Simone, for being the stars in my life;

To my parents, Fernando and Mariana, for showing me the world from a young age;

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CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Uncovering My Research Topic and Its Aims

The global higher education sector has been through significant transformations over the past few decades and the internationalisation of higher education is one of the main changes. As a result, higher education institution leadership has sought new approaches to improve their educational offerings, including partnerships for cross-border activities. In this evolving scenario, joint degrees can be seen as such an approach (Michael & Balraj, [2003](#)) because by definition, a joint degree programme is a degree that “is designed and delivered by two or more partner institutions in different countries” (Helms, [2014](#), p. 6). Joint programmes have been on the Bologna Process agenda since the beginning in 1999,¹ but gained strong incentives over the last few decades, when the European Union considered them as essential instruments for the consolidation of the European Higher Education Area (YERUN, [2018](#)). In 2004, with the launch of the Erasmus Mundus Programme, a crucial moment for the development of joint programmes arrived. The Erasmus Mundus Joint Master’s Degrees (EMJMDs) prioritise academic networking, collaboration, and international student mobility (Marques et al., [2022](#)).

Consequently, staff with professional and academic backgrounds (Whitchurch, [2015](#)) are involved in these large projects, which include a wide range of tasks (Gornitzka & Larsen, [2004](#)) and imply new spaces of interaction. The way staff involved in EMJMDs collaborate is the primary focus of my dissertation, in which I aim to verify if “one of the most persistent dualisms in higher education – a dualism of academic/non-academic othering” (Macfarlane, [2015](#)) and the division between these two categories persists, or if on the contrary, they develop a supportive collaboration.

¹ Bologna (Italy). Ministers from 29 countries expressed their willingness to increase the competitiveness of the European Higher Education Area (EHEA).

1.2 An Overview of the Core Subjects Under Study

1.2.1 *The Uniqueness of an Erasmus Mundus Joint Master's Degree*

As stated by Knight, the European Union was the leader in creating awareness about the value of joint programmes, and strongly promoted their development (Knight, [2008](#)). The European Commission ([2013](#)) indicated the following: “Evidence shows that joint and double degrees are powerful tools: to promote quality assurance and mutual recognition of qualifications; to attract talent and deepen partnerships; and to enhance the international experience, intercultural competence and employability of graduates” (European Commission, [2013](#), p. 9).

The distinctiveness of the Erasmus Mundus programmes can be attributed to their signature intensive mobility scheme, the diverse and complex nature of the actors involved (i.e., a consortium of higher education institutions and associate partners), and the unique demand they place on effective communication, feedback, and coordination with all stakeholders (Abebe & Ford, [2019](#)). Conversely, when these programmes do not have a broad involvement of all relevant actors, they usually have a short life (Overmann & Kuder, [2018](#)). Therefore, frequently, institutions that develop joint programmes employ additional staff for the coordination of the project and to maintain – among other things – the liaison with the partners inside the consortium (Overmann & Kuder, [2018](#)) because wide-ranging projects require increasingly multi-professional approaches to be delivered (Whitchurch, [2006](#), [2015](#)).

Despite significant growth in funding, scholarships, and participating universities, researchers in higher education have paid little attention to the EMJMDs (Marques et al., [2022](#)). The available studies (European Commission, [2013](#); European Commission, [2014](#); European Commission, [2016](#); European Commission, [2022](#); European Commission et al., [2024](#); European Commission & European Education and Culture Executive Agency, [2021](#); YERUN, [2018](#)) mainly focus on student experience, employability, institutional data, number of participants, and academic aspects rather than staff interactions behind the scenes. This is unfortunate, because it should be acknowledged that both professional staff and academics play a crucial role in

developing and implementing these degree programmes. The first group is in charge of creating or adjusting the institutional framework necessary for the effective functioning of the EMJMDs. This involves specialised knowledge and experience in project management, resource allocation, visa procedures, joint diplomas, European projects, quality assurance and other areas. Academics in turn contribute to the programme with their educational expertise, scholarly connections and scientific knowledge. This collaboration aims to create a joint curriculum that excels in innovative teaching methods and content to meet the excellence and high standards required for the EMJMDs.

1.2.2 New Spaces in Higher Education

Celia Whitchurch ([2008a](#), [2013](#)) introduced the term *Third Space* in higher education to designate an area where there is a growing blurring of margins separating professional staff and academics (Sebalj et al., [2012](#)). Bhabha's ([1994](#)) conceptualisation of *Third Space* implies a place where cultures, groups, and identities converge, share views and understandings, and work together to arrive at novel insights (Obexer, [2022](#)) allowing individuals to interact with and jointly create alternate identities (Veles et al., [2023a](#)). In addition, Soja ([2009](#)) declared: "Third space is a meeting point, a hybrid place, where one can move beyond the existing borders" (Soja, [2009](#), p. 56). Other scholars such as Akerman ([2020](#)), Veles ([2020](#), [2023a](#), [2023b](#)), Bossu and Brown ([2018](#)), Smith et al., ([2021](#)), and McIntosh and Nutt ([2022](#)) deepened the topic and the *Third Space* became more used as more staff members realised their duties were entering on this collaborative area where people put their knowledge to achieve academy-set goals.

The *Third Space* allows us to view the collaboration with colleagues as a conversation that produces outcomes for all involved (Bamford & Moschini, [2024](#)). However, as stated by Whitchurch ([2013](#)), the rise of *Third Space* environments raises questions about whether they are intentionally designed or naturally occurring and allows us to examine the various factors that affect their development. Furthermore, this situation prompts queries into the opportunities,

challenges, and motivations of individuals working in these spaces and how they view their roles (Whitchurch, [2013](#)).

While a comprehensive study of the definition and terminology associated with professional staff is not included in my research, it is important to underline that this is an area that needs further investigation because “[t]he restructuring of the administrative staff is in all likelihood not an isolated phenomenon, but a change that is connected to larger alterations in the university system and society in general” (Gornitzka & Larsen, [2004](#), p. 466). Hence, only a brief description is presented in the following chapter, and among the available nomenclature, the term that I used within this study is professional staff. Although this term is not used everywhere, it has been officially recognised in Australia by the Association for Tertiary Education Management (ATEM) and the Association of University Administrators (AUA) in the United Kingdom, promoting its dissemination throughout the world’s higher education sector. (Veles, [2023b](#)). In light of this, I use it to designate all those individuals working in administrative positions (managerial, administrative and technical staff) who work in departments and faculties – or their equivalents – and in other institutional units as well.

A New Category: Blended professionals

Whitchurch ([2008a](#)) coined the term “*Third Space* professional” or “blended professional” to describe a setting where diverse functions are combined, moving beyond historic binaries and strict categories. In higher education it refers to an individual who contributes to, and in part participates in, both the professional and the academic realms (Whitchurch, [2009](#)). Primarily, the concept was founded to describe academic and professional individuals developing skill sets and carrying out tasks beyond the scope of their job descriptions (Campbell, [2024](#)). A shift has led to the hybrid or *Third Space* roles: staff who work for the central administration in close conjunction with academic colleagues to provide greater internal coordination of management processes (Middlehurst, [2013](#)).

These practitioners are important to the academy because they can adapt to change, provide additional services, and share and apply their expertise across boundaries (Campbell, [2024](#)). For this reason, the blended professional is becoming an increasingly common figure across higher education institutions, with individuals partially participating in intricate practices and projects (Whitchurch, [2015](#); Beer, [2022](#); Obexer, [2022](#); Campbell-Perry, [2022](#)) and enhancing their credibility through their expertise and performance (Moran & Misra, [2018](#)). According to Gray ([2015](#)), *Third Space* professionals may hold official titles as either academic or professional staff, but these designations do not fully capture the interdisciplinary nature of their work because their roles often include responsibilities that transcend these traditional designations. They might be academics fulfilling managerial duties, or professional staff actively involved in teaching or research tasks, such as creating online educational resources or providing specialised research assistance (Gray, [2015](#)).

Because of this, those who operate in the *Third Space* are recognised for assisting in bridging the gap between discourses (Campbell, [2024](#)), smoothing out the differences and tensions between the two primary staff groups within higher education institutions: professional staff and academics. These differences, also called the ‘divide’, have historical origins and many factors have contributed to reinforce them, such as the increased bureaucratisation of universities (Finkielsztejn & Wagner, [2023](#)), economic pressure (Shepherd, [2018](#)) and professional staff professionalisation (Sebalj et al., [2012](#)), amongst other reasons.

1.2.3 Collaboration as the Key Element to Succeed

As underlined by Briody et al. ([2022](#)), higher education scholarly research primarily focuses on professors and students but the significant contributions of professional staff, who support the work of academics and students, have received little attention and understanding. Although professional staff do not teach in traditional classroom settings, their work contributes to the overall student experience (Noltemeyer, [2014](#)), and an effective internationalisation strategy

acknowledges the equal importance of all staff members, whether academics or professional staff, and actively promotes their participation (Hunter et al., [2018](#)) in the different institutional activities.

Within this framework, EMJMDs can be considered *Third Space* settings capable of bringing together professional staff and academics and activate close interactions between these two groups via a supportive collaboration. Following Mattessich and Johnson's ([2018](#)) definition, the collaboration within an EMJMD comprises a commitment to shared objectives, as well as a common structure, accountability for achievement, mutual authority, collective responsibility, and distribution of resources and benefits. Existing studies on EMJMDs (European Commission, [2013](#); European Commission, [2014](#); European Commission, [2016](#); European Commission, [2022](#); European Commission et al., [2024](#); European Commission & European Education and Culture Executive Agency, [2021](#); YERUN, [2018](#)) predominantly focus on student experiences in terms of challenges and success stories, mobility, and institutional prestige. There is a shortage of scientific work from the perspective of the workforce behind the scenes of these degrees even if staff play a crucial role in equipping students with the essential new skills needed to navigate the evolving world environment (Hunter et al., [2018](#)). Even more, current research provides information related to the type of degree awarded, accreditation issues, type of cooperation, students' employability and others (Obst et al., [2011](#)). However, as highlighted by Fourie-Malherbe et al. ([2016](#)), "[t]he fact that joint degrees are issued in the framework of partnerships between higher education institutions located in different countries and issuing their degrees within different higher education systems, gives rise to a host of other interesting issues" (Fourie-Malherbe et al., [2016](#), p. 317).

1.3 Scope and Importance of My Research

My study aims to develop a comprehensive understanding of the collaborative dynamics between professional staff, academics and blended professionals within an unexplored *Third Space* and

grasp the characteristics of their relationship. Specifically, it seeks to explore whether the essence of their collaboration within this unique setting is distinct and, if so, how and why.

While exploring the features of their relationship, I wanted to validate the effectiveness of this collaboration and verify whether there were changes regarding the historical ‘divide’ between staff categories. Therefore, aspects such as the interaction and teamwork while designing, implementing and managing these complex environments were comprehensively discussed. Likewise, the roles professional staff undertake, their credibility, the acknowledgement of their contributions, the impact of their work on the overall programme, the decision-making authority, and the relationships within their institutions were considered. Furthermore, I also looked to investigate this collaboration’s personal and institutional implications to identify tangible best practices that could be replicated in other institutional settings. In a single illustration, Figure 1.1, my focus is summarised. It represents the *Third Space* of an EMJMD, in which different staff groups enter to develop an international project and my aim is to understand what happens within that space in terms of their collaborative – or not – relationship.

The importance of my research project was to describe – through the development of the Theoretical and Conceptual Framework, and empirical understanding – the reasons, nuances and changes of the collaboration that takes place between different staff categories in EMJMDs settings. In order to obtain the detailed information needed to deeply understand the research topic, I developed two main Research Questions and four sub questions:

Research Question #1: To what extent does the experience of working in EMJMDs change the effectiveness of staff collaboration within and across the universities involved?

Sub questions:

- (i) What are the evolving characteristics of the professional staff-academic collaboration in EMJMDs?
- (ii) What are the key factors influencing these changes?

Research Question #2: Is the experience of working in EMJMDs changing the understanding of staff collaboration?

Sub questions:

- (i) What is the added value of collaboration within EMJMDs for the staff involved?
- (ii) How is this collaboration enhancing the recognition of the role and the work performed by professional staff?

Figure 1.1 – Focus of this Study

Source: Author's own work.

1.4 My Assumptions: The EMJMDs setting help to overcome the “Divide”

A positive relationship among higher education staff benefits everyone involved, especially the students who receive a high-quality teaching and learning experience. The essential elements of positive relationships are trust and respect for each other's roles, work, knowledge, and performance. These factors impact motivation, engagement, job satisfaction and workplace well-being and promote psychological safety, innovation, and teamwork (O'Brien & Guiney, [2018](#)). On the contrary, a lack of trust and respect can lead to conflicts, high turnover, and decreased productivity (Tytherleigh et al., [2005](#)).

My study expected that due to the close working relationship among professional staff and academics within an EMJMD, the historical “divide” between these two staff categories was overcome. Consequently, the study was guided by the following assumptions: (i) the EMJMDs allow all staff categories working on them to develop close collaborations based on trust and mutual respect for each other's capabilities; (ii) the EMJMDs offer professional staff a safe environment where their work, skills and expertise are acknowledged and valued; and (iii) the EMJMDs are unique international programmes which provide all individuals involved (staff and students) with a truly life-changing experience.

1.5 Structure of My Dissertation: A Brief Description of the Chapters

My dissertation has nine chapters organised as follows. Chapter Two presents the academic literature related to my research topics. Firstly, I present the evolution and structural changes in higher education institutions and their impact on staff, such as professionalisation in higher education. Secondly, I describe three realities currently present in the higher education landscape, i.e., the “division” between categories of personnel, the internationalisation of higher education and the EMJMD as the case study that will be observed in this research, and the concept of *Third Space* with the emergence of blended professionals. Third, I present the intricate idea of collaboration, the competencies needed to collaborate, and the importance of teamwork and good collaborative practices.

Chapter Three explores the theories and concepts that form the foundation of the Theoretical Framework supporting this research, specifically focusing on the notions of “division”, the *Third Space*, and interprofessional collaboration. It also elaborates on the Conceptual Framework developed for this study, which encompasses three main dimensions: Collaborative Mindset, Team Effectiveness, and Job Satisfaction.

Chapter Four details the research design employed in this study, specifically the sequential Explanatory Sequential Mixed-methods approach. It outlines the tools utilised for data

collection during the quantitative and qualitative phases, highlighting how each phase contributed to the findings. Additionally, this chapter discusses my role as a researcher, emphasising the importance of maintaining objectivity to prevent bias and the ethical considerations throughout the research process. By addressing these elements, the chapter establishes a solid foundation for understanding the methodology behind the study and ensures that the research is conducted rigorously.

Chapter Five outlines the steps involved in the quantitative phase of the study, detailing the distribution of the online questionnaire, the selection of variables, the analytical strategy employed, as well as the findings of this data collection phase. The results indicated that team spirit was not only fundamental but also a driving force behind the overall success of the EMJMDs observed, fostering collaboration, motivation, and a shared commitment to achieve this common goal.

Chapter Six provides a comprehensive presentation of the results from the qualitative phase of the study. This chapter explains the implementation of the interview protocol, the tool for gathering in-depth insights from participants. The analysis of the interview data led to the identification of three overarching themes: the singularity of the EMJMDs, the characteristics of the higher education institutions involved, and the personal and interpersonal perspectives of those working in the EMJMDs involved in this research.

Chapter Seven offers a comprehensive analysis of the key findings by examining the results from the research's qualitative and quantitative phases, directly addressing the Research Questions that guided my study. The answers to these questions are derived from the evidence gathered and by synthesising the qualitative and quantitative data to provide robust and well-supported responses. This approach ensures that the research questions are answered clearly, coherently, and evidence-based.

Chapter Eight provides a comprehensive summary of the study's conclusions, offering a clear and concise overview of the key takeaways. This chapter presents the expected results of the research, highlighting the anticipated impact and significance of the findings.

Chapter Nine offers my reflection on my interest in the topic and the motivations behind selecting it for study. This chapter allows me to share my perspective and journey, underscoring the topic's significance. This personal description highlights the nature of my PhD transformative journey itself. By sharing my story, I invite the reader to engage with my research on a deeper level, fostering a sense of connection with the study's outcomes.

1.6 Concluding Remarks

My study extended the existing research related to the *Third Space* by analysing the complex collaborative environment of EMJMDs. As Veles et al. (2018) stated, the implication of *Third Space* proliferation is not only the redefinition of professional borders but also leads to the ratification of new working practices, the development of new collaborative skills, and further integration among professions (Veles et al., 2018). Under this perspective, EMJMDs represent an excellent scenario for improving the environment of those working in the *Third Space* of these degrees to offer new collaborative approaches and more egalitarian relationships between professional staff and academics.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

The evolution of higher education institutions is a dynamic and multifaceted process shaped by social, economic, and technological factors, which also modify the working environment of staff categories. Hence, to understand the current state of the art, it is necessary to be familiar with these changes as well as with the perceptions, priorities and feelings of professional staff and academics and the interactions between these two groups. This literature review is organised in chronological order to present the different topics, show how they are related, and identify gaps in the literature. Figure 2.1 visually illustrates the interconnectedness of these topics, offering a holistic perspective on the research problem under investigation.

Figure 2.1 – Topics Examined within this Literature Review

Source: Author's own work

2.2 The Evolution of Higher Education Institutions

During the 21st century, higher education became a central venue for sustaining knowledge economies (Sam & van der Sijde, [2014](#)), by increasingly focusing on skills and employability (Sam & van der Sijde, [2014](#); Tuononen et al., [2022](#)) in response to the changing demands of the job market. This shift has led to the integration of experiential learning, internships, and cooperative education programmes, because these collaborations serve to provide funding sources and are also platforms for reciprocal learning and joint implementation (European Commission, [2012](#)), as is the case of the EMJMDs. “Modern, knowledge-based economies require people with higher and more relevant skills” (European Commission, [2012](#), p. 3), and in the technologically driven economies of the 21st century, the competencies acquired through higher education or other postsecondary education are highly valued since higher education degrees hold notable significance in modern society (Altbach, [1999](#)) and it is believed that a higher education degree improves one’s quality of life (Owens & Lane, [2014](#)).

In parallel to these changes, higher education institutions have also experienced structural transformations driven by environmental pressures and, in part, by the aspirations emerging from new generations of staff (Whitchurch & Gordon, [2010a](#)). This involves professional staff in particular, whose identity has experienced significant changes in recent decades (Leece & Jaquet, [2017](#)) due to current collective expectations placed on higher education institutions (Bossu & Brown, [2018](#)) in terms of performance, interaction with industry and wider society, and quality assurance and excellence in education, which requires staff with specific skills.

2.2.1 Professionalisation of Higher Education

A consequence of the aforementioned transformations over the past decades is the expansion of higher education institution professional staff. This is a result of the restructuring of administrative positions as a societal change related to the professionalisation of the workforce in general (Gornitzka & Larsen, [2004](#)), which leads “to a significantly different mix of participants

within university administration” (Gornitzka & Larsen, [2004](#), p. 467). This multilayered phenomenon is connected with market-oriented approaches, growing competition, different institutional missions, and new organisational frameworks (Baltaru & Nuhoglu Soysal, [2018](#)). According to Szekeres ([2004](#)), the work of professional staff in higher education has a multifunctional approach because:

[I]s about either supporting the work of academic staff, dealing with students on non-academic matters or working in an administrative function such as finance, human resources, marketing, public relations, business development, student administration, academic administration, library, information technology, capital or property (Szekeres, [2004](#), p. 8).

Furthermore, administrative restructuring is not only part of a broad renovation and significant change in higher education institution management, but also a broader workforce professionalisation in society in general (Gornitzka & Larsen, [2004](#)). In the 1960s and 1970s, staff with formal qualifications replaced those with clerical competencies in different organisations as well as in the higher education institution environment where the development of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) changed the administrative systems for dealing with financial and human resources, and student management (Gornitzka & Larsen, [2004](#)). Additionally, as noted by Gornitzka and Larsen ([2004](#)), the late 1980s and the 1990s saw significant shifts in the dynamic between governments and higher education institutions related to legal obligations for the institutions and brought subsequent changes around finances, budgeting, and human resources.

Even if it is not possible to characterise professional staff as a homogenous profession, there is a clear path towards its professionalisation (Gornitzka & Larsen, [2004](#)). In this context, Whitchurch and Gordon ([2010b](#)) affirmed that institutions needed diverse expertise, recruiting personnel with advanced management functions, organisational development roles, and cross-sector knowledge, which has challenged traditional hierarchies and structures. Predictably, joint

work involving professional staff and academics emerged, and changes in hiring patterns aimed at acquiring more professional staff with specific skills (Briody et al., [2022](#)).

Definition and Key Elements of Professionalisation

DiMaggio and Powell ([1991](#)) defined professionalisation as “the collective struggle of members of an occupation to define the conditions and methods of their work, [...], and to establish a cognitive base and legitimation for their occupational autonomy” (DiMaggio & Powell, [1991](#), p. 70). Based on their work, Gornitzka and Larsen ([2004](#)) suggested a primary definition of professionalisation in higher education institutions which encompasses four elements: (i) the increased formal status of administrative positions; (ii) the significant number of academic qualification requirements for administrative roles; (iii) the need for a shared cognitive basis; and (iv) the increased number and formalisation of associations of employees in administrative positions (Gornitzka & Larsen, [2004](#) pp. 462-63).

Nonetheless, as Rixom ([2011](#)) mentioned, defining the professionalisation of staff working in higher education institutions while preserving the essence of higher education provides an ethical dimension to the process. Consequently, the author specified that in higher education institutions, “[t]he wider characteristics of professionalisation include the possession of a body of knowledge, the ability to self regulate and a shared service ethic” (Rixom, [2011](#), p. 19). This means that it is essential to delineate the knowledge requirements of higher education groups and professions by establishing standards, outcomes, or competencies (Robson, [2006](#)).

Reforms Impacting Professional Staff in Higher Education Institutions

In higher education, “[t]he role of professional administrative and support staff is becoming pivotal as the sector becomes more competitive, more business and market focused, and more international” (Wild & Wooldridge, [2009](#), p. 5). Bosu and Brown ([2018](#)) described the various roles that have appeared in higher education institutions, encompassing areas such as teaching

and learning, quality administration, external relations, academic development, and research administration, among others. However, professional staff still face challenges constructing their identities due to a lack of a predefined script (Ryttberg & Geschwind, [2019](#)). For this reason, they establish their legitimacy through techniques and procedures, such as methods, models, routines, and support for academics, which serve as predefined toolboxes in their roles (Ryttberg, [2022](#)).

Whitchurch ([2008b](#)) explained the complexities and dynamism of professional staff identities, mentioning that these professionals are more active and move across practical and established borders “to create new professional spaces, knowledge, relationships and legitimacies” (p. 375). Veles et al. ([2023a](#)) reaffirmed this tendency by declaring that the evolution of professional identities among higher education institution staff now sees the traditional roles in teaching and research overlapping with additional missions, such as community engagement and internationalisation, blurring previously delineated boundaries between roles.

Professional Staff – A Discussed Nomenclature

During the mid-2000s a description of professionals without academic contracts but with administrative and management roles in academic units and specific areas such as finance, fundraising, human resources, online learning and others, appeared (Whitchurch, [2017](#)). As a result, the term “professional staff” has been used since then due to the growing specialisation and professionalisation of this group, and changes in staff identities and roles (Sebalj, [2012](#)). Conway ([2012](#)) described professional staff as individuals responsible for performing “tasks associated with managing learning, teaching, research, and corporate functions” (p. 38).

However, as explained earlier, professional staff identities are not easily defined, and there have been many misunderstandings about their roles (Whitchurch, [2017](#)). Furthermore, these individuals have been overlooked in scientific research (Graham, [2012](#)). Only recently scholars have investigated the involvement of professional staff in solving higher education

issues (Gravett & Winestone, [2018](#); Graham, [2018](#)) bringing to light their institutional contribution. Therefore, a variety of labels are applied to them, including: assistant, clerical staff, general staff, administrators, professional staff, managerial professionals, secretaries, support staff (Szekeres, [2011](#); Conway, [2012](#); Sebalj et al., [2012](#); Whitchurch, [2017](#)). Moreover, as highlighted by Pitman ([2000](#)), it is worth mentioning that studies on administrative staff in higher education institutions were mainly formulated by academics, which usually focused on their areas of concern and in the higher education institutions' aims of teaching and research. This means that administrative tasks were considered as a means to facilitate the teaching and research goals, and the role of professional staff to some extent was ignored (Pitman, [2000](#)) since they were seen only as facilitators of the academic activities and not, as underlined by Graham ([2012](#)), key resources in a higher education institution.

Similarly, other scholars have noted a significant gap between academic research and the needs of practitioners in higher education. This gap arises from the limited involvement of professional staff and policymakers in shaping research agendas (Keller, [1985](#); Kezar, [2000](#)). Furthermore, Kezar ([2000](#)) argued that higher education research often focuses too heavily on internal academic issues rather than considering broader impacts. As a result, it tends to lack practitioners' perspectives and practical applications, ultimately failing to address the critical problems related to equity, inclusivity, and adaptability in response to evolving societal needs (Kezar, [2000](#)). In addition, following Terenzini ([1996](#)), research should be written in a way that is accessible to non-academic audiences, including institutional leaders, the public in general and policymakers to re-engage with public policy issues. After nearly two decades, Dee ([2014](#)) called on scholars to study higher education organisation, administration, and leadership grounded in practice and engaging practitioners to obtain information more readily applied to the realities of higher education administration.

Szekeres (2011) described changes in the literature related to the management and operations of higher education institutions, and indicated the literature especially expanded on topics such as: (i) academics and professional staff working together; (ii) the fragility of the relationship between academics and professional staff; (iii) the role of senior and middle management in higher education institutions; (iv) roles and functions in higher education; and (v) professionalisation of staff (Szekeres, 2011). Nevertheless, even if some changes had occurred, the same author also declared that “[t]here is still an uneasy relationship between academic and professional staff and there are still a number of professional staff who see their work as being ‘invisible’ in the university” (Szekeres, 2011, pp. 688-689).

More recently, Lavigne (2021) examined the complex nature of higher education administration in Canada and the research approaches used to study it over the past fifty years. The study analysed 38 articles published in the Canadian Journal of Higher Education between 1971 and 2020. Most of these articles referenced publications from North America, with very few citing researches from other regions. The results indicated that professional staff face challenges related to role conflict, resource limitations, values in decision-making, and managing power within the institutional system (Lavigne, 2021). Vander Kloet and Campisi (2023) explored the subjectification of professional staff within the academic system, particularly in the Canadian context. The authors utilised Whitchurch's (2008a) concept of the *Third Space* to describe the ambiguous position of blended professionals, who navigate the blurred lines between academic and non-academic roles. Their findings highlighted the often-unseen labor of these professionals and how they negotiate their identities and roles to gain legitimacy and recognition within the complex academic landscape (Vander Kloet & Campisi, 2023).

It is highly plausible that further research on the administration of higher education institutions, as well as the roles and experiences of all staff involved, is needed. Their perspectives, expertise, and evolving needs should be actively integrated into the higher education research agenda. Doing so will not only enrich our understanding of institutional

dynamics but also complement the existing knowledge focused primarily on academic aspects, fostering a more holistic and comprehensive approach to higher education research. Professional staff now form a substantial segment of staff at higher education institutions. Their representation expanded significantly in quantity and expertise, encompassing a broad spectrum of responsibilities, including basic clerical work services to highly skilled responsibilities such as internationalisation, business contacts, and research projects (Ryttberg & Geschwind, [2021](#)). For example, in the 2010s, professional staff made up more than half of the higher education institution workforce in Australia (Graham, [2012](#)), and nowadays in the same country, the proportion of professional staff to academics continues to increase (Croucher & Woelert, [2022](#)).

It is clear that even if professional staff are “no longer the ‘invisible workers’, professionals still have some way to go to claim their space in universities” (Szekeres, [2011](#), p. 689). For this reason, as cited by Szekeres ([2004](#)), Conway affirmed, “the stories of administrative staff need to be heard” (Szekeres, [2004](#), p. 20), since the acknowledgement of their work is fundamental and recognition from academics, institutions and government is still needed (Conway, [2000](#)). Only through reciprocal appreciation, genuine interest, and continuous respect all staff members are enabled to transcend borders searching for new experiences, which in turn, enriches them and their relationships (Veles, [2023b](#)).

Shifting Identities of Academic Staff

“Despite the general assumption that the academic body represents the core component of higher education institutions, since the mid-twentieth century administrative resourcing has been rivalling and, at times, outpacing that of academics” (Baltaru & Nuhoğlu Soysal, [2018](#), p. 214). As a result, there are signs that a new era of professional identity is emerging for academics due to the increasing presence of strategic specialists. This challenges traditional academic identities, including authority and autonomy (McInnis, [2010](#)), requiring academics to redefine their identity and work relationships in the face of blurred functioning roles.

McInnis also (2010) indicated, “[t]he impact of the changing dynamics in the workplace has significant implications for individual academic faculty and their sense of identity” (p. 162). For example, the roles of higher education institution leaders, such as pro-vice-chancellors and vice-chancellors, are evolving from traditional academic responsibilities to encompass management, business, and commercial capabilities, including skills in negotiation, leadership, and engagement with local and international communities, which reflects the current societal role and interconnectedness of higher education institutions (Middlehurst, 2010). According to Macfarlane (2011), the traditional academic role, once integrated teaching, research, and service as a unified whole, is becoming increasingly fragmented into specialised functions. This division of academic responsibilities has given rise to "para-academics"—professionals who concentrate on specific areas of academic practice, such as educational development or research management, rather than embracing the comprehensive role of a well-rounded academic (Macfarlane, 2011). This shift is closely linked to the casualisation of academic positions, resulting in a growing number of non-tenured roles that contribute to job insecurity and increased work pressures, making it challenging for academics to fulfil all aspects of traditional academic practice (Macfarlane, 2011). Furthermore, this fragmentation has blurred the lines between academics and professional staff, creating ambiguous academic identities and potentially undermining the collective memory of academia’s core purposes (Macfarlane, 2011).

To deep dive into the challenges experienced by academics, the “Changing Academic Profession” (CAP) comparative study, coordinated by William Cummings in 2007, surveyed the academic profession across 19 countries, highlighting the evolving nature of academia, the importance of internationalisation², and the issues including declining prestige and varying

² Specifically (i) research cooperation with international partners; (ii) scholar mobility; (iii) publishing in a foreigner language; (iv) willingness to relocate for work across national boundaries; (v) internationalising research and teaching;

working conditions (Höhle & Teichler, [2013](#); Teichler et al., [2013](#)). Since roughly half of the scholars involved in the CAP study had taken part in the Carnegie Survey³, they served as the foundation for an additional sub-analysis of how much the circumstances and perspectives of the academic community had evolved over time (Teichler et al., [2013](#)). Additionally, the CAP study led to two further comparative investigations in the field: The Academic Profession in Europe: Responses to Societal Change (EUROAC) in Germany and another one in Asia conducted by Japanese researchers (Teichler et al., [2013](#)), allowing a global understanding of the system's overall changes as a result of its quick growth and the evolving societal roles of higher education.

A few years later, in 2014, initiated the APKIS project: The Academic Profession in the Knowledge-Based Society with the aim of creating a comparison survey for academics approximately ten years after the CAP project. It also incorporates new elements and areas of focus such as the acknowledgment of the potential reorientation of academia and higher education in relation to the knowledge economy and/or society (Jones et al., [2023](#)). Surveys were distributed in 2019-2020 and included research groups from 22 nations on 5 continents. The surveys encompassed topics such as function, working conditions, career paths and opportunities, demands and expectations for using research, instruction to support social improvement and economic prosperity (Aarrevaara et al., [2021](#)). Over time, knowledge appears

(vi) teaching in a different language or overseas; and (vii) being involved with international students in mobility (Rostan et al., [2013](#)).

³ The Carnegie Foundation for the Advancement of Teaching (Princeton, New Jersey, USA) conducted the first academic profession survey in 1969. It examined the professor's working and employment conditions, documented the changing demographic profile, and discussed their views, principles, and perspectives. After two decades, the Carnegie Survey of the Academic Profession was promoted by Ernest L. Boyer in 1992 to identify whether academics worldwide faced similar challenges the Americans faced in their profession. Data on demographics, employment and work conditions, time spent on different activities, attitudes toward teaching and learning, academic institution governance, and motivation were gathered in this first international survey (Teichler et al., [2013](#); Teichler & Höhle, [2013](#)).

to be required more and more to show how it relates to economic development and technical innovation, as well as to cultural identity and social well-being (Teichler & Höhle, 2013).

As a result, there is an increased number of management professionals within higher education institutions, which suggests that management practices become more professionalised (Brennan, 2007). Therefore, functions, duties, and roles become more specialised, requiring specific knowledge, constantly updated information, and explicit competencies (Schneijderberg & Merkator, 2013). In this context, a set of professionals who are not actively involved in research and teaching but able to formulate management choices and establish core services arise. They were called by Whitchurch (2008a) “*Third Space* professionals” or “blended professionals”⁴ and presented by Klumpp and Teichler (2008) as “Hochschulprofessionelle” or “higher education professionals (HEPROs). According to Schneijderberg and Merkator (2013), in the survey conducted by Klumpp and Teichler in 2015, the HEPROs were a heterogeneous group of professionals highly trained, meeting the increasing need of university administration for systematic knowledge and were experts on the institutional core functions.

Nevertheless, managerialism's effects are complex and have generated a lot of discussion because when management techniques are used in an academic setting, frequently give efficiency, accountability, and performance measures precedence over conventional academic principles (Höhle & Teichler, 2013). Consequently, academics develop a new professional identity as a result of adaptation to these managerial needs but also “as a response to the presence of the new generation of specialist staff in the contemporary university who increasingly expect parity of status as professionals in their own right, and who also compete with academics for status and authority” (McInnis, 2010, p. 148). In addition, academics who previously assumed managerial

⁴ See also chapter 1: Section 1.2.2 New Spaces in Higher Education – A New Category: Blended professionals and chapter 2: Section 2.3.3 The Concept and Features of a *Third Space* Setting – The Escalation of Blended Professionals.

and leadership roles within higher education institutions now see professional staff engaging in academic tasks such as learning design, learning support, and career development as a new common reality (Hobson et al., [2018](#)), giving space for different types of interaction as within an EMJMD, where professional staff and academics work together for the benefit of a common objective.

2.3 Three Interconnected Realities Shaping the Current Higher Education Landscape

Given the outlined institutional and staff transformations, three interconnected effects emerged, which will be elaborated further in the following sections since each one contributed to the current evolving landscape of higher education. The first is the notable impact on organisational culture and dynamics of higher education institutions, such as the traditional hierarchies and power balances that affect the relationships between professional staff and academics.

Secondly, there was an escalation of the internationalisation of higher education and its multiple aspects, which includes cooperation between higher education institutions to foster research programmes, the development of joint degrees, and the promotion of student mobility to improve professional skills and advance interculturality. Finally, new spaces populated by different staff categories, such as academics and professional staff, offer the potential for enhanced collaboration. These staff groups work together in certain areas and projects in which the expertise of both groups is required.

2.3.1 The Historical 'Divide'

Traditionally, staff in higher education have been categorised in binary terms, i.e., the administrative and academic domains, with strong hierarchical relationship (Hobson et al., [2018](#)) and tensions, placing the academics at the centre and holding the authority, and professional staff downgraded to the periphery and acting as support (Clark, [1998](#)). Clashes between academic expectations and professional staff's increasing authority regarding strategic priorities,

budget allocations, organisational restructuring and decision-making (Bess & Dee, [2014](#)) increased the pressure. Even more, the attention given to economic development (Young & Pinheiro, [2022](#)), the connection between economic growth and the capacity to obtain and apply scientific, technical, and economic knowledge proliferated (Siddiqui, [2014](#)), modifying the institutions' goals. Besides, the assumption that higher education will help to improve economic competitiveness globally (Buckner, [2017](#)), the burden on institutions to increase their productivity while using public funds (Alexander, [2000](#)), the escalation of bureaucracy (Coccia, [2009](#)), and the prevalence of managerialism that decreased academic authority (Shepherd, [2018](#)) influenced even more negatively the interaction among these staff groups ([Appendix A](#) – Factors Influencing the 'Divide').

This conflict has been especially salient in recent years as higher education has undergone significant changes in goals, structure, and staffing (Bess & Dee, [2014](#)). To go deeper into this topic, Conway ([2012](#)) studied this dysfunctional relationship and described the competitive relationship between the two groups by using the term 'divide' as “shorthand for the academic-administrator relationship” (Conway, [2012](#), p. 39). It is written between inverted commas because according to this author, even if the term was commonly used, it was not well understood by either professional staff or academics (Conway, [2012](#)).

The instability of these relationships can be partly contributed to intrinsic differences in how academics and professional staff think, prioritise, and are motivated. For example, the conflict between the academic profession and corporate managerialism, along with cultural differences, institutional logic, and misaligned motivational structures, often leads to communication breakdowns, power imbalances, and mutual distrust (Seyd, [2000](#); Vican et al., [2019](#); Kuo, [2009](#)). Furthermore, academics prioritise intellectual freedom and disciplinary values, while professional staff focus on operational efficiency and centralised goals, resulting in a divergent worldview (Seyd, [2000](#); Vican et al., [2019](#)). Academics typically operate under norms such as autonomy and research excellence, whereas professional staff adopt corporate or

institutional principles emphasising accountability and financial metrics, which can conflict with academic pursuits (Vican et al., [2019](#)). Additionally, academics are incentivised by publications and teaching outcomes, while professional staff often underline cost savings, enrolment growth, and external compliance (Vican et al., [2019](#); Kuo, [2009](#)).

Similarly, Del Favero and Bray ([2005](#)) described, for example, academics pay attention to decision-making that affects their agendas, while professional staff handle matters that impact the broader institutional community. Regarding priorities, academics are focused on their autonomy, in contrast to professional staff, who try to reach a compromise if this is the way to solve issues. When it comes to motivation, professional staff values responsiveness and efficiency, whereas academics value creativity and the unrestricted search for knowledge, acknowledging that compromise is a fundamental component of decision-making (Del Favero & Bray, [2005](#)).

Currently, scholars have contrasting opinions about the 'divide'. On the one hand, this division seems to be a product of social construction, arising from divergent perspectives and isolated working practices that continue through the ongoing perception that professional staff exist in the shadow of academics and not being regarded as equals in terms of their contributions and value (Caldwell, [2022a](#)). On the other hand, since this intricate and multidimensional issue has evolved, professional staff are now seen as multi-disciplinary – positive disruptors – who can benefit higher education institutions, even if they also question the perception that higher education institutions' management is an academic competence (Akerman, [2020](#); Bess & Dee, [2014](#)). Consequently, their managerialist style with a team-based approach became strong to improve service, efficiency and reliability (Wheeldon et al., [2022](#)), and higher education institutions can now be seen as a community of experts dedicated to advancing knowledge, regardless of their involvement in academic fields, providing an alternative view to the traditional hierarchical structure (Rybkowska & Godonoga, [2023](#)).

Bridging the gap between different staff categories in higher education institutions requires fostering effective communication, collaboration, and understanding each group's needs and challenges. Institutions must promote a cooperative relationship among all staff members, built on trust and respect for each other's roles, regardless of qualifications or job titles, since a division hinders the achievement of institutional goals. This dissertation addresses the 'divide' from the perspective of an international project because the role of professional staff is crucial in providing academics with the resources and infrastructure they require to succeed in such complicated projects. By working together and nurturing solid relationships, academics and professional staff can cultivate a more efficient and effective institution that benefits students, staff, and all stakeholders involved.

2.3.2 Joint Programmes as Key Elements in the European Internationalisation Strategy

Overmann and Kuder ([2018](#)) mentioned that the interest from higher education institutions in tactical partnerships demonstrates their commitment in achieving goals that are part of a broad internationalisation strategy. As a result, joint programmes are usually part of this strategy and have a pivotal role because they “address the heartland of academia – the teaching/learning process and the production of new knowledge between and among countries” (Knight, [2008](#), p. 22). Furthermore, cooperation between higher education institutions can be seen as another effect of the evolution of higher education, and joint programmes derived from this cooperation are internationalisation activities that encompasses multiple aspects, where “[a]ll involved in these programmes tend to take for granted the quite remarkable learning opportunities which are provided to students, staff and institutions” (European University Association, [2004](#), p. 12).

Policy reforms in Europe like the Bologna Declaration emphasised the importance of educational cooperation for accomplishing peace and democracy in societies, as a means “to boost growth and jobs and to foster social equity and inclusion” (European Commission, [2014](#), p. 9):

Joint programmes have been encouraged by the Bologna Process and listed on the agenda of all the Bologna conferences since Prague 2001. During the Bologna conference in Berlin in 2003, ministers explicitly agreed on supporting the development and quality assurance of integrated curricula leading to joint degrees (Stichting EP-Nuffic, [2015](#), p. 14).

For the European Union, joint programmes were seen as the mechanism to improve attractiveness, competitiveness and acknowledgement of European higher education institutions. Additionally, “[t]he concept of joint programmes as a means for internationalisation has spread globally, probably in response to European developments” (Stichting EP-Nuffic, [2015](#), p. 15). However, after decades of expertise and hundreds of courses in various disciplines, confusion regarding the definition and types of joint programmes is a common issue, as stated by Spinelli ([2013](#)):

When speaking of Joint and Double Degree it is necessary to define our subject since on this issue, one can notice a great ambiguity in the terminology. Considering the great diffusion of the phenomenon, particularly in Europe, this is a serious problem (Spinelli, [2013](#), p. 117)

Characteristics, Terminology and definitions of Joint Programmes

Cross-border and cross-functional partnerships (Veles et al., [2018](#)) are examples of environments where joint programmes represent the highest level of association. They require that academic and administrative units with resources and specific competencies create proper communication procedures and a clear modus operandi both internally and with partner institutions (Overmann & Kuder, [2018](#)). The fields of expertise needed for a joint programme are in domains such as curriculum design, quality assurance, teaching and learning methods, recognition, accreditation, admissions, legal aspects, study abroad, marketing and much more (Overmann & Kuder, [2018](#)). The professional staff – who work in areas frequently seen as peripheral functions – in these projects become more central (Ryttberg & Geschwind, [2017](#)), fulfilling new and specific tasks

and, in that way, become essential for the success of the programme. Therefore, the ideal team for any joint programme is a group of professionals with complementary skills who are committed, have a collective purpose and support each other to achieve a specific goal (Contu & Pecis, 2017).

In Table 2.1, an overview of the most relevant definitions related to joint programmes proposed by scholars and practitioners is provided. Joint programmes have different levels of integration or “jointness”. This is reflected in the curriculum, teaching methodology, learning

Table 2.1 – Definitions of Joint Programmes

Definition	Description and Sources
Joint programme	Study programmes with an integrated curriculum coordinated and offered jointly by two (or more) higher education institutions and leading to a (double/multiple or joint) degree in a particular subject area (Aerden & Reczulska, 2012; Overmann & Kuder, 2018; YERUN, 2018).
Joint degree	Upon finalising a joint programme, students receive a single degree certificate/diploma/qualification issued and signed jointly by the rectors of the two or more higher education institutions involved in the programme (Schüle, 2006; Knight, 2008; Aerden & Reczulska, 2012; Overmann & Kuder, 2018; Kuder, Lemmens, & Obst, 2013; European Commission, 2016).
Multiple degree	When separate degrees are awarded by higher education institutions offering a joint programme attesting the successful completion of the programme (Aerden & Reczulska, 2012; European Commission, 2016; YERUN, 2018)
Double degree	Two diplomas/degrees certificates awarded separately by each higher education institution offering the joint programme attesting the successful completion of this programme (Schüle, 2006; Aerden & Reczulska, 2012; Overmann & Kuder, 2018; Kuder, Lemmens, & Obst, 2013; European Commission, 2016). As double degrees are a specific type of multiple degrees, to avoid misunderstanding with dual degrees, it is also recommended to call them multiple degrees (Aerden & Reczulska, 2012).
Dual degree	“Two degrees awarded individually, attesting the successful completion of two separate curricula, with potential overlap and efficiencies in course-taking, and, if more than one institution is involved, each institution is primarily responsible for its own degree. → <i>A dual degree is not awarded by a joint programme</i> ” (Aerden & Reczulska, 2012, p. 12). “At the international level, the term is normally used interchangeably with double degree. However, at the domestic or national level it often refers to a double major indicating two areas of concentration attached to one degree or two degrees in different fields from the same institution” (Knight, 2008, p. 17).

outcomes, quality assurance, credit transfer, admission procedures, selection criteria, financial management, student services, staff requirements, and so on (Dvoretzky et al., [2013](#); European Commission & European Education and Culture Executive Agency, [2013](#)). According to the Bologna Process Implementation Report ([2012](#), p. 185) a joint programme should have, if not all, at least some of the following characteristics described by Tauch and Rauhvargers ([2002](#)):

- (i) the programmes are developed and/or approved jointly by several institutions; (ii) students from each participating institution study part of the programme at other institutions; (iii) the students' stays at the participating institutions are of comparable length; (iv) periods of study and exams passed at the partner institution(s) are recognised fully and automatically; (v) professors of each participating institution also teach at the other institutions, work out the curriculum jointly and form joint commissions for admission and examinations; and (vi) after completion of the full programme, the student either obtains the national degrees of each participating institution or a degree awarded jointly by all of them (Tauch & Rauhvargers [2002](#), p. 29).

From the point of view of de Rosa ([2010](#)), there are some “musts” that a joint doctorate should have in terms of training, administration and quality assurance (de Rosa, [2010](#)). Although her study is based in doctoral degrees, many elements described by de Rosa are applicable to any joint programme. Figure 2.2 displays elements taken from de Rosa ([2010](#)) and adapted to this study, together with other elements taken from the European Commission and European Education, Audiovisual and Culture Executive Agency ([2013](#)) and Dvoretzky et al. ([2013](#)). They were all incorporated into the three presented categories. The groups and items listed in the figure illustrate the interaction between professional staff and academics for the proper implementation of a joint programme. Consequently, a successful EMJMD requires a series of strategies, not only at the programme level but also at the organisational level as any other strategy implemented for integrating the international dimension in a higher education institution (Knight & de Wit, [1999](#)).

Figure 2.2 – “Musts” of a Joint Master’s Degree

Source: Developed by the author for this research with information retrieved from de Rosa (2010), with some changes in the content of each category. Additional features were taken from the European Commission and European Education and Culture Executive Agency (2013) and Dvoretzky et al. (2013).

In 2011, Obst et al. conducted a global survey – at the higher education institution level – related to joint and double degrees. The vast majority of participants agreed that setting up these programmes was part of their institution’s internationalisation strategies (Obst et al., 2011) and has multiple benefits. The responses were also related to broadening their educational offerings, strengthening collaboration for research, advancing internationalisation, and increasing international prestige. Other motivations, although less important, were related to revenue and participating in courses from partner institutions that do not exist at their home institution. The overall consensus was that joint programmes were not offered for their lucrative nature, but rather to strengthen and broaden the institution’s portfolio and visibility (Obst et al., 2011).

Table 2.2 explains detailed descriptions of the benefits of these degrees divided into four areas. It is worth noting how the research and literature clearly define the benefits for different

categories and on various levels but professional staff are rarely mentioned in these studies, leaving space for future research.

Table 2.2 – Beneficiaries and Benefits of Joint Programmes

Students	Academics
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gain new ways of thinking • Learn new cultural opportunities • Improve language skills • Experiment learning methods • Benefit from changing lives experiences • Acquire broad intellectual horizons • Develop networks • Gain new professional perspectives • Improve interpersonal skills and explore global issues • Extend the pan-European social and technological knowledge • Access to programmes that can lead to professional accreditation in their field 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gain international professional development opportunities • Develop networks • Improve international cooperation for research projects • Benefit from international teaching experiences • Explore complementarities in teaching and learning methods • Be exposed to different academic environments and traditions
Higher education institutions	Region (Europe)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be at the forefront of inter-university cooperation • Enhance reputation • Increase internationalisation of the campus • Attract top-level students • Gain knowledge about international policies • Combine resources • Develop innovative international education, curricula, and mobility experiences for students • Combine the diverse strengths of individual institutions • Provide a structured mobility experience • Increase the international visibility • Internationalise the staff (academics and professional staff) • Establishing close links for research collaboration • Improve the quality of the courses 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement Bologna reforms (degree and ECTS⁵ recognition, quality assurance, etc.) • Promote an integration process • Increase transparency between educational systems • Encourage cultural understanding • Boost European citizenship • Retain Europe's best students • Attract overseas students • Encourage cooperation with non-European institutions for international understanding • Promote multiculturalism and multilingualism

Source: Developed by the author with information retrieved from Paschaloudis et al. ([n.d.](#)); European University Association ([2004](#)); Knight, ([2011](#)); Russell et al. ([2007](#)); Wang ([2017](#)) and YERUN ([2018](#)).

⁵ European Credit Transfer System (ECTS).

Erasmus Mundus Joint Master's Degrees

Launched in 2004, to continue with the implementation of the Bologna Process, a cooperation and mobility scheme – the Erasmus Mundus – was introduced to promote European higher education institutions worldwide and encourage the convergence of European higher education systems. The Erasmus Mundus aim to foster excellence and internationalisation of higher education through educational initiatives (European Commission, [2022](#)) and by attracting the best talent worldwide while offering financial assistance to institutions and scholarships to outstanding candidates globally (European Commission & European Education and Culture Executive Agency, [2021](#)).

These high-quality integrated courses are delivered by a consortium of European higher education institutions, included mandatory mobility periods in two different countries and issued a multiple or joint diploma (European Commission & European Education and Culture Executive Agency, [2013](#)). Their collaborative framework is created by a combined system of institutions and compared to national study programmes, these degrees require a lot more resources, which increases the development and operating expenses (Nickel et al., [2009](#)). Within these consortiums, one coordinating higher education institution manages the overall consortium and, depending on their role, the other higher education institutions can act as beneficiaries (if they also receive European Union funds) or as associated partners. Predictably, it is challenging to create strong coordination and meet the demands of the many parties involved (Owens and Lane, [2014](#)), but good communication promotes the development of the ideal scenario with the needed operative feedback procedures (Abebe & Ford, [2019](#)).

The Erasmus Mundus programme has experienced numerous and important changes since its establishment and their evaluation reports have brought attention to them and, validated the complexity of these programmes (Zenkienė, [2020](#)). In 2014, “the Erasmus Mundus Programme has formed part of the Erasmus+, the new umbrella programme for education, training, youth and sport” (European Commission, [2016](#), p. 7). The budget for the period

increased compared to the previous one, and the courses were called “Erasmus Mundus Joint Master Degrees” (EMJMDs). As for the previous editions, the significant growth in programme participation over cycles with the notwithstanding consolidation of established networks (Marques et al., [2022](#)) brought a new funding cycle in 2021, with the Erasmus Mundus Joint Masters (EMJMs). Table 2.3 presents the evolution of these degrees.

The EMJMDs’ multi-institutional and multi-geographical structure offer specific insights beyond those of typical mobile students who attend a single institution for the duration of their studies (Abebe & Ford, [2019](#)). Unlike other forms of mobility, EMJMD-style programmes offer a multiple-destination institutionalised group experience without a designated ‘home’ country (Czerska-Shaw & Krzaklewska, [2022](#)).

Table 2.3 – Erasmus Mundus Master’s Degrees Evolution

Name	Funding Cycle	Funding Scheme	Scholarships
Erasmus Mundus Masters Courses (EMMCs)	2004-2008	Erasmus Mundus	- Only non-European/ non-European Economic Area students
Erasmus Mundus Masters Courses (EMMCs)	2009-2013	Erasmus Mundus	- Non-European/ European Economic Area students - European students
Erasmus Mundus Joint Master’s Degrees (EMJMDs)	2014-2020	Erasmus +	- Non-European/ European Economic Area students - European students
Erasmus Mundus Joint Masters (EMJMs)	2021-2027 (ongoing)	Erasmus +	- Non-European/ European Economic Area students - European students

The EMJMDs meet all the essential components of an educational environment, which include a good atmosphere, diverse learning opportunities, adequate facilities, foster personal development, promote relationships, and an appropriate supportive organisation to ensure the

quality of education (Xu et al., [2022](#); Xu et al., [2023](#); Schönrock-Adema et al., [2012](#)) and a positive life-changing experience. Besides, the deliberate cultural diversity of the student and the required built-in mobility of EMJMDs generate special opportunities for the expansion of students' intercultural skills (Yarosh et al., [2018](#)).

Still, at the same time, these super-mobile students face specific difficulties which contribute to the development of their tight community, which is distinguished by a high degree of reflexivity and intercultural sensitivity (Czerska-Shaw & Krzaklewska, [2021](#)). Difficulties are associated to the fact that Erasmus Mundus students consider themselves to be privileged compared to other mobile students (the “regular” Erasmus students), but at the same time they feel isolated from the rest of the institution and closed in an exclusive bubble (Czerska-Shaw & Krzaklewska, [2021](#)). Similarly, at the institutional level, issues related to qualification and recognition, joint degree awarding, quality control, and financial plans are areas of disagreement (Zenkiene, [2020](#)), increasing and adding complexity to regular institutional administrative procedures. As a result, the staff involved in these degrees programmes create a close-knit community with colleagues in partner institutions who face similar problems at their own institution.

The EMJMDs as a Case Study: Roles and Collaboration within these degrees

EMJMDs are developed by different professionals with more or less defined roles and require a significant amount of human and financial resources and intensive planning at all stages. These degrees suggest a new paradigm for collaboration in higher education: formalised networks of institutions that share accountability for students' learning outcomes while they move across campuses via a planned educational framework (Czerska-Shaw & Krzaklewska [2021](#)). In this landscape, EMJMDs are continually nurtured and supported by all actors, including governments and institutions, to promote European collaboration in the global education scene (European University Association, [2004](#)). Therefore, to succeed in a partnership of such magnitude, every

single consortium should involve all relevant stakeholders from the beginning, during the development phase, and in the long-term implementation (Barre et al., [n.d.](#))

Managing EMJMDs varies according to the institution, curriculum integration, the teaching methodology, the mobility format, and other factors. The integrated character of these degrees also demands a team-based approach in the teaching methodology, which means that the development of the course content and the teaching activities are organised by a team of professors of different countries (Paschaloudis et al., [n.d.](#)). Academics have a pivotal role in supporting the collaborative degrees. “Without faculty’s commitment, it would be extremely hard to develop programs to improve students’ multicultural competencies, create stronger collaboration with foreign universities and develop current offerings to better meet the requirements of today’s educational environment” (Holstein, [2012](#), p. 113). In parallel, without the cooperation and support of appropriate professional staff, such programmes are complicated to implement (Gallicchio, [2007](#)).

As multifaceted projects developed by different staff types, EMJMDs necessitate extensive collaboration among academics, professional staff, and higher education institution leadership, as Obst et al. ([2011](#)) highlighted. For this reason, many EMJMDs employ additional staff for the coordination and connection with the partnering institution(s) (Obst et al., [2011](#)) since the EMJMDs encompass specific administrative procedures for the mandatory mobility periods, visas, and joint degree – all complex and time-consuming processes. As a result, contrasting regular degrees, the consortium under the EMJMD develop a distinct, independent pillar that stands apart from all of the member universities (Balyasin et al., [2016](#)) and, in a sense, remain isolated within the higher education institutions involved. Additionally, following Veles et al.’s ([2018](#)) statement, EMJMDs represent the integration of the three most prominent dimensions of collaborations that emerged from the scientific literature, “*culture* (national, local and global), *professional/occupational integration* (multi-professional, inter-professional and trans-

professional) and *relationship integration* (networking, coordination, coordination and collaboration)” (p. 80) making them an ideal *Third Space* ecosystem.

These unique features of the EMJMDs can sometimes create challenges within the rigid structures of certain higher education institutions in which there is a resistance to change due factors such as the organisational structure, limited resources, fear of the unknown, threats to power or influence, habit, loss of freedom, economic implications, and obsolescence of knowledge and skills (Yilmaz & Kılıçoğlu, [2013](#)). To prevent the frustration derived from this situation and accomplish any EMJMD, a cohesive team with positive working dynamics is needed to achieve common goals and foster a unified environment that promotes a flexible and collaborative approach within higher education institutions.

2.3.3 The Concept and Features of a Third Space Setting

Activities in higher education institutions have been always seen in binary terms: the academic domain and the administrative or management sphere that supports the academic one (Whitchurch, [2008a](#)). Predictably, with all the institutional changes previously described, and the increased number of professional staff, new mechanisms, spaces and ways of interaction within the higher education institutions’ environment appeared. Apart from Whitchurch ([2008a](#), [2013](#), [2015](#), [2018](#)), scholars such as Veles ([2016](#), [2018](#), [2020](#), [2023a](#), [2023b](#)) and McKay and Robson ([2023](#)) have written about “additional spaces” that exist in higher education institutions: areas that could not fit into the defined borders between professional staff and academics. Within these new spaces, activities and contributions that challenge existing practices and expectations appear, offering new opportunities for staff and their institutions (Whitchurch & Gordon, [2017](#)), particularly in terms of collaboration. This type of spaces, defined by Whitchurch ([2008a](#)) as the *Third Space*, is “an emergent territory between academic and professional domains, which is colonised primarily by less bounded forms of professional” (Whitchurch, [2008a](#), p. 377). Figure 2.3 describes the *Third Space* in higher education, along with some of the activities which take

place within it, and Figure 2.4 by Rytberg (2020) represents the undistinguishable limits of a *Third Space*.

Figure 2.3 – The Emergence of *Third Space* Between Professional and Academic Spheres

Source: Whitchurch (2013, p. 25)

Figure 2.4 – *Third Space*, Blurred Boundaries on Relation to Staff Groups

Source: Rytberg (2020, p. 30)

Initially, the *Third Space* was viewed as a short-term, project-oriented initiative that brought together individuals from various backgrounds and professions, focusing on the growth of social capital and networking (Veles, [2023a](#)). In these environments, structures and organisation continue to be present; but these spaces provide an opportunity for the emergence of new activities and approaches (Ryttberg, [2020](#)). The characteristic of *Third Space* thinking is being receptive to new ideas originating from many voices, personalities, and viewpoints (Veles, [2024](#)), making traditional binary concepts of staff in higher education obsolete, ineffective, and unable to capture the complexity of the objectives and processes of current reality of higher education institutions (Veles et al., [2023a](#), [2023b](#))

Any joint programme and, consequently, any EMJMD, can be considered a *Third Space* because they combine staff categories working in a single project. Deans, professors, international officers, academics with managerial roles, admission officers, recruitment specialists and quality assurance experts are only some of the team members that bring in their knowledge and expertise in a collaborative relationship to achieve a high-quality international educational offer. Therefore, by exploring the nature of the interaction among different staff categories and the type of relationships they develop while pursuing a common goal, it will be possible to understand the characteristics of this collaboration and the research topic of this study will be addressed.

The *Third Space* encompasses activities that do not neatly align with formal organisational structures, hierarchical charts, or predefined job descriptions (Whitchurch, [2013](#)). Consequently, it is characterised by: (i) mixed teams of staff who work on short- and long-term projects, not necessarily located geographically in the same place, so may also be virtual (Whitchurch, [2008a](#)); (ii) contributions from administrative services which have been redirected towards a partnership relationship with academic colleagues (Whitchurch, [2008a](#)); (iii) offering a way to review binary approaches in higher education environments and the roles of the staff involved (Whitchurch, [2013](#)); and (iv) giving professional staff the ability to manage ambiguity and even productively

use the tensions they may encounter (Whitchurch, [2015](#)). As a result, *Third Space* complements other higher education institution spaces where core activities occur (Veles & Carter, [2016](#)) and it can also create bridges between existing areas and/or generates new ones (Whitchurch, [2013](#)).

Nevertheless, since *Third Space* settings do not fit well into traditional organisational systems can be perceived as unclear and unpredictable, and those who work in them are likely to come across a series of dilemmas and paradoxes presenting both opportunities and challenges (Whitchurch, [2015](#)). According to this author, the ambiguity of boundaries such as the lack of rigid structures fosters creativity and innovation, but it can also lead to confusion and dysfunction, as individuals fit in multiple roles without clear frameworks. This ambiguity extends to its nature as both a safe and risky environment. Although the *Third Space* allows for experimentation and the questioning of institutional norms, this freedom can be perceived as a threat, creating tensions between new practices and traditional expectations. Ultimately, as Whitchurch ([2015](#)) underlines, these paradoxes—safety and risk, clarity and ambiguity, autonomy and instability—shape the *Third Space* as a dynamic yet precarious environment that profoundly impacts the professional experiences and effectiveness of those who work on it.

Finally, Whitchurch's diagram of a *Third Space* (Figure 2.3) does not look explicitly at matters related to the internationalisation of higher education and the roles and evolution of the professional staff and academics involved in it. Professional staff participating in the internationalisation of higher education develop – while collaborating with academics – a range of areas such as teaching and learning, research and also external engagement. They also work in collaboration with other professional staff in functions such as marketing, recruitment, alumni, and general student services. Consequently, the internationalisation of higher education is now increasingly perceived as a comprehensive dimension of the institution and the findings of this research may be included in Whitchurch's diagram. This output might provide not only a complementary reading of the *Third Space* but also opens options to extend studies in this domain.

The Escalation of Blended Professionals

With its blurring margins, the *Third Space* promotes the rise of new categories of staff – the so-called *Third Space* professionals (Whitchurch, [2008a](#)), also denominated blended professionals. These are individuals who carry out borderless or blended roles that include both academic and professional activities without organisational boundaries limiting their activities (Whitchurch, [2009](#), [2013](#)). Furthermore, as noted by Whitchurch ([2008a](#), [2013](#), [2018](#)), in a higher education institution, *Third Space* staff are situated in a transitional area between traditional academic and professional services.

With a distinctive identity formed through blending talents and integrating skills (Akerman [2020](#)), these are individuals of high qualification, with academic degrees, and serving in strategic positions close to the leadership (Ryttberg, [2022](#)). They contribute to the higher education institution's growth by developing specific projects, and their contributions are “unencumbered by titles, job roles and position descriptions” (Veles & Carter, [2016](#), p. 522).

Adopting a polymathic approach (proficiency and expertise across multiple fields), staff in the *Third Space* develop know-how in multiple aspects, understanding professional motivations, and establishing connections with different work-related settings (Manoharan, [2020](#)). Besides, as declared by Whitchurch ([2009](#)), they offer new perspectives and skills that could shape the future of higher education, for example, bridging the gap between professional and academic domains. This is because they challenge the long-lasting separation between academic and professional functions by undertaking these “blended” or hybrid roles encompassing academic and administrative activities (Manoharan, [2020](#)).

According to Whitchurch ([2013](#)), blended professionals have the following characteristics: they (i) are passionate about the projects and possess the needed flexibility; (ii) generate knowledge by analysing information useful for decision-making and policy formulation; (iii) prioritise relationships and networks, adopting a people-centric approach; (iv) establish credibility by facilitating the work of others, rather than having authoritarian behaviour; (v)

understand and mediate between different stakeholders; and (vi) adapt and use the appropriate language depending on the audience (pp. 79-80). However, according to Whitchurch (2015), professionals operating in the *Third Space* must continuously negotiate competing stakeholder interests, balancing diverse agendas that can generate conflicts and struggles for recognition. The inherent fluidity of roles further amplifies uncertainty, simultaneously offering liberation from conventional constraints while making it difficult to establish a stable professional identity or sense of belonging (Whitchurch, 2015). Consequently, despite their significant contributions, blended professionals often face institutional challenges in gaining legitimacy and recognition, leaving them vulnerable to feelings of isolation and frustration (Whitchurch, 2015).

Therefore, even if blended professionals have a pivotal role in higher education because they generate knowledge, cultivate relationships, and encourage collaboration across conventional boundaries, they also face challenges in establishing their credentials and identities (Whitchurch, 2009), as well as role ambiguity, self-advocacy, and blurred positions, which may also result in stress and burnout (Smith et al., 2021). Consequently, the linkage between constructing an identity and securing legitimacy for their role is pivotal for establishing their professional identity and acknowledging their jobs (Ryttberg, 2022). Specially because as cited by Whitchurch (2013), “[t]he narratives also suggest that *Third Space* professionals are contributing to new definitions of management, leadership and professionalism that focus more on development, facilitation and collaboration than on control” (p. 143).

Blended professionals are the other staff category involved in the design and management of EMJMDs. They maintain an efficient working relationship with academics, students, institutional leadership and the European Commission and are fundamental in achieving the results of these degrees.

2.4 Understanding the Multifaceted Concept of Collaboration

Before examining the essence of the collaboration within an EMJMD *Third Space*, it is pertinent to consider the academic literature on the concept of collaboration itself. While numerous studies and theories have been proposed on this topic, this section will not only review the key aspects but also concentrate on those that are particularly relevant to higher education settings.

2.4.1 Collaboration: *What it is and What it is not*

A variety of studies have made contributions to the meaning and definition of collaboration. In the 1990s, Henneman et al. (1995) declared that collaboration is a multidimensional phenomenon whose definition is vague or highly variable, but it is clear that collaboration requires individuals that view themselves as members of a team and participate in the development of a common product or goal. It is a complex and sophisticated process that “requires competence, confidence and commitment on the part of all parties involved” (Henneman et al., 1995, p. 108). Individual and environmental factors influence whether or not collaboration occurs. However, an effective group dynamic with clear roles and excellent communication skills – as well as respect and trust – are crucial components to build the needed relationship (Henneman et al., 1995). According to the authors, collaboration offers results at different levels: the individual, the group, the organisation and the end-user. Furthermore, collaboration promotes a sense of success and accomplishment in meeting individual and team objectives (Henneman et al., 1995).

Nevertheless, as declared by Thomson et al. (2007), a “lack of consensus among scholars on the meaning of collaboration makes it difficult to compare findings across studies and to know whether what is measured is really collaboration” (Thomson et al., 2007, pp. 23-24). This is because effective collaboration depends on coordination (continuous renegotiation and managing interdependencies to achieve a goal) between tasks to ensure effectiveness and mitigate the risk of conflicts (Raposo et al., 2001). Even more, “[w]hen collaboration is successful, it is a

powerful way of working together and making change in education” (Goulet et al., [2003](#), p. 338), offering diverse advantages such as enhancements in effectiveness, resource utilisation, capacity building, social development benefits and ways to address challenges due to interdependence among stakeholders to achieve goals (Lawson, [2004](#)). Collaboration, in the context of this research, is characterised by joint effort on a selected project, aiming to optimise outcomes despite potential inefficiencies (Deb et al., [2020](#)).

However, the term collaboration is often interchanged with terms like “cooperation” and “coordination” (Mattessich & Monsey, [1992](#)), although these terms have different significate, as illustrated in Table 2.4. Martin et al. ([2016](#)) focused on the differences between coordination and collaboration, emphasising that collaboration can take many different forms, being casual and sporadic interactions to highly structured partnerships with contractual agreements such as any EMJMD. Castañer and Oliveira’s ([2020](#)) study also examined the meanings of cooperation, coordination, and collaboration in inter-organisational relationships and emphasised the ambiguity of these terms.

Table 2.4 – Commonly Interchangeable Terms, Different Meanings

Cooperation	Coordination	Collaboration
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informal relationships without any commonly defined mission, structure or planning effort • Information is shared as needed • Authority is retained by each organization • Resources are separate as are rewards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More formal relationships and understanding of compatible mission • Some planning and division of roles are required • Communication channels are established • Authority still rests with the individual organisations, but there is some increased risk to all participants • Resources are available to participants and rewards are mutually acknowledged 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More durable and pervasive relationship • Brings separated organisations into a new structure with full commitment to a common mission • Require comprehensive planning • Well defined communication channels operating on many levels • Authority is determined by the collaborative structure • Risk is much greater because each member of the collaboration contributes its own resources and reputation • Resources are pooled or jointly secured, and the products are shared

Source: Adapted from Mattessich and Monsey ([1992](#), pp. 42-43)

2.4.2 Competencies Needed to Ensure a Fruitful Collaboration

Over the years, several attempts have been made to formulate the necessary skills for collaborative practice. “These include the development of skills in communication, teamwork and the management of conflict within an understanding of the professions and their histories” (Barr, [1998](#), p. 184). Besides, collaborative practice also encompasses responsibility, accountability, cooperation, coordination, assertiveness, autonomy, and mutual trust and respect (Way et al., [2000](#)) and the acknowledgement of shared skills of team members facilitates building confidence in each other’s proficiencies (Hobson et al., [2018](#)).

However, these competencies are usually developed to support a professional within their own profession, but not to interact with members of other professions (Bainbridge et al., [2010](#)). According to Barr ([1998](#)), competencies with particular reference to collaborative practice should be: (i) common, i.e., between all professions; (ii) complementary, i.e., distinguish one profession and complement other professions; and (iii) collaborative, i.e., promote the collaboration with similar professionals, with other professions, with non-professionals, and within and between organisations (Barr, [1998](#)).

To understand the various components contributing to the way professionals work together in a team, and the outcomes of their actions, a multilevel sequential approach is needed, i.e., it is crucial to identify the individual, the team, and the organisational characteristics (Salas et al., [2017](#)). Furthermore, as knowledge becomes increasingly specialised, teams must rely on other teams to bring together the expertise needed, as is the case of EMJMDs.

2.4.3 Characteristics of Collaborative Workplaces

According to Salas et al. ([2017](#)), “[t]eams are a way of life in organizations” (Salas et al., [2017](#), p. 22). For this reason, the study of teams and their effectiveness increased in the fields of industrial organisational psychology and organisational behaviour (Asencio & DeChurch, [2017](#)), among

other sectors, because teamwork can be defined as the “[c]ooperative effort by the members of a group to achieve a common goal” (IPC, [2011](#), p. 1).

Although organisations can be influential in establishing collaborative projects, they cannot ensure and be responsible for their success: “Collaboration is in fact, a process which occurs between individuals, not institutions, and only the persons involved ultimately determine whether or not collaboration occurs” (Henneman et al., [1995](#), p. 108). Gaboury et al. ([2009](#)) highlighted that problems within a team arise when: (i) one profession may see another profession as a rival and not want to involve these colleagues in the collaboration; (ii) professional groups that are afraid to interact with other colleagues for various reasons, for example, historical isolation or low status within the professional hierarchy; and (iii) a culturally dominant profession may have attitudes that are prejudiced against other professions (Gaboury et al., [2009](#)).

Consequently, it is fundamental to promote positive and supportive co-working relationships and collaborative environments due to the strong connections between these two elements and job satisfaction (Bella, [2023](#)). More specifically, academic institutions can encourage engagement and work satisfaction by the implementation techniques such as rewards, recognition, professional development, communication and understanding (Janib et al., [2022](#)) to create general well-being of the whole community (Bella, [2023](#)).

2.4.4 Different Types of Interaction Among Professionals

A wide range of professionals, in all types of domains, interact for diverse work-related reasons. As stated by Veles et al. ([2018](#)), the literature divides into three key ways the collaboration between various professions, as explained in Figure 2.5. The types of collaboration may be multi-professional, inter-professional and trans-professional (Thylefors et al., [2005](#)).

Multi-professional interaction refers to professionals working in parallel, but each one has clear role definitions and specific tasks. Within such teams there are clear hierarchical guidelines

of authority but with professional autonomy. In multi-professional partnerships, engagement means contributing to the plan/project autonomously and presenting a part of the job (Thylefors et al., [2005](#)).

Figure 2.5 – Types of Interaction in Professional Domains

Source: Developed by the author with information retrieved from Thylefors et al. ([2005](#))

Inter-professional collaboration implies the efforts of two or more professions combining their skills to achieve shared objectives, address challenges and intricate issues. It offers the advantage of accomplishing more collectively than could be achieved independently (Green & Johnson, [2015](#)). Inter- and trans-professional collaborations have a higher level of integration between the different professionals and include collective planning, decision-making and equal contribution.

Between both of them, trans-professional collaboration is the optimal level of collaborative engagement practice because it has the highest level of integration and professional

boundaries are in part cancelled, and roles enhanced and extended (Thylefors et al., [2005](#)).

According to Veles et al. ([2018](#)), this is the level desired for successful sustainable collaborations.

Consequently, these are the type of collaborations needed to design and implement any EMJMD.

2.4.5 Teamwork: The Power of Collaboration

Teams are crucial in any organisation and across all sectors, from the industry to the healthcare environment and educational settings because effective teamwork produces benefits like knowledge creation, error reduction, innovation, productivity, job satisfaction, and goal achievement. Understanding team dynamics requires a multilevel approach considering individual, team, and organisational factors (Salas et al., [2017](#)). In addition, in terms of skills, Rosen et al. ([2018](#)) specified that competence in teamwork is not only related to knowledge, skills, and attitudes because the nature of the tasks and the environment in which teams operate play crucial roles in enhancing teamwork.

Consequently, the collaboration within an EMJMD *Third Space* is a process, a product, where different actors overcome several barriers to foster the shared goal of creating a collaborative capital and establishing reciprocal trust and closeness among individuals (Veles, [2023b](#)). This kind of ecosystem, though, can only function well if all participants' contributions are properly and systemically recognised (Veles, [2024](#)). For this reason, the essential competencies to excel in teamwork encompass: (i) respect and shared values; (ii) clear understanding of roles and responsibilities; and (iii) personal behaviours such as integrity, honesty, critical self-assessment, supportive attitude and being open to feedback, among others (Rosen et al., [2018](#)).

2.5 Concluding Remarks

The structural transformations within higher education institutions have significantly altered the career paths of individuals working in the sector. Tensions between various staff categories have been exacerbated by multiple factors, increasing the perceived 'divide' between them.

Simultaneously, the professionalisation of roles and the development of specific projects have created new spaces where the expertise and collaboration of diverse professionals are required to succeed.

Governments, in response to pressing financial, social, and accountability challenges, have implemented policies aimed at enhancing the overall education experience and meeting the demands of the knowledge society and economy. This shift is particularly evident in the European Union's strategy to improve the European Higher Education Area, exemplified by one of its flagship initiatives, the EMJMDs. These unique academic programmes necessitate close collaboration among all staff categories to ensure their effective implementation and long-term sustainability. Therefore, fostering a collaborative relationship built on strong teamwork is crucial for overcoming differences and achieving common goals within the EMJMD context. This is a relationship that should bring collaborative production, as well as common ideals and abilities (Joubert, [2024](#)).

To gain a deeper understanding of the nature of interaction among staff categories within an EMJMD, the next chapter presents the Theoretical and Conceptual frameworks derived from this comprehensive literature review, which guided my research in terms of data collection and analysis. Both frameworks were essential in addressing and answering the Research Questions central to this study.

CHAPTER THREE: TOWARDS A CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK ON COLLABORATION IN EMJMDs

3.1 Introduction

This chapter is organised into three sections. The first section provides an overview of the theories and concepts that support the main topic of this dissertation, i.e., the ‘divide’, the *Third Space*, and collaboration. The second section presents the specific concepts and theories that were selected for the Theoretical Framework of this study and their relevance to my Research Questions and objectives. The third and last section discusses the Conceptual Framework used for collecting and analysing the research data for this study.

3.2 Theories and Concepts as the Foundation for my Theoretical Framework

The results from the literature review were examined using the concepts and theories that can be clustered under the following topics: (i) concepts and theories related to the relationship between professional staff and academics in higher education institutions, (ii) the concept of spaces, precisely *Third Spaces*, and (iii) the concept of collaboration.

First, as described in the previous chapter, the oftentimes challenging relationship between professional staff and academics is characterised by power dynamics, differing priorities, and a lack of mutual understanding, which can prevent effective collaboration and decision-making processes within higher education institutions. Hence, theories and models that explore professional identity, organisational culture, hierarchical relationships, and interprofessional collaboration can provide valuable insights.

The second group of concepts is related to the notion of *Third Spaces*, which emerged within the context of an international project like an EMJMD. As outlined in Chapter Two, *Third Spaces* are hybrid areas where different perspectives and ways of working interact, creating opportunities for new forms of collaboration, knowledge sharing and production. Theories

behind the *Third Space* in different contexts can explain the dynamics and potential of these spaces.

The final group of concepts focuses on collaboration, which is a central aspect of the problematic relationship between professional staff and academics. Collaboration involves the joint effort of individuals or groups to achieve common goals, often requiring the negotiation of differences and the development of shared understandings. Theories and models that explore collaborative processes, such as those from the fields of team dynamics and interprofessional collaboration, provide an understanding of the challenges and opportunities associated with collaboration in the context of my study.

3.2.1 Relationships Between Staff Groups

As explored in the previous chapter, both personal and institutional factors contribute to the ‘divide’, with some being internal to the organisation and others external. However, since the interaction between these two groups is labelled in academic publications by adjectives like “conflict”, “competitive”, “tension” or “negative”, scholars describe the tension as an organisational trait (Conway, [n.d.](#)). Others argue that the tension causes the dysfunctional ‘divide’ since the two groups inside higher education institutions have different ideals and are working toward distinct objectives (Conway, [n.d.](#); Bess & Dee, [2014](#)). Additionally, even if many academics and professional staff have friendly and positive relations, there is sometimes competition between the two groups and “[a]cademics who take on administrative roles such as heads of departments and even vice-chancellors require a set of skills and knowledge very different to those used for their academic work” (Conway, [n.d.](#), p. 4).

How individuals construct their identities – who they were, are, and want to be – is integral to and crucial to what occurs inside and around an organisation (Brown, [2015](#)), because “identity is central to our understanding of how individuals relate to the groups and organisations in which they are participants” (Brown, [2001](#)). Even more, the reinterpretation of

role provided by Simpson and Carroll (2008) is in line with understandings of identity as a multifaceted, discursive, dynamic social process. These authors emphasise that role theory is still a prominent issue in organisational discourses, leading to a reconsideration of role as a border object that is essential to identity development (Simpson & Carroll, 2008).

The changes in professional identities are deeply interconnected with a higher education institution's organisational culture. As declared by Arnold (2005), organisational culture is “[t]he distinctive norms, beliefs, principles and ways of behaving that combine to give each organisation its distinct character” (Arnold, 2005, p. 625). Similarly, for Brown (1998), the non-explicit actions that characterises an institution's operation may comprise ideals, rules, views, attitudes, ideologies, and assumptions that give it its distinct identity, and according to Johnson, organisational culture is to an institution what personality is to a human being (Johnson, 1990).

Instead, Harrison and Stokes (1992) divided organisational culture into four different dimensions, which can describe the current reality or the ideal reality expected of higher education institutions: (i) Power dimension: There is a single source of power that spreads throughout the organisation, the power is centralised and members of the organisation are linked to the centre; (ii) Role dimension: The primary focus of this kind of culture is on job descriptions and specialisation. Job description serves as the foundation for the processes and norms that govern employment. It is characterised by formal job descriptions and a focus on roles rather than personal traits; (iii) Achievement dimension: This one is frequently used to describe a task culture, in which employees concentrate on achieving the organisation's objectives. The capacity to do tasks efficiently is the most crucial component of this dimension, which focuses on the levels of abilities and competences needed to handle the tasks. Organisations with a task culture often function on a project basis, with deadlines to accomplish for each project; and (iv) Support dimension: Describes a culture within the organisation that is built on mutual trust between the individuals and organisations. A support-oriented organisation may be seen as a cluster where no one leads and that exists only for the individuals that make up the organisation. The emphasis on

the support and well-being of members defines organisations which are frequently linked to a dependence on interpersonal connections and trust as well as a lack of formal hierarchy (Harrison and Stokes, [1992](#)).

It is well known that hierarchical situations in the workplace can significantly impact motivation and job satisfaction. “Hierarchy is a generic structure in which levels are asymmetrically ordered” (Luo et al., [2009](#), p. 3). Even if clear hierarchies can provide structure and direction, they can also interfere with motivation if not managed effectively. Conversely, providing individuals with increased autonomy, flattening the hierarchy, fostering a sense of belonging and recognising contributions are strategies to mitigate the negative effects of hierarchical structures. Although the ideas of hierarchy and organisational levels have been around for a very long time, hierarchy theory did not start to take shape until the beginning of the 1960s (Wu, [2013](#)).

Hierarchy theory is not a formal theory, and there are several versions because a cross-disciplinary approach was used to establish it: management sciences, economics, psychology, biology, and mathematics, among others (Wu, [2013](#)). Herbert A. Simon was the theory’s principal originator. According to Simon ([1962](#)), a hierarchy, in general, is just a system that is organised into levels or layers with unbalanced relationships. Even more, the definition provided is a “system that is composed of interrelated subsystems, each of the latter being, in turn, hierarchic in structure until we reach some lowest level of elementary subsystem” (Simon, [1962](#), p. 468).

There is also a distinction between nested and non-nested hierarchies, which is another classification that was presented by Ahl and Allen ([1996](#)) while mentioning that there are many nested hierarchies in the natural, social, and organisational spheres, where higher levels either include or are made up of lower ones. Despite the many versions and distinctions, it is possible to affirm that according to hierarchy theory, most complex systems function best when there is a healthy balance between top-down restrictions and bottom-up processes (Wu, [2013](#)). Neither

flexibility nor a lack of diversity and creativity are implied by hierarchy theory; however, these elements are possible with a suitable hierarchical, dynamic structure (Wu, [2013](#)). Therefore, transformational leadership, where leaders collaborate with their team members to achieve goals and have a great deal of respect and trust for them (Asif et al., [2019](#)), is the ideal approach in which organisations can create a more inclusive and collaborative work environment, where individuals feel valued and motivated to contribute to the institution's success. This leadership style is specifically characterised by: (i) setting an example for others; (ii) inspiring and encouraging others; (iii) offering several suggestions and solutions to obstacles; and (vi) coaching people, allowing them to flourish (Asif et al., [2019](#)).

3.2.2 Emerging Spaces for Enhanced Experiences

Edward Soja ([1996](#)) explained the *Third Space* as a dynamic, ever-evolving conceptual space that combines people's lived experiences, imagination, and perceptions of reality to integrate the physical and mental realities. This author offered an alternative perspective on space and spatiality. Primary and secondary spaces are two distinct – and perhaps contradictory – spatial settings where individuals physically and socially interact; examples of these are home (for everyday knowledge) and school (for academic knowledge) (Soja, [1996](#)). Soja decided to stay away from the traditional dichotomy between society and the individual, nature and culture and the actual and the imagined, and proposed *Third Spaces* or hybrid spaces, which are the middle, as the result of the interactions of the other two spaces to form a new space (Soja, [1996](#)).

Gutiérrez et al. ([1999](#)) implemented the *Third Space* theory in education, emphasising how students in a culture of collaboration create certain zones or settings in the classroom – spaces of conflict and struggle – where hybrid activities, roles, and practices lead to productive contexts and areas for learning and development. Similarly, Moje et al. ([2004](#)) applied the *Third Space* theory to scientific literacy learning in a bilingual immersion school to place more focus on common understanding amongst students than on fights and pressure, fostering, in this way, an

environment where diverse discourses were respected, and none was given more weight than the other.

Whitchurch (2013), based on Soja's theory, used the term *Third Space* to designate the context in which different staff categories operate in a space between academic and professional practice and, sometimes, even across academia and other external stakeholders (Figure 2.3). The term was coined to describe places in which professional staff and academics work together as mixed teams for mutual benefit and to create strong links. In parallel, the *Third Space* professionals or blended professionals emerged within the same context, transcending traditional staff categories. Individuals with both academic and administrative knowledge and skills appeared to complement the mixed-team needs. Even though blended professionals' roles are expanding in importance and quantity, they often lack formal recognition within higher education institutions, which gives space to expand scholarly work on this staff group.

3.2.3 The Fundamentals of Collaboration

As described in the literature review, collaboration is a multifaceted concept that has been defined and explored by various scholars in different contexts. While there is no consensus on a single definition, several common traits are present in most definitions, including communication, shared goals, respect, and mutual engagement. However, the lack of consensus on a single definition highlights the complexity of collaboration and the challenges of capturing its multifaceted nature.

Collaboration in joint programmes is about staff members' relationships among themselves and the interaction with a genuinely multicultural and multilingual community. Green and Johnson (2015) focused on commitment, mutual goals, collective accountability, shared authority and respect and Hobson et al. (2018) highlighted the importance of trusting other's abilities, which was also underlined by Thornhill-Miller et al. (2023). Hence, all these factors are crucial for the effective functioning and success of mixed teams within the EMJMDs.

Theoretical Models Acting as Team Effectiveness Facilitators

High performing teams take time to evolve and mature, and they usually pass through the different stages of development. The Tuckman Model ([1965](#)), the T7 Lombardo and Eichinger model ([1995](#)), the LaFasto model ([2001](#)), and the Lencioni model ([2002](#)) are four distinct Team Effectiveness models that offer insights into the dynamics of team development and performance ([Appendix B](#) – Most Frequently Cited Team Models).

The Tuckman Model, also known as the FSNP model, proposes that teams go through five stages of development: Forming, Storming, Norming, Performing, and Adjourning. It highlights the stages of collaboration, from initial formation to an eventual successful performance. The last phase is for projects, which is the completion of the project and the consequent breakdown of the team. This model highlights the importance of understanding the stages of team development to ensure effective team functioning (Tuckman, [1965](#)).

Lombardo and Eichinger's ([1995](#)) model emphasises the importance of trust, communication, and shared goals in building effective collaboration. LaFasto's ([2001](#)) model focuses on the role of leadership in fostering collaboration. LaFasto's model suggests that effective teams are characterised by five elements: trust, communication, commitment, accountability, and results. This model accentuates the importance of building trust and fostering open communication among team members (LaFasto & Larson, [2001](#)). Finally, the Lencioni model ([2002](#)) identifies five dysfunctions of a team: absence of trust, fear of conflict, lack of accountability, avoidance of accountability, and inattention to results. This model highlights the importance of addressing these dysfunctions to achieve effective teamwork (Lencioni, [2002](#)). Each of these models offers insights into the factors that contribute to Team Effectiveness, emphasising the importance of trust, communication, commitment, accountability, and addressing potential dysfunctions.

Nevertheless, while previous team models offer valuable reflections, they fail to account for a crucial aspect that is central to my study: role clarification. A trait that is prominently featured in Interprofessional Collaboration models from the healthcare environment, which will be explained in the following section.

Effective Collaborative Practices Taken from Other Disciplines.

Collaborative good practices in healthcare environments encompass Interprofessional Collaboration among healthcare professionals from various disciplines, such as physicians, nurses, pharmacists, and therapists, to provide comprehensive and coordinated patient care. These environments could be comparable to a higher education institution in terms of bureaucracy complexity and hierarchical approaches.

D'Amour et al. (2005) declared that Interprofessional Collaboration is collaborating together while acknowledging, trusting, and appreciating the diverse skills and knowledge that healthcare professionals from various training backgrounds bring to the table in delivering patient care. Courtney (2013) stated: "An interprofessional approach has the potential to invigorate higher education by allowing it to reap the benefits of fuller contributions from different professional groups" (Courtney, 2013, p. 50). This author also declared that at the heart of Interprofessional Collaboration lies the necessity for professional groups to comprehend the roles and duties of other professionals, coming together to form collaborative teams. The distorting of boundaries in higher education brings the necessity for different professionals to learn from one another. While this sharing of knowledge may already occur sporadically, for it to be most impactful and benefit different staff groups, strategic leadership and support are needed to foster Interprofessional Collaboration systematically (Courtney, 2013). In the same line, in

[2018](#), Mclaney et al. from the Sunnybrook Health Sciences Centre⁶ presented the Sunnybrook's Core Competencies for Interprofessional Team Collaboration (Figure 3.1).

Figure 3.1 – Sunnybrook's Core Competencies for an Interprofessional Team Collaboration

Source: Adapted from Mclaney et al. ([2018](#), p. 2)

It is an all-embracing framework that contains the needed competencies and its corresponding behaviours ([Appendix C](#) – Sunnybrook's Core Competencies and Behaviours) to ensure constructive collaboration within interprofessional teams. One of these abilities is role clarification, which is a key element in addressing my second Research Question about whether EMJMDs increase the recognition of professional staff's work.

⁶ A leading academic health sciences centre in Toronto, Canada

This Framework outlines core competencies for Interprofessional Collaboration, providing an organised approach to effectively work together. Its significance lies in several aspects such as: (i) giving clear guidance on essential competencies and behaviours so team members understand what is expected of them in collaborative settings; (ii) promoting communication while encouraging respect, shared values, and clear roles and responsibilities; (iii) improving the outcomes by offering a comprehensive and coordinated experience; and (iv) providing team members a complete skillset to be equipped to work effectively in interprofessional teams.

Since I did not find a Theoretical Framework that was entirely suitable for my study, I merged multiple concepts that contained elements that were relevant to my Research Questions. By combining these elements, I developed a customised Theoretical Framework that responded to the specific needs of this study. This Theoretical Framework, in turn, informed the development of the Conceptual Framework used for data gathering and analysis, presented the last section of this chapter.

3.3 Theoretical Framework

To fully comprehend the intricate collaboration between professional staff and academics within EMJMDs *Third Space* and determine the existence of a ‘divide’, I developed a Theoretical Framework that encompassed the crucial concepts pertinent to my research topic: the ‘divide’, the *Third Space* and collaboration. The interrelation between these three key concepts provided me with the guidelines for the data collection.

3.3.1 Strategies for Overcoming a Dysfunctional Relationship

With the aim of selecting a concept that could be suitable for this research in terms of overcoming the ‘divide’, the model of “Dispositional Contexts Model” offered by Del Favero and Bray ([2005](#)) offers elements to reach the ideal interaction among professional staff and

academics. The authors highlighted the challenges that complicate collaboration and shared governance within higher education institutions due to different motivations, divides, and structural issues. They proposed a conceptual framework with models associated with academic and professional staff interactions to handle these issues. Their conceptual framework was grounded in the intersection of two key theories: relational attitude and cohesion among academics. The relationships can then be understood as a grid of attitudes and dispositions represented along those two axes of relational attitude and academic cohesion. The relational attitude theory focuses on the perceptions and dispositions that individuals hold toward one another within a relationship, which depend on their attitude (Del Favero & Bray, [2005](#)). Even more, as stated by Olufemi ([2012](#)):

Attitude refers to feelings, beliefs, and reactions of an individual towards an event, phenomenon, objects or person. Attitudes are not innate attributes of mankind. They are learnt, relatively stable but can be modified. Attitudes could be implicit or explicit, conscious or unconscious, rational or irrational; extraversion or introversion. Attitudes are evaluations people make about objects, ideas, events or other people. Attitudes can be positive or negative (Olufemi, [2012](#), p. 61).

This leads to the point that the relationship quality is influenced by the prevailing attitudes of the individuals involved, which can significantly affect the collaboration itself and the decision-making processes. Therefore, if one staff group is inclined to bias and prejudice towards another staff group, the relationship and consequent collaboration can be affected. However, these relational attitudes are not static but can shift based on interactions and experiences within the institution (Del Favero & Bray, [2005](#)); hence, it is important to experience good relationships and learn from good practices.

The framework presented by Del Favero and Bray ([2005](#)) can be compared to previous frameworks and theories in higher education. Still, it distinguishes itself by focusing on the attitudes and contexts aiming to enhance the effectiveness of the relationship between academic

and professional staff. For example, Kezar and Eckel (2004) emphasised the importance of collaborative governance and the need for a comprehensive understanding of group interactions within governance processes, highlighting the necessity of fostering relationships marked by mutual respect and trust. Similarly to the Del Favero and Bray (2005) framework, Kezar and Eckel (2004) advocated shifting from traditional hierarchical models to more inclusive, relationship-focused governance systems. The institutional models Birnbaum (1988) presented defined different models in higher education, including the bureaucratic, collegial, and political governance models. Their collegial model highlights shared governance and participation in decision-making, which resonates with the Del Favero and Bray (2005) framework regarding staff interactions. Finally, the work of Baldrige et al. (2000) and Dill (1991), highlighted the tensions between academic autonomy and administrative oversight, while Del Favero and Bray (2005) framework adds depth by focusing on the relational attitudes and cohesion between academics that can either mitigate or exacerbate these tensions.

Within the Del Favero and Bray (2005) grid, there are four models of interactions: “Symbiotic Functioning”, “Wary Collaboration”, “Fractured Dissension”, and “Aggressive Discord” (Figure 3.2). Each model represents a different level of academic cohesion and relational attitude, which, in turn, influence the behaviour and culture of the institution. In the “Wary Collaboration” model, occasional disagreements arise due to the academics’ lack of unanimity, encouraging cautious collaboration between professional staff and academics, often without complete openness and trust. In the bottom left-hand quadrant, the “Fractured Dissension” model, distrust and conflict between academics and professional staff prevail, with discordance spread among fragmented groups. Not all academics oppose the professional staff uniformly, often resulting from internal disagreements over their desire of collaboration with professional staff. The top left-hand quadrant, the “Aggressive Discord” model, represents complete opposition from academics towards professional staff and their goals. Although not all

Figure 3.2 – The Dispositional Contexts Model

Source: Del Favero & Bray (2005, p. 64)

academics are against the administration individually, this leads to an environment which encourages academics initiatives without the presence of professional staff.

Finally, in the last quadrant on the top right-hand, the model of “Symbiotic Functioning”, professional staff and academics collaborate effectively with mutual respect, negotiating strategies and policies to benefit the institution and its members (Del Favero & Bray, 2005). This last model represents the effective relationship between the two groups and is fundamental to guarantee the effectiveness of higher education institutions’ shared governance, which is the basis for a more egalitarian and less hierarchical relationship. Consequently, the “Symbiotic Functioning” placed in the upper right quadrant was the type of interaction expected to be found within the EMJMDs.

Divides, mistrust, or academics prioritising academic concerns over professional staff who give precedence to institutional objectives produce an adversarial mindset that can only create barriers to effective collaboration and communication, ultimately undermining the quality of education. Building trust through open dialogue and mutual respect is essential for improving

relational attitudes and fostering a more egalitarian atmosphere in which interprofessional collaboration offers the most benefits in settings such as the *Third Space*, where different staff categories can efficiently work together.

3.3.2 Unlocking the Value of Third Spaces

The second concept that was included in my Theoretical Framework was the *Third Space* proposed by Whitchurch ([2008a](#), [2013](#)). Although Whitchurch does not explicitly mention international projects, the projects listed can be related in one way or another to the internationalisation of higher education and, consequently, to an EMJMD. Specifically, the similarities with EMJMDs made me select it as part of the Theoretical Framework. The “Community and Business Partnership” within the “Institutional Projects” (Figure 3.3) mentioned by the author has similarities with any cooperation project, which allows students to enrich their knowledge exchange by being exposed to external partners. Likewise, “Student Experience” and “Learning Support” are intrinsic to any international academic programme. These elements symbolise the foundation for a transformative academic journey, which can be similar to the experience of participating in an EMJMD. In addition, *Third Spaces* offer “some respite from time and organisational pressures, providing opportunities to experiment, to develop novel applications and to form new relationships” (Whitchurch, [2013](#), p. 84), which are essential for the accomplishment of any international project.

3.3.3 Interprofessional Collaboration as a Foundation for Staff Relationships in Mixed Teams

The last concept included in my Theoretical Framework is related to Interprofessional Collaboration. The Sunnybrook Framework (McLaney et al., [2018](#)) (Figure 3.1) was previously explained and even if it was designed for healthcare settings, its principles can be easily adapted

Figure 3.3 – Institutional Projects

Source: Extracted from Whitchurch ([2013](#), p. 25)

for use in higher education because it encompasses all the key elements that must be present within a team for a positive collaborative relationship: trust, respect, clear roles, shared decision-making, positive communication and collective conflict resolution. As in healthcare, collaboration among different staff categories in higher education is crucial for achieving common goals. By applying the principles of the Sunnybrook Framework, professional staff and academics can foster a culture of collaboration and teamwork among their groups.

Figure 3.4 represents the convergence of the three aforementioned theoretical perspectives, which collectively provide the foundation for my study's Theoretical Framework. The Dispositional Contexts proposed by Del Favero and Bray ([2005](#)) examines how professional

Figure 3.4 – Study’s Theoretical Framework

Source: Author’s own work

staff and academics’ individual dispositions, perceptions, and behaviours shape their interactions and relationships. The concept of the *Third Space*, introduced by Whitchurch ([2008a](#), [2013](#)), offers a new setting where the blurring of traditional boundaries allows staff to engage in different roles that go beyond the conventional designations, allowing the emergence and recognition of blended professionals, who are increasingly common within EMJMDs programmes. Finally, the Sunnybrook Framework (McLaney et al., [2018](#)) for Interprofessional Cooperation offered not only the behaviours but also the competencies needed to foster an effective collaboration among staff categories.

My Theoretical Framework facilitated the study’s conceptualisation and streamlined the process of designing and refining the research tools essential for data collection. By using these concepts and their main features, it was possible to understand the type of collaboration among staff categories working in an EMJMD *Third Space* and verify whether it was possible – or not – to overcome the ‘divide’. My study and Theoretical Framework made use of previous concepts but, at the same time, took them a step further. Del Favero and Bray ([2005](#)) stated that the

dispositional contexts described in the outlined model can serve as a tool for studying professional staff relationships empirically and enhancing the implementation of shared governance in practice. Consequently, they can also be applied to an EMJMD. In the *Third Space* concept (Whitchurch, [2008a](#), [2013](#)), international projects are not explicitly mentioned. Hence, it is possible to incorporate all the internationalisation of higher education actions within this concept and apply it to future research.

Lastly, the Sunnybrook Framework (McLaney et al., [2018](#)) has been designed and implemented in healthcare settings. However, its core components and behaviours are a valid contribution to any team context and provide an interesting and valuable interdisciplinary approach. The framework promotes better communication and efficiency among various professional categories by emphasising collaboration, adaptability, and shared decision-making. Its relevance goes beyond healthcare, providing valuable insights that enhance teamwork, trust, respect, and problem-solving in different organisational settings, such as higher education institutions.

3.4 Conceptual Framework to Ensure an Effective Professional Staff-Academic

Collaboration

After conducting the review of the theoretical and empirical literature, a Conceptual Framework was developed (Figure 3.5) with three main dimensions which describe the factors needed for an enriching relationship among professional staff, academics and blended professionals working in an EMJMD: Collaborative Mindset, Team Effectiveness and Job Satisfaction. These three dimensions and their associated factors were defined based on the elements of the ideal scenario for a symbiotic interaction, described by Del Favero and Bray ([2005](#)). This ideal scenario is characterised by mutual trust, respect, effective communication, shared goals, and the understanding of different viewpoints. When these elements are combined with the reflection, conflict resolution, role clarification, and shared decision-making from the Sunnybrook's

framework (2018), in a “new *Third Space*” in which professional staff and academics can interact, it is expected to lead to a positive working environment.

Figure 3.5 – Conceptual Framework: Positive Collaboration Dimensions and Factors

Source: Author’s own work

As a consequence, individuals will exhibit a supportive attitude and develop specific behaviours and skills to work together constructively. In this way, the interactions and knowledge exchange among team members will create collaborative roles instead of autonomous roles (MacNaughton et al., 2013), and this collaborative behaviour brings trust, respect, and a sense of shared purpose within a team (McLaney et al., 2018; Rosen et al., 2018). This, in turn, will be reflected in the degree to which individuals feel satisfied and have good feelings about their jobs (Bella, 2023), which translates to a willingness to engage constructively with their colleagues and support one another. In other words, an effective teamwork with strong connections can be characterised by clear roles, defined responsibilities, aligned objectives, and a spirit of camaraderie, which reinforces the interpersonal bonds because openness breeds confidence, and confidence breeds loyalty (LaFasto, 2001).

Hence, the combination of collaborative skills, personal contentment, and team cohesion creates a context where staff can develop meaningful, productive relationships built on mutual understanding and a shared commitment to the programme's success. Consequently, when Collaborative Mindset, Team Effectiveness, Job Satisfaction and their corresponding factors function correctly, the achievement of common goals through joint endeavours in complex environments such as an EMJMD should be possible.

3.4.1 First Dimension: Mastering the Collaborative Mindset

The first dimension, Collaborative Mindset, is intended as the competency needed for the collaboration between professionals as defined by Barr (1998): (i) describe one's role and responsibilities; (ii) recognise the limitations of one's own roles; (iii) recognise and respect roles, duties, expertise and limitations of other professions; (iv) know when, where and how to involve other professionals; (v) work with other professionals to enhance standards, solve problems and conflicts; (vi) work with other professions to assess, plan, and review; (vii) tolerate differences, misunderstandings, uncertainties, limitations and changes in other professions; (viii) create interdependent relationships, and support other professionals; (ix) learn from other professions; and (x) facilitate interprofessional meetings, teamworking and networking (Barr, 1998, p. 185). A Collaborative Mindset promotes productivity, creativity, and a sense of collective accomplishment, transforming the workplace into an environment where professional staff, academics, and blended professionals can work together seamlessly. When team members adopt a collaborative approach, characterised by a shared vision, open communication, and a willingness to reinforce each other's unique skills and perspectives, it can lead to significant benefits.

3.4.2 Second Dimension: Perfecting the Art of Working Together

The second dimension, Team Effectiveness, is based on a statement from Rubin et al. (1975), which was complemented and completed in the following years. Initially, Rubin et al. (1975) declared: “If a task or job to be done requires the interdependent efforts of two or more people, then a team situation exists. Interdependent means that the individuals involved must work together and coordinate their activities with each other” (Rubin et al., 1975, p. 2). Almost two decades later, Katzenbach and Smith (1994) mentioned that: “[r]eal teams are deeply committed to their purpose, goals, and approach. High-performance team members are also very committed to one another” (Katzenbach & Smith, 1994, p. 9). After ten years, LaFasto and Larson (2001) enriched the concept of Team Effectiveness by declaring that the right people and a straightforward relationship is needed for a positive environment because transparency creates confidence, and confidence develops loyalty. In addition, they also mentioned the relevance of clear roles because, in their absence, team members are not capable of fully committing to the advancement of different projects (LaFasto & Larson, 2001).

Even more, while efficacy means accomplishing one’s goals and efficiency is carrying out activities in the most cost-effective manner possible, the term “[e]ffectiveness means doing proper things” (Patel, 2021, p.34). In other words, the extent to which intentional results, aims, or purposes are attained as a result of an action or initiative meant to have a specific outcome with a degree of success (Patel 2021). Citing Hackman (1987), Team Effectiveness is seen as the mixture of three elements: team performance (results), team functioning, and team viability (Hackman, 1987), and comprises elements such as: (i) psychological safety & trust; (ii) adaptability & resilience; (iii) attitudes (feel); (iv) behaviours (do); (v) cognitions (think); (vi) organisation; (vii) leadership ; (viii) technical competencies; and (ix) clear roles & purpose (Zajac et al., 2021). In essence, effectiveness is a combination of the results that the team can achieve (also known as team performance or outcomes), how the team functions while working together

each day (team functioning), and the degree to which the team believes that they will be working together productively in the future (viability) (Hackman, [1987](#)).

Additionally, the Sunnybrook's Core Competencies for Interprofessional Team Collaboration (McLaney et al., [2018](#)) were also considered for this second dimension. The six core competencies and specific behaviors outlined in the framework offer a thorough understanding of the skills necessary within a collaborative mixed team.

3.4.3 Third Dimension: The Path to Professional Fulfilment

The last dimension, Job Satisfaction, has multiple facets, such as effective management, communication, facilities, benefits (including salaries) and career prospects (Al-Jenaibi, [2010](#)). Job Satisfaction has been on the agenda of industrial and organisational psychology research given that most people spend a significant portion of their lives at work, and understanding the elements that impact work happiness can enhance general welfare (Staples & Higgin, [1998](#)). The Job Satisfaction dimension appeared in the literature in the 1960s with Herzberg's dual or two-factor theory (Volkwein & Parmley, [2000](#); Smerek & Peterson, [2007](#)), and later it was applied to higher education (Smerek & Peterson, [2007](#)). The theory classified the work aspects into intrinsic job content and extrinsic job context (Volkwein & Parmley, [2000](#)). The first aspect, also called motivators, includes "achievement, recognition, work itself, responsibility, advancement, and growth" (Smerek & Peterson, [2007](#), p. 230). The second, or hygiene aspects, are salaries, relationships, supervision, status, security, physical working conditions and others (Volkwein & Parmley, [2000](#); Smerek & Peterson, [2007](#)). In addition, "[j]ob satisfaction has been studied as the outcome of some factors (antecedents such as pay, work conditions, and management practices) or as the cause of some effects (consequences such as employee performance, absenteeism, and life satisfaction)" (Staples & Higgin, [1998](#), p. 212).

Due to its multidimensionality, it is erroneous to believe that increased satisfaction in one aspect of a job results in satisfaction with other job aspects (Al-Jenaibi, [2010](#)). For example,

employees can be satisfied with job security and dissatisfied with their responsibilities (Jung & Shin, 2015). Consequently, “management in higher educational institutions should design a pleasant working environment for their employees by taking into consideration their welfare facilities and satisfaction” (Hanaysha, 2016, p. 139).

When team members adopt a collaborative approach, characterised by a shared vision, open communication, and a willingness to reinforce each other’s unique skills and perspectives, it can lead to significant benefits. Models of Team Effectiveness and Interprofessional Collaboration provide insights into the key factors that contribute to high-performing teams, including trust, accountability, conflict resolution, decision-making and the ability to navigate different stages of team development to create a solid team. When these elements of Team Effectiveness are combined with a Collaborative Mindset, they can foster greater Job Satisfaction, as individuals feel supported, engaged, and empowered to contribute to shared goals. Ideally, higher education institutions should promote a culture that bridges traditional divides between staff categories, underlining the strengths of different perspectives and enhancing overall institutional performance and individual well-being.

3.5 Integrating All Concepts Together: A Holistic Perspective

In this section, I describe how all of the concepts from my Theoretical Framework and my Conceptual Framework are integrated to create a logical and organised basis for my study. My Conceptual Framework gave me a means of putting these theories into practice, while the Theoretical Framework gave me the main ideas, theories, and prior knowledge that directed the study and gave me a wide perspective. As a result, this integration guarantees that abstract theories and real-world applications are in line, improving the validity of my research and modifying pre-existing theories to fit the EMJMDs setting. It also shows that my research is based on previous research and was customised for these master's degrees.

The three main concepts in my Theoretical Framework—the *Third Space* (Whitchurch, [2008a](#), [2013](#)), the Dispositional Contexts Model (Del Favero & Bray, [2005](#)), and the Sunnybrook Framework (McLaney et al., [2018](#))—are intimately related to a Collaborative Mindset. The capacity and willingness of people to cooperate in order to achieve a common objective is known as a Collaborative Mindset. Close relationships will develop among staff members if the attitude of the various staff categories lean toward working together for the good of everyone. This mindset is also essential for *Third Space* since it enables many professional categories with a range of backgrounds to cohabit and showcase their proficiency. To foster an atmosphere that is open, flexible, and creative—where it is possible to transcend borders, integrate information, and participate in meaningful collaborative practices—staff members with a Collaborative Mindset embrace a variety of viewpoints. This, in turn, fosters learning and growth opportunities. Similarly, a Collaborative Mindset may be considered the foundation of effective Interprofessional Collaboration as mutual respect, trust, and understanding are increased when professionals from other units and disciplines actively seek out each other's knowledge. As a result, individuals transcend their conventional roles, break down traditional organisational structures, and connect more fruitfully in new contexts like the *Third Space* of the EMJMDs. When people have a Collaborative Mindset, they understand that the team's success is dependent on both their own and others' contributions. This improves the entire performance.

Team Effectiveness shows how successfully a team completes its work and meets its objectives. Team members may enhance communication, spread the word about how their jobs complement one another, and improve their attitudes toward other professions by using the Dispositional Contexts Model. All of this will eventually show in the team's performance since they work together to build a more efficient team. Since the *Third Space* creates an atmosphere where staff members may innovate outside of their professional silos and combine their knowledge to solve challenges in ways that aren't feasible in conventional workspaces, Team Effectiveness has the potential to succeed there as well. Additionally, in the *Third Space*, Team

Effectiveness can be seen as each team member's capacity to adjust and draw on a variety of skills and knowledge. Therefore, Team Effectiveness in these spaces also depends on the team members' capacity to incorporate a range of viewpoints, professional experiences, and skill sets into a coherent and actionable project.

According to O'Leary et al. (2009), Job Satisfaction is typically understood as a sense of fulfillment or happiness that people get from their work and is positively correlated with both job performance and employee health. Good relationships with coworkers and employees, effective time management, and sufficient resources are all indicators of Job Satisfaction (Mefi & Nambei, 2021). Hence, respect for one another, supportive and inclusive work environments, and interpersonal interactions, all have an impact on Job Satisfaction. Because it promotes a sense of shared accountability and team accomplishment, also Interprofessional Collaboration is crucial in increasing Job Satisfaction. Individuals may acquire a variety of perspectives and abilities by working with different staff categories, which creates a more dynamic and engaging work environment. Effective teamwork makes staff feel more appreciated, empowered, and supported, which raises their motivation and Job Satisfaction. As a result, Interprofessional Collaboration also contributes to the development of a respectful and reliable culture, which is essential for Job Satisfaction. All this is not possible to achieve if the attitude of the different staff members is not a positive one as the Symbiotic Functioning described in the Dispositional Contexts Model. Regarding the *Third Space*, staff with a variety of professional experiences foster an atmosphere that is both fruitful and satisfying. As a result, when staff realises they are a part of a collaborative environment where their opinions and views are respected, their Job Satisfaction frequently rises. The *Third Space* gives staff the chance to move beyond their job descriptions and participate in more horizontal, collaborative interactions, which fosters a stronger sense of fulfilment and belonging while working towards as a common goal.

Staff who adopt a Collaborative Mindset instantly improve Team Effectiveness by promoting shared accountability, open communication, and active participation. Job Satisfaction

is directly impacted by the team's increased effectiveness since members feel more connected to one another, understand how their work affects the project as a whole, and experience a feeling of accomplishment and belonging. The *Third Space*, where various responsibilities and areas of knowledge may be combined, is fundamental to this process because it enables one individual's contribution to meaningfully enhance the others. By encouraging a culture of adaptation and resilience, the flexibility provided by these new spaces may foster organisational development and growth. This, in turn, has a beneficial effect on Team Effectiveness and Job Satisfaction as staff members feel empowered to make important contributions while promoting mutual respect and improve results.

In conclusion, all of these concepts are linked by a web of mutual advantage, as well as by theoretical frameworks and practical implementations. Figure 3.6 illustrates the interconnections between the Theoretical and Conceptual Frameworks of this study.

Figure 3.6 – Interconnections between the Theoretical and Conceptual Frameworks

Source: Author's own work

A Collaborative Mindset empowers and enhances the successful functioning in the *Third Space* because it fosters Interprofessional Collaboration, which in turn increases Team Effectiveness

and Job Satisfaction in shared work environments like the *Third Space*. Therefore, when combined, they create a setting that values Interprofessional Collaboration, which enhances team performance and increases Job Satisfaction accordingly.

3.6 My Conceptual Framework in the Context of the EMJMDs

The performance of both individuals and institutions in the EMJMDs is enhanced by the interplay of three key elements in my conceptual framework: Collaborative Mindset, Team Effectiveness, and Job Satisfaction. A collaborative approach among professional staff, academics, and blended professionals ensures the smooth operation of these academic programmes, fostering an environment where everyone's contributions are valued. This, in turn, leads to greater Job Satisfaction, as staff members feel engaged, supported, and recognised for their efforts. When staff can collaborate effectively, work within diverse teams, and observe the impact of their contributions, they are more likely to have a fulfilling and rewarding professional experience.

Since staff in EMJMDs must collaborate on various tasks—such as developing curricula and managing administrative responsibilities—it is essential to create a supportive and cohesive environment to ensure the success of the programmes. A Collaborative Mindset is crucial for effectively engaging with colleagues and partner institutions across different countries, academic disciplines, and cultural backgrounds. Given the international and multidisciplinary nature of the programme, staff members need to be flexible in their roles, open to new ideas, and capable of adapting to diverse situations. They should also take a proactive approach to foster a culture of collaboration by adjusting their daily tasks and procedures in response to changing demands. This level of adaptability contributes to Team Effectiveness, which in turn enhances Job Satisfaction and is vital for productive collaboration. Furthermore, the Collaborative Mindset promoted within EMJMDs helps develop cross-cultural competencies. This capability aids staff in managing international teams and creates a more inclusive workplace, improving daily tasks

and personal growth. Ultimately, these factors lead to increased Job Satisfaction among team members.

Team Effectiveness is crucial for staff working within the EMJMDs, as it ensures that all aspects of the programme—teaching, administration, and services—function cohesively. When staff members collaborate effectively, it enhances programme delivery, leading to higher job satisfaction; individuals feel a sense of accomplishment when the programme runs smoothly and meets its goals. Moreover, Job Satisfaction within EMJMDs is influenced by other factors, including professional development opportunities, intercultural and international exposure, global connections, a sense of achievement, and a supportive work environment, among others. Therefore, it is reasonable to assert that the performance of the EMJMDs largely results from the collaborative efforts of all staff members. A Collaborative Mindset and Team Effectiveness significantly impact Job Satisfaction. Staff members are more likely to feel valued and motivated in their roles when they work in a supportive environment and engage in high levels of collaboration with their colleagues.

Furthermore, there are certain characteristics of EMJMDs that should be taken into account:

- (i) Staff frequently collaborate in decision-making processes across different levels, ranging from academic programme planning to administrative management. This collaborative approach can empower staff members by enabling them to share their insights and expertise. Such empowerment positively influences Team Effectiveness and enhances Job Satisfaction, as staff feel respected and recognise that their contributions are valued and essential to the programme's success.
- (ii) The EMJMDs are highly complex and well-structured programmes. As a result, staff often face challenges that require collaborative problem-solving. In this environment, staff are encouraged to brainstorm ideas and address issues together, which enhances their ability to respond effectively to problems. Whether it involves resolving procedural difficulties, addressing student concerns, or overcoming cultural barriers,

teamwork in these multicultural and dynamic settings help to find the most suitable solutions for everyone involved. Additionally, solving problems as a group fosters a sense of accomplishment, as staff leverage their collective capacity to overcome challenges. This collaboration not only equips them with the skills and confidence needed to handle complex situations but also contributes to increased Job Satisfaction.

- (iii) A Collaborative Mindset can lead to the development of peer support systems. Hence, staff working in EMJMDs often establish both informal and formal networks of collaboration. These networks provide support, share best practices, and create opportunities for professional growth. When staff members engage in these networks, they develop a sense of community and shared purpose, which enhances Team Effectiveness and increases Job Satisfaction. As a result, staff members feel more confident and secure in their roles, connected to their colleagues both professionally and personally, fostering a sense of belonging.
- (iv) Collaborative goal-setting fosters a shared sense of purpose, and achieving these goals leads to greater Job Satisfaction. Staff members feel that their work contributes to the overall success of the programme. In the case of the EMJMDs, setting collective goals is a common practice. This approach enhances Team Effectiveness and Job Satisfaction among staff because having clear and shared objectives, and working together to achieve them, creates a sense of accomplishment when these goals are reached.
- (v) After achieving key milestones within the EMJMDs, it is common practice to hold collective reflection sessions. These sessions allow staff to evaluate what worked well, identify areas for improvement, and discuss how they can enhance their practices for the future. This ongoing learning process promotes a Collaborative Mindset and ensures Team Effectiveness, as it enables staff to learn from each other's experiences.

When staff see that their feedback is valued and implemented, it improves their overall Job Satisfaction. Additionally, these reflection sessions contribute to creating a culture of continuous improvement, which is essential for achieving the high academic standards of the EMJMDs.

- (vi) A key element of Team Effectiveness is having a shared vision. In an EMJMD, this vision is centered on academic excellence and providing a world-class education. When staff members align with this collective vision, their collaboration becomes more focused and purposeful. A shared vision helps staff understand the bigger picture; they are not merely completing tasks but contributing to a greater mission: running a successful academic programme that promotes excellence in education. This sense of purpose enhances Job Satisfaction, as staff can clearly see the positive impact of their efforts.

In conclusion, by promoting a culture of collaboration and empowering staff to work together towards common goals, EMJMDs improve Job Satisfaction, enhance Team Effectiveness, and strengthen the overall impact of these programmes. In essence, EMJMDs create an environment where staff can thrive, feel supported, and make meaningful contributions to the success of their EMJMD.

3.7 Concluding Remarks

By developing a tailored Theoretical Framework and adopting a specific Conceptual Framework, I was able to effectively navigate the complexities of staff collaboration within the EMJMD *Third Space*. This approach not only enabled me to implement the data collection for this research but also allowed me to uncover the intricacies of staff collaboration and its impact. The following chapters will delve into the details of the data collection process and the findings that emerged from it, providing a comprehensive understanding of the dynamics of staff collaboration in this unique context. Additionally, the chapters will explore the implications of these findings for

future research and practice, highlighting the potential for my study to inform and improve the development of collaborative environments in various settings.

CHAPTER FOUR: CRAFTING MY RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND DESIGN

4.1 Introduction

In this chapter, I explain the overall study design. I describe the rationale for choosing specific research methods, highlighting their suitability in answering my Research Questions and the alignment with the study's objectives. I also outline the data collection techniques, including instruments and procedures for gathering the necessary information. Finally, I describe the data analysis methods, detailing the steps taken to process, interpret and draw meaningful conclusions from the collected data.

4.2 Formulating My Research Questions

The Research Questions for this study were presented in the Introduction. It is possible to synthesise them by saying that the primary purpose of this study is to understand the type of relationships and collaboration developed by professional staff and academics while working together on the design, development, launch, and implementation of an international Master's degree.

Understanding this interaction is important for two reasons. The first one is related to verifying if working in an EMJMD changes the type of collaboration between the two main staff groups working within higher education institutions – frequently marked by hierarchical approaches – to understand its features and the reasons behind how these individuals collaborate. The second one is to validate if participants' perceptions of collaboration between professional staff and academics changed in terms of an added value to those involved and also in enhancing the recognition of the role and work of professional staff.

4.3 Outline of the Research Approach

In order to provide an in-depth understanding of the essence and nuances of the relationship between professional staff and academics in an EMJMD environment, this study adopted a

mixed-method research design, using both quantitative and qualitative research methods. Creswell (2002) and previously other authors such as Greene et al. (1989) emphasised that a mixed-methods design has the potential to offer a more exhaustive response to a study's Research Questions. Similarly, for Mertler and Charles (2008), when both quantitative and qualitative data are collected and equally emphasised, this enables the researcher to reinforce the strengths of each type of data. In addition, other researchers have promoted quantitative and qualitative approaches as complementary (Tashakkori & Teddlie, 1998; Johnson et al., 2007).

As stated by Creswell (2014), in a mixed-methods design, the pragmatic worldview with a sequential gathering of quantitative and qualitative data offers a more comprehensive understanding of the research topic than either quantitative or qualitative data alone. Hence, it allows the mixed methods researcher to use a variety of approaches, worldviews, and assumptions, as well as various data gathering and analysis techniques (Creswell, 2014). Additionally, since pragmatism does not adhere to a single philosophy or system of reality (Creswell, 2014), I incorporated the transformative worldview into my research. This perspective focuses on the needs, experiences, and lives of groups and individuals who are often overlooked (Creswell, 2014). Aligned with Creswell's insights, my study proposes action plans that aim to enhance the lives of participants and the higher education institutions in which they work. Mainly because "[t]ransformative research provides a voice for these participants, raising their consciousness or advancing an agenda for change to improve their lives. It becomes a united voice for reform and change" (Creswell, 2014, p.10). Figure 4.1 illustrates my study's research approach and the interconnections between worldviews, design and research methods.

The advantages of a mixed-methods approach have been described by several authors. Creswell and Creswell (2018) stated that:

Mixed methods research is an approach to inquiry involving collecting both quantitative and qualitative data, integrating the two forms of data, and using distinct designs that may involve philosophical assumptions and theoretical frameworks. The core assumption of

Figure 4.1 – Research Approach Framework

Source: Adapted for this dissertation from Creswell and Creswell (2018, p. 5).

this form of inquiry is that the integration of qualitative and quantitative data yields additional insight beyond the information provided by either the quantitative or qualitative data alone (Creswell & Creswell, 2018, p. 4).

The rationale for selecting this research design is that it allowed me to use the strengths of both types of data (Mertler & Charles 2008). I opted for a two-phase Explanatory Sequential Design, as shown in Figure 4.2. In this design, an online survey was distributed among different EMJMDs selected, followed-up by semi-structured interviews with a sub-sample of the survey.

Figure 4. 2 – Explanatory Sequential Mixed-Methods Design

Source: Adapted for this research from Creswell and Creswell (2018, p. 218).

4.4 Methodology and Limitations of the Study

My study delves deeply into the dynamics of effective collaboration among diverse staff groups, a critical factor in ensuring the successful development of international projects. As a result, the selection of a mixed-methods methodology was based on the intention of uncovering experiences, by an in-depth exploration of the dynamics at play, highlighting different perceptions and shared opinions. Through combining quantitative data from an online questionnaire ($n = 133$) with qualitative insights from 28 semi-structured interviews it was possible to integrate the data and link the strengths of both methodologies to increase the validity of my findings and provide a deeper, broader understanding of the topic (McKim, [2017](#)). The EMJMDs sample was selected randomly and aimed to have a variety of fields of study and a pool of participants for each staff category (professional staff, academics, and blended professionals). Although it was impossible to compare with the general population since this information was not available, I obtained a high response rate, allowing me to validate the study's assumptions.

My role in the EMJMDs setting is not neutral, demanding careful consideration of potential biases (see section 4.8, Role of the Researcher). Therefore, I sought to remain as objective and self-reflective as possible by seeking feedback from my supervisors and maintaining a solid commitment to self-awareness to ensure a reliable, high-quality study. I adopted this approach from the initial formulation of questions for the online questionnaire and the structuring of interviews to every stage of the data analysis process as a way to systematically address and mitigate various biases that might influence the research outcomes.

4.5 Advantages and challenges of the Explanatory Sequential Mixed-Methods Design

Scholars such as Greene and Caracelli ([1997](#)), Creswell ([2002](#)), Moghaddam et al. ([2003](#)) and others have extensively addressed the benefits and disadvantages of mixed-methods approaches. Some of the benefits in this design are: (i) it is helpful for a more exhaustive examination of

quantitative findings, (ii) it enables the comparison of findings from both quantitative and qualitative methods, and (iii) it offers methodological flexibility, enabling researchers to adjust their approach based on the findings of the quantitative strand (Creswell, [2014](#)).

Nevertheless, there are also some challenges related to this research design. The main challenges are related to the significant resources and time that are required to complete and analyse the distinct stages of data collection (Almeida, [2018](#)). This holds both for the investment into the data collection itself, as well as in terms of training the involved researcher(s), as it means they need to become familiar with a more varied set of methodologies and analytical techniques.

4.6 Selecting the EMJMD Consortiums

By retrieving information from the online Erasmus Mundus Catalogue⁷ offered by the European Commission's European Education and Culture Executive Agency, I randomly contacted EMJMD directors and invited them to participate in my research. The selection began in November 2019 and was concluded in April 2020, when the directors of 26 consortiums confirmed their availability. These EMJMD consortiums varied in terms of size and study field, but were well established and successful programmes. The coordinating institutions of each EMJMD assisted me in administering the questionnaires and organising the follow-up interviews.

4.7 Research Tools for Data Collection

4.7.1 Quantitative Data Collection

Questionnaires are used to statistically represent the tendencies, attitudes, and views of a certain group, as stated by Creswell and Creswell ([2018](#)). Furthermore, surveys respond to different

⁷ https://www.eacea.ec.europa.eu/scholarships/erasmus-mundus-catalogue_en

kinds of inquiries: queries that are descriptive and queries that relate to the relationships between variables as well as the predictions of those relationships over time (Creswell & Creswell, [2018](#)). In addition, online questionnaires are flexible and present the advantages of being time-savers, easily and quickly arriving to any respondent, cost-effective, and providing automation so participants can rapidly complete them (Ball, [2019](#)). Besides, they facilitate the acquisition of numerous amounts of data, may be disseminated by non-researchers without damaging the validity and reliability, are analysed using a software, and are appropriate for diverse research domains (Taherdoost, [2021](#)).

The online questionnaire was specifically developed for this project, considering the three dimensions of my Conceptual Framework (Collaborative Mindset, Team Effectiveness, and Job Satisfaction) to address the research questions of my study. They served as the foundation for examining changes in staff collaboration and how these changes shape their understanding of their roles, their experiences of working together, and the overall benefits of being part of an EMJMD. As staff collaborate, they evolve and create a more interconnected, effective, and supportive environment, which should enhance the EMJMD experience. More specifically, the participatory approach to programme design and implementation allows all staff members to have a voice, thereby strengthening the Collaborative Mindset and increasing Job Satisfaction. This occurs because staff feel valued, supported, and acknowledged for their contributions. Consequently, the Collaborative Mindset influences how staff interact, communicate, and perceive each other's roles, ultimately shaping the effectiveness of their collaboration. As a result, Team Effectiveness is enhanced through these collaborative practices, which foster communication, build trust, and leverage diverse skills, finally benefiting the programme.

Further details about the study accompanied each questionnaire on the online landing page, where also the consent to participate was included. The questionnaire itself was structured in three sections. The first section aimed to gather respondents' demographic data (gender, university, consortium, age, level of education, nationality, role, years of service, and others). In

the second section – the core of the survey – closed-ended statements were used to explore the essence of the staff collaboration. Respondents could mention how they perceived collaborative behaviours or attitudes in the EMJMD team in their institution and within the consortium on five-point Likert scales. The third and last section of the questionnaire had two open-ended questions to allow participants to share other relevant information (de Leeuw et al., [2008](#)) that could be linked to the Research Questions. In addition, on the survey's last page, respondents could mention if they wanted – or not – to be part of the second phase of the project (the qualitative data gathering).

Before implementing the survey, I conducted a pilot test to ensure the questionnaire's reliability. It helped me to establish the content validity and consistency of the items, improve the questions, and check the presentation, format, wording, length, and instructions (Creswell & Creswell, [2018](#)). The preliminary study was conducted in April 2021 with colleagues and experts in higher education internationalisation from CHEI. A total of 21 participants took part in the survey, with the following gender distribution: women ($n = 11$) and men ($n = 10$). Participants were further categorised based on their roles: professional staff ($n = 8$), academics ($n = 6$), and blended professionals ($n = 7$). Suggestions and comments from the pilot testing were incorporated into the final version ([Appendix D](#) – Online Questionnaire). The questionnaire was distributed to the 26 selected consortiums in May and June 2021. More information about this phase and the selected respondents are presented in the following chapter, which contains the quantitative results.

4.7.2 Qualitative Data Collection

Since the purpose of this study was to gain a holistic understanding of participants' thoughts, feelings, and perceptions on collaboration within EMJMDs, semi-structured interviews were considered to be the most effective qualitative research method to complement the results obtained from the quantitative phase.

With the quantitative results in mind, and considering again the study's Conceptual Framework and my Research Questions, an interview protocol was created for the qualitative data collection ([Appendix E](#) – Interview Protocol Designed for this Study). During the interview, participants were asked to describe their educational background and work experience, to mention positive and negative, satisfying and frustrating aspects of their roles, and also to describe challenges faced (Ryttberg & Geschwind, [2017](#)) in achieving career aspirations. They were also asked to provide accurate information about how the EMJMDs were developed, the division of roles and responsibilities among co-workers and the sources – such as expertise and/or level of education – that validated their credibility among other team members, as well as the challenges experienced in their daily work.

A sub-sample of 28 survey participants was selected for interviews based on their willingness to discuss the survey topics in more detail. Nearly half of the 81 individuals contacted after the survey responded when reached out again. To ensure a balanced sample, participants were selected based on their roles and gender distribution while keeping the sample size manageable for a doctoral study. At the end of the interview, all participants were also free to express their opinions on any other relevant aspect, enriching the research topic.

4.7.3 Bridging Perspectives: Integrating Quantitative and Qualitative Insights

The mixed method design used for my study aimed to capture different angles from participants' perspectives while comparing and contrasting qualitative and quantitative data. This was done because both qualitative and quantitative research may complement one another and offer a more comprehensive understanding of the problem being studied (Flick, [2018](#)). Even more, there is also the idea that this combination is based on the uniqueness of each method and that qualitative research has different characteristics than quantitative research (Flick, [2018](#)).

Consequently, my qualitative and quantitative assessments were carried out in two different phases. Still, to guarantee semantic consistency, questions were created considering items from instruments (Njie-Carr, [2014](#)) used in both phases. Afterwards, “[t]he results were then compared and contrasted to identify data convergence and divergence” (Njie-Carr, [2014](#), p. 383), i.e., I triangulated findings. As underlined by Flick ([2009](#)), triangulation is the process by which it is possible to consider several viewpoints on a problem or, more broadly, while addressing research questions. These viewpoints can be supported by different methodologies, but they are or ought to be connected. As a consequence, triangulation yields knowledge on several levels beyond the knowledge made feasible by a single methodology, thus advancing the rigour of a study (Flick, [2009](#)). Conducting the triangulation offered my study the needed reliability an individual project – as a doctoral study conducted by a single researcher – can have since it was the instrument used to evaluate the empirical findings and the way to obtain further information (Flick, [2018](#)). As a consequence of this, my results showed the validity of the methodology used to expand the understanding of the staff members’ collaboration in an EMJMD since two data sources and two methodological techniques were used to cross-validate variables and themes and while assessing the empirical results to gain more insights and knowledge.

4.8 Ethical Considerations and Confidentiality

As the study involved collecting data from people, it was crucial to anticipate ethical problems before starting the study to protect participants, develop trust, prevent misconduct, and respect privacy, among other things (Creswell & Creswell, [2018](#)). For this reason, the questionnaire final version was presented to the Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore’s Ethics Committee for approval. Once clearance was received, the questionnaire was set up using Qualtrics, the online software used for the survey’s distribution ([Appendix F](#) – Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore’s Ethics Committee approval).

Additionally, some of the actions that helped me to address potential ethical issues were the following: (i) participants were informed on the type and aim of the research, their involvement and their right to withdraw at any time; (ii) respondents confirmed their willingness to participate through a checkmark in the first checkbox of the online questionnaire and giving authorisation to record the interview; (iii) confidentiality about participant identities were respected at all times, so a pseudonym was used to protect the participants' anonymity (Creswell & Creswell, [2018](#)); (iv) backup copies containing personal data were stored in secure locations; (v) during the entire study, access to data was limited to myself, except if required for academic supervision (Kostoulas, [2010](#)); (vi) connections about higher education institutions, EMJMDs and individuals were not revealed and would not be revealed in future publications; and (vii) the dissertation and results will be shared with each consortium and participants. No concerns or reservations were expressed by any of the participants.

4.9 Role of the Researcher

Any form of bias can compromise the reliability and validity of a research study (Šimundić, [2013](#)). As a practitioner and blended professional involved in the design, launch, and implementation of master's degrees, I recognise that my perspective is not entirely neutral. Therefore, I took considerable care to minimise biases throughout the study. I clearly defined my hypotheses, methodologies, and the types of analysis to be conducted before beginning the research. Furthermore, I consistently sought input from my supervisors to ensure an impartial evaluation of the methodological tools and data processing used.

First, to avoid "selection bias," which occurs when study participants do not represent the target population (Šimundić, [2013](#)), I used random sampling. This approach allowed me to include every member of the target population, resulting in an adequate sample size that ensured representativeness and minimised "sampling bias" (Šimundić, [2013](#)). Additionally, while designing the online questionnaire, I made sure to eliminate "leading questions and wording

bias" (Shah, [2019](#)). The questions were crafted to be neutral, avoiding language that could guide participants toward a specific response. This strategy was intended to prevent my own preconceived notions from influencing the answers and introducing bias into the data.

During the qualitative phase, semi-structured interviews ensured that all candidates were asked the same questions. This approach provided consistency across interviews while allowing flexibility to explore the unique perspectives that emerged at the end of the conversations, particularly when interviewees were invited to add anything else they considered relevant to my research. To prevent “confirmation bias” (Bergelson et al., [2022](#))—the tendency to seek evidence during interviews that confirms my hypothesis or to ignore contradictory information—I made a conscious effort not to gather or remember information selectively. Instead, I considered all information together to avoid partial interpretations. To address the “halo effect” (Sarniak, [2015](#)) or “halo bias” (Bergelson et al., [2022](#)), where a researcher may overemphasize one positive trait, or conversely, the “horn bias” (Bergelson et al., [2022](#)) that exaggerates one negative trait, I approached the interview responses avoiding the influence of my pre-existing opinions. Including participants from different countries in the study helped mitigate “cultural bias” (Sarniak, [2015](#)) and allowed me to steer clear of assumptions based on cultural lenses. Additionally, to further reduce the impact of “affinity bias” (Bergelson et al., [2022](#)), I consciously avoided favouritism toward interviewees with backgrounds similar to my own. This approach aimed to prevent subjective evaluations and biased interpretations based on shared experiences or affinities.

As advised by Šimundić ([2013](#)), it is crucial to avoid “data manipulation” and “misinterpretation” when interpreting data. To prevent such biases during my data analysis, I refrained from selectively reporting only favourable results or conducting unplanned analyses. I made it a point to include data that did not support my hypothesis. Similarly, I avoided misinterpreting any results solely to align with my opinions. I also took measures to prevent “reporting bias” (Šimundić, [2013](#); Dawson & Dawson, [2018](#)), which involves sharing only

successful outcomes, as this can distort perceptions and create an overly optimistic view of the EMJMDs, a phenomenon referred to as “positive bias” (Tight, [2023](#)). To achieve this, I employed a robust research design and thorough statistical analyses, recognising, as van der Steen et al. ([2019](#)) suggest, that it is essential to report all study findings—both positive and negative—regardless of their magnitude.

4.10 Concluding Remarks

This chapter provided a detailed description of the research procedures selected for my doctoral studies: An Explanatory Sequential Mixed-methods approach. The selection of the EMJMD consortiums and the methods and software used for the data gathering and analysis were also explained. The mixed-methods approach was selected for this research because it allows the use of qualitative data to describe the quantitative results in more detail. In the next chapters, the complete findings of Phase 1 (quantitative) and Phase 2 (qualitative) are presented.

CHAPTER FIVE: EXPLORING THE ‘DIVIDE’

5.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the findings of the first data-gathering process related to the quantitative phase of the study, which aimed to investigate staff relationships in EMJMD’s *Third Space* environments to verify the type of collaboration and the presence or absence of the ‘divide’. The chapter offers a comprehensive overview of the initial procedure for acquiring the data, including the data collection methods, the analysis methodology, and the results. The chapter also discusses the implications of the findings. The results of this chapter provide a foundation for the subsequent chapters, which explore the qualitative phase of the study and integrate the quantitative and qualitative findings.

5.2 Online Questionnaire Distribution

In May and June 2021, the online questionnaire was distributed to the various staff categories within the 26 selected consortiums. The aim was to gather information about their interactions, both within their institution and with consortium partners. Professional staff, academics, and blended professionals involved in the participating EMJMDs were provided with the access link, while efforts were made to ensure representation from the different staff groups by contacting individuals from the three different categories. In the end, I invited 260 staff members from 26 consortiums to participate, leading to 133 valid questionnaires – yielding a response rate of 51.15%.

Since the selection of consortiums was conducted randomly and based on their availability, this resulted in a diverse representation of academic disciplines. Consequently, the EMJMDs studied covered a wide range of fields, including chemistry, art, political science, environmental studies, engineering, and more. Responses from staff members offering master’s degrees in various academic areas provide this study with an interdisciplinary perspective. This allows for the examination of different viewpoints, approaches, and academic traditions,

strengthening the study's validity and promoting a more comprehensive understanding of the "divide" within the EMJMDs. Additionally, this diversity enables the identification of common patterns, challenges, and best practices across disciplines, thereby enhancing the overall analysis and making it more robust and well-rounded.

5.3 Variables

5.3.1 *Dependent Variable*

The dependent variable of this study was the respondents' reply to the statement, "I notice a 'divide' between academic and administrative staff members". Respondents could rate this statement on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree.

Respondents had to indicate how much they agreed with this statement for both the institutional setting and the EMJMD consortium.

5.3.2 *Independent Variables*

Three item banks, measured on five-point Likert scales, were used to create the three independent variables of the study. The first one, Collaborative Mindset, consisted of 15 items, which were adapted from Hinyard et al. (2019), Ushiro (2009), and Thomson et al. (2007). The second scale measured Team Effectiveness and consisted of 16 items borrowed from Sharif and Nahas (2013), Anderson and West (1998), Curran et al. (n.d.), Florenthal and Tolstikov-Mast (2012), Florenthal et al. (2009), LaFasto and Larson (2001), Logan et al. (2019), Singh and Muncherji (2007), and Kenaszchuk et al. (2010). The last one, Job Satisfaction, had 17 items based on Smerek and Peterson (2007), Spector (1994), Rizzo et al. (1970), Alpern et al. (2013), Lyons (1971) and Schuler et al. (1977).

A Principal Component Analysis was conducted to identify the latent variables underlying each scale. The suitability of all items was always verified before the principal component analysis was conducted.

Collaborative Mindset within the institutions. For the Collaborative Mindset within the institutions, the correlation matrix showed coefficients of 0.5 and above. The Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) obtained ($= 0.818$) for three components verified the sampling adequacy for the analysis. Bartlett’s test of sphericity showed 0.000 (p -value: $less < 0.05$), indicating good correlations. The three components got eigenvalues over Kaiser’s criterion of 1 and, in combination, explained 60.436% of the variance. The items that cluster on the same components suggested that Component 1 (*Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient* = 0.825) represented workplace conditions. Instead, Component 2, (Cronbach’s Alpha was not needed because only two variables were loading) explained the individual predisposition. Finally, Component 3 (*Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient* = 0.736) demonstrated the communication skills.

Collaborative Mindset within the EMJMDs consortiums. The correlation matrix showed coefficients of 0.5 and above. The Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) obtained ($= 0.814$) for three components verified the sampling adequacy for the analysis. Bartlett’s test of sphericity showed 0.000 (p -value: $less < 0.05$), indicating good correlations. The three components got eigenvalues over Kaiser’s criterion of 1 and, in combination, explained 66.790% of the variance. The items that clustered on the same components suggested that Component 1 (*Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient* = 0.723) represented workplace conditions, Component 2 (*Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient* = 0.747) demonstrated the individual predisposition and Component 3 (*Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient* = 0.746) explained the relevance of each role.

Team Effectiveness within the institutions. The correlation matrix showed many coefficients of 0.5 and above. The Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) value obtained for the components was 0.860, above the recommended value of 0.6 and verifying the sampling adequacy for the analysis. Bartlett’s test of sphericity was statistically significant, 0.000 (p -value: $less < 0.05$), indicating that correlations between items were sufficiently large. The Principal Component Analysis revealed the presence of three components with eigenvalues exceeding 1 and explained the variance in the following way: Component 1: 45.858 %, Component 2: 12.947% and Component 3: 9.511%. In

combination, all the components explained 68.315% of the variance. The new components reached the minimum value of the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient that should be 0.7 or above. Component 1: 0.829, Component 2: 0.824 and Component 3: 0.803. For this reason, the first component was used to describe the team spirit, the second one explained the goals and leadership, and the third one illustrated the team values.

Team Effectiveness within the EMJMDs consortiums. The correlation matrix showed many coefficients of 0.5 and above. The Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) value obtained for the components was 0.885, above the recommended value of 0.6 and verifying the sampling adequacy for the analysis. Bartlett's test of sphericity was statistically significant, 0.000 (*p-value: less < 0.05*), indicating that correlations between items were sufficiently large. The Principal Component Analysis revealed the presence of two components with eigenvalues exceeding 1 and explained the variance in the following way: Component 1: 53.492 %, Component 2: 8.553% and in combination explained 62.044% of the variance. The new components reached the minimum value of the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient that should be 0.7 or above. Component 1: 0.905 and Component 2: 0.852. For this reason, the first component was used to describe the team spirit, and the second one explained the goals and leadership.

Job Satisfaction within each institution. The correlation matrix showed many coefficients of 0.5 and above. The Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (*KMO = 0.726*) obtained for the components verified the sampling adequacy for the analysis. Bartlett's test of sphericity showed 0.000 (*p-value: less < 0.05*), indicating that correlations between items were sufficiently significant for the Principal Component Analysis. The three components explained 60.739% of the variance, and two of them reached the minimum reliability value of the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient that should be 0.7 or above. Component 1 (*Cronbach's Alpha coefficient = 0.724*) represented motivation and Component 3 (*Cronbach's Alpha coefficient = 0.727*) described the rewards. Component 2 explained the challenges and was also included in the analysis even if the minimum value of the Cronbach's

Alpha coefficient for reliability was not reached (0.567); the reason behind this is that only three variables were loading that component, which explains the low Cronbach's Alpha.

Job Satisfaction within the EMJMDs consortiums. The correlation matrix showed many coefficients of 0.5 and above. The final Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin ($KMO = 0.747$) obtained for the components verified the sampling adequacy for the analysis. Bartlett's test of sphericity showed 0.000 (*p-value: less < 0.05*), indicating that correlations between items were sufficiently significant. Besides, the three components obtained eigenvalues over Kaiser's criterion of 1 and, in combination, explained 53.484% of the variance. Two components reached the minimum reliability value of the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient that should be 0.7 or above. Component 1 (*Cronbach's Alpha coefficient = 0.810*) represented the motivation and Component 2 (*Cronbach's Alpha coefficient = 0.759*) described the rewards. Component 3 explained the challenges and was also included in the analysis even if the minimum value of the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient for reliability was not reached (0.414); the reason behind this is that only two variables were loading that component. It is essential to highlight that while verifying the reliability of Components 2 and 3, those variables that were not related to the component or had a negative value were not included. The number of components obtained for these three independent variables was similar, apart from Team Effectiveness in the consortiums (see Table 5.1).

5.3.3 Control Variables

In the analyses, I controlled for several possible confounding variables, namely gender, job role, age, and region. Gender was measured as a binary variable, 51.9% of the respondents were male, 45% female and 3.1% of the participants did not disclose their gender. As for the role, 54.9% of the respondents were academics, 34.6% were professional staff, and 9.2% were blended professionals. Age was measured as a categorical variable, ranging from 26 to 35 (first group) to 66-75 (last group). Most of the participants were in the group between 46 and 55 years old. Lastly, regarding the region, the majority of the institutions were located in Southern Europe

Table 5.1 – Components Derived from the Principal Component Analysis

	Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO)	Bartlett’s test of sphericity	Explanation of the variance (%)	Components	Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient*
Collaborative Mindset Institutions	0.818	0.000 (p-value: less < 0.05)	60.436%	CMI1: Workplace conditions CMI2: Individual predisposition CMI3: Communication skills	0.825 - 0.736
Collaborative Mindset EMJMDs	0.814	0.000 (p-value: less < 0.05)	66.790%	CMEM1: Workplace conditions CMEM2: Individual predisposition CMEM3: Relevance of each role	0.723 0.747 0.746
Team Effectiveness Institutions	0.860	0.000 (p-value: less < 0.05)	68.315%	TEI1: Team spirit TEI2: Goals and Leadership TEI3: Team Values	0.829 0.824 0.803
Team Effectiveness EMJMDs	0.885	0.000 (p-value: less < 0.05)	62.044%	TEEM1: Team spirit TEEM2: Goals and Leadership	0.905 0.852
Job Satisfaction Institutions	0.726	0.000 (p-value: less < 0.05)	60.739%	JSI1: Motivation JSI2: Challenges JSI3: Rewards	0.724 - 0.727
Job Satisfaction EMJMDs	0.747	0.000 (p-value: less < 0.05),	53.484%	JSEM1: Motivation JSEM2: Rewards JSEM3: Challenges	0.810 0.759 -

*The components without a Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient had only two items and therefore, it was not feasible to obtain such coefficient.

(35.3%), followed by Western Europe (26.3%), Northern Europe (18%), Eastern Europe (12%), and non-EU (3.1%).⁸ Despite the age differences or types of professionals, there were – interestingly – no significant discrepancies by role, age or gender concerning the perception of the ‘divide’. A significant but negative association was found between the perception of the ‘divide’ in certain European regions. Specifically, in Western Europe at the institutional level and in Western and South Europe for the EMJMD consortiums. These findings suggested that respondents in those regions have a lower perception of the ‘divide’.

⁸ The EU regions were divided following the United Nations publication “Standard Country or Area Codes for Statistical Use”, issued initially as Series M, No. 49 and currently indicated as the M49 standard.

5.4 Analytic Strategy

First, the descriptive statistics provided preliminary insights into the perception of the ‘divide’, overall Job Satisfaction, and the components obtained from the Principal Component Analysis for Collaborative Mindset, Team Effectiveness, and Job Satisfaction. This analysis was used to reduce the large dataset obtained from the online survey while maintaining patterns and trends. Afterwards, Hierarchical Multiple Linear Regression was applied to examine the relationship between multiple independent variables and a dependent variable, i.e., to investigate the relationship between the different components and the ‘divide’ perception.

5.5 Results

5.5.1 Descriptive Statistics.

Table 5.2 provides an overview of the descriptive statistics of all variables included in the analysis. During the online survey, participants were asked to respond to the same questions from two different perspectives: first, considering their own institutions, and second, examining the same dynamic within their EMJMD consortium. As can be observed, the overall perception of the ‘divide’ obtained a slightly higher mean value in the institutions ($n = 121$, $M = 2.72$, $SD = 1.312$) compared to the consortiums ($n = 119$, $M = 2.53$, $SD = 1.213$). This indicates that, on average, staff in institutions felt a slightly stronger sense of division compared to those in consortiums. On the contrary, the mean score of Job Satisfaction was higher in the EMJMD consortiums ($n = 126$, $M = 8.20$, $SD = 1.670$) than in the institutions ($n = 127$, $M = 7.80$, $SD = 1.782$) suggesting that staff in consortiums generally reported higher levels of Job Satisfaction than those in institutions.

The correlation analysis showed that in the institutions, there was a statistically significant relationship between the perception of the ‘divide’ and communication skills ($r = 0.307$, $p = 0.002$) and the challenges related to Job Satisfaction ($r = 0.362$, $p = 0.001$). The connection between the perceived ‘divide’ and communication skills suggests that when staff perceived more

Table 5.2 – Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Mean	SD	Range	n		Mean	SD	Range	n
Age	46.93	10.981	27-71	124					
<u>Institutions</u>					<u>EMJMDs consortiums</u>				
Overall perception of the "divide"	2.72	1.312	1-5	121	Overall perception of the "divide"	2.53	1.213	1-5	119
Job satisfaction	7.80	1.782	0-10	127	Job satisfaction	8.20	1.673	0-10	126
CMI1 - Workplace conditions			-3.16-1.45	99	CMEM1 - Workplace conditions			-4.07-1.38	99
CMI2 - Individual predisposition			-2.84-1.65	99	CMEM2 - Individual predisposition			-1.30-3.38	99
CMI3 - Communication skills			-1.12-4.79	99	CMEM3 - Communication skills			-3.42-1.15	99
TEI1 - Team spirit			-2.66-1.14	104	TEEM1 - Team spirit			-4.17-1.04	108
TEI2 - Continuous feedback			-4.42-2.26	104	TEEM2 - Continuous feedback			-3.55-1.22	108
TEI3 - Team values			-4.47-1.15	104	JSEM1 - Motivation			-2.94-1.71	66
JSI1 - Motivation			-3.04-1.52	87	JSEM2 - Challenges			-1.77-2.92	66
JSI2 - Challenges			-2.10-2.40	87	JSEM3 - Rewards			-2.62-2.60	66
JSI3 - Rewards			-2.22-2.21	87					

the 'divide', there were greater effective communication skills to bridge the gaps. Even more pronounced was the relationship between the perceived 'divide' and the challenges related to job satisfaction. The stronger the perception of a 'divide' was, the more staff reported difficulties in feeling satisfied with their work. This correlation implies that feelings about the 'divide' within the institution may significantly impact how content staff feel in their roles.

There was also a statistically significant but negative relationship between the 'divide' perception and workplace conditions ($r = -0.297, p = 0.003$), team spirit ($r = -0.382, p = 0.000$), team values ($r = -0.368, p = 0.000$), motivation related to job satisfaction ($r = -0.236, p = 0.031$), and the rewards ($r = -0.217, p = 0.049$). The connection between the 'divide' and workplace conditions means that when the first one was stronger, staff satisfaction with their work environment tended to diminish. Even more pronounced was the effect of the 'divide' on team spirit. The stronger the perception of a 'divide', the more team cohesion suffers. This negative correlation implies that the feelings of a division can undermine the sense of a collective purpose among staff members leading to decreased collaboration, and a fragmented relationship where staff groups work in silos and not in a cohesive supportive team. Similarly, team values decrease when the 'divide' was perceived more strongly. This suggests that the 'divide' might erode the common ground that connect different staff groups within the institutions. Job satisfaction, particularly in terms of motivation, also showed a negative relationship with the perceived 'divide', indicating that feelings of the 'divide' may reduce staff enthusiasm. Lastly, the perception of rewards was also negatively linked to the sense of 'divide', although to a lesser degree than other factors. This suggests the possibility that feelings of a division might influence how staff view the recognition and compensation they receive for their work which, in turn, can affect their motivation when they do not feel appreciated.

Similarly, in the EMJMD consortiums, a statistically significant positive relationship was also encountered in the perception of the 'divide' and the challenges related to job satisfaction (r

= 0.402, $p = 0.001$). This relationship suggests that as staff members perceive a greater ‘divide’ within the consortium, they also tend to experience more challenges in feeling satisfied with their work. On the contrary, a statistically significant negative relationship in the EMJMD consortiums was found only among the perception of the ‘divide’ and the relevance of the role ($r = -0.245, p = 0.016$) and team spirit ($r = -0.194, p = 0.05$). This negative correlation between the perception of a ‘divide’ and the relevance of one’s role implies that as the sense of division decreases, staff might actually feel that their roles become more relevant or important within the consortium. In the same way, a negative relationship was observed between the perception of a ‘divide’ and team spirit, although with a weaker correlation. This suggests that as perceptions of division diminish, there might be a tendency for team spirit to improve. This could potentially indicate that small groups or teams within the consortium might bond more closely in response to perceived divisions in the larger organisation where the statistically significant negative relationship was stronger ($r = -0.382, p = 0.000$). This finding highlights how perceptions of division can potentially impact the overall work experience and contentment of individuals within the EMJMDs because a positive working atmosphere and a supportive team work – where trust and respect guide the relationships – is fundamental for the success of these degrees.

5.5.2 Hierarchical Multiple Linear Regression.

The final step of the analysis was a Hierarchical Multiple Linear Regression to find associations between the perception of the ‘divide’ and Collaborative Mindset, Team Effectiveness, and Job Satisfaction, controlling for possible confounding variables.

The stepwise analysis is presented in Table 5.3. Model I (Collaborative Mindset) includes the control variables role, region, gender, and age. It showed a statistically significant negative association ($\beta = -0.377$) between the perception of the ‘divide’ and workplace conditions. In

Table 5.3 – Hierarchical Multiple Regression for the Perception of the ‘Divide’ in the Institutions

Variables	Perception of the "divide"							
	Model I: CM		Model II: TE		Model III: JS		Model IV: Full	
	β	<i>Std. E</i>	β	<i>Std. E</i>	β	<i>Std. E</i>	β	<i>Std. E</i>
CMI1 - Workplace conditions	-0.377*	0.213					-0.209	0.238
CMI2 - Individual predisposition	-0.124	0.165					-0.144	0.170
CMI3 - Communication skills	0.163	0.183					-0.276	0.266
TEI1 - Team spirit			-0.478*	0.267			-0.496*	0.288
TEI2 - Continuous feedback			-0.036	0.205			-0.029	0.217
TEI3 - Team values			-0.188	0.260			-0.188	0.273
JSI1 - Motivation					0.037	0.243	0.037	0.243
JSI2 - Challenges					0.058	0.201	0.058	0.201
JSI3 - Rewards					-0.115	0.218	-0.115	0.218
Role. Reference category: Academic								
Blended	-0.121	0.632	-0.046	0.604	-0.005	0.651	-0.005	0.651
Administrative	0.139	0.494	0.138	0.465	0.147	0.491	0.147	0.491
Universities' region. Reference Category: Southern Europe								
Northern Europe	-0.142	0.580	-0.153	0.545	-0.087	0.637	-0.087	0.637
Eastern Europe	-0.229	0.648	-0.229	0.627	-0.202	0.664	-0.202	0.664
Western Europe	-0.246	0.452	-0.209	0.434	-0.159	0.480	-0.159	0.480
Non-EU	0.059	1.004	0.081	0.938	0.105	0.984	0.105	0.984
Gender. Reference category: Male								
Female	-0.014	0.424	-0.072	0.424	-0.084	0.448	-0.084	0.448
No gender disclosed	0.418*	1.538	0.408*	1.436	0.395*	1.732	0.395*	1.732
Age. Continuous variable	-0.065	0.020	-0.108	0.019	-0.121	0.021	-0.121	0.021
R²	0.333		0.460		0.471		0.471	

Note. $N = 60$. * = $p < .05$, ** = $p < .01$, *** = $p < .001$

other words, as workplace conditions improve, the perception of a 'divide' tends to decrease. This Model explained about one-third (33.3%) of the variance in the perception of the 'divide'. Introducing Team Effectiveness in Model II, an even stronger negative statistically significant relationship ($\beta = -0.478$) was obtained between team spirit and the perception of the 'divide'. This suggests that stronger team spirit is associated with a lower perception of staff 'divide'. The explanatory power of the Model increased significantly, now accounting for 46% of the variance.

Interestingly, there were no statistically significant associations in Model III (Job Satisfaction), with the perception of a 'divide'. However, this Model explained a slightly higher percentage of variance (47.1%) compared to Model II. On the contrary, the same control variables in the Full Model again showed a negative statistically significant association ($\beta = -0.496$) between the perception of the 'divide' and team spirit, reinforcing the findings from Model II. It showed a strong negative relationship between team spirit and the perception of a 'divide', similar to what was observed in Model II. This final model explained 47.1% of the variance in the perception of the 'divide'. Overall, these results suggest that workplace conditions and especially team spirit play crucial roles in reducing the perception of organisational divides. Improving these aspects could potentially lead to a more unified organisational culture. The lack of significant findings related to job satisfaction is noteworthy and might warrant further investigation.

The same procedure was run for the EMJMD consortiums (see Table 5.4). As can be observed, when introducing the control variables in Model I (Collaborative Mindset), it did not show any statistically significant relationships with the perception of the 'divide'. This model explained 32.8% of the variance in the perception of the 'divide'. In Model II (Team Effectiveness), a strong statistically significant negative association between the perception of the 'divide' and team spirit can be observed ($\beta = -0.644$). This means that as team spirit increases, the perception of a 'divide' tends to decrease substantially. This model explained 41.3% of the variance, indicating

Table 5.4 – Hierarchical Multiple Regression for the Perception of the ‘Divide’ in the EMJMDs Consortiums

Variables	Perception of the "divide"							
	Model I: CM		Model II: TE		Model III: JS		Model IV: Full	
	β	<i>Std. E</i>	β	<i>Std. E</i>	β	<i>Std. E</i>	β	<i>Std. E</i>
CMEM1 - Workplace conditions	0.135	0.250					0.473	0.347
CMEM2 - Individual predisposition	0.157	0.216					0.057	0.235
CMEM3 - Communication skills	-0.177	0.259					-0.157	0.265
TEEM1 - Team spirit			-0.644*	0.355			-0.559	0.372
TEEM2 - Continuous feedback			0.070	0.276			0.119	0.307
JSEM1 - Motivation					0.116	0.334	0.116	0.334
JSEM2 - Challenges					0.291	0.264	0.291	0.264
JSEM3 - Rewards					0.072	0.202	0.072	0.202
Role. Reference category: Academic								
Blended	-0.225	0.827	-0.250	0.800	-0.201	0.820	-0.201	0.820
Administrative	-0.250	0.530	-0.091	0.544	-0.102	0.557	-0.102	0.557
Universities' region. Reference Category: Southern Europe								
Northern Europe	-0.217	0.656	-0.179	0.645	-0.159	0.676	-0.159	0.676
Eastern Europe	-0.245	0.615	-0.120	0.626	-0.138	0.646	-0.138	0.646
Western Europe	-0.409*	0.523	-0.305	0.521	-0.322	0.545	-0.322	0.545
Non-EU	0.142	1.247	0.162	1.204	0.131	1.213	0.131	1.213
Gender. Reference category: Male								
Female	0.140	0.457	0.070	0.449	0.153	0.480	0.153	0.480
No gender disclosed	0.474*	1.478	0.465*	1.436	0.329	1.624	0.329	1.624
Age. Continuous variable	-0.287	0.021	-0.219	0.021	-0.134	0.021	-0.135	0.021
R2	0.328		0.413		0.472		0.472	

Note. $N = 49$. * = $p < .05$, ** = $p < .01$, *** = $p < .001$

that adding Team Effectiveness factors improved the Model's explanatory power. Instead, there were no statistically significant relationships in Model III (Job Satisfaction) and the Full Model, and the total variance explained was 47.2% in both models.

Interestingly, Model III (Job Satisfaction) and the Full Model, which included Job Satisfaction and all variables respectively, did not show any statistically significant relationships. However, both these models explained 47.2% of the total variance in the perception of the 'divide'. This suggests that while Job Satisfaction and the combination of all factors did not produce significant individual predictors, they still contributed to explaining more of the overall variation in the perception of the 'divide'.

The key takeaway from these results is that team spirit appears to be the most influential factor in reducing the perception of a 'divide' within the collaboration among professional staff and academics ensuring a nurturing environment. However, as for the EMJMDs' results, the lack of significant relationships in the later models may require further investigation to fully understand their combined effects on mixed groups dynamics.

5.6 Discussion

The findings reveal that some academics, professional staff, and blended professionals still perceive the 'divide', which was slightly higher in the institutions than in the EMJMD consortiums. Specifically, results suggest that when a supportive workplace with standard procedures, defined responsibilities, recognition of roles, and constructive evaluations exists in the institutions, professionals are less likely to perceive a 'divide'. The differences between the institutional and the EMJMD findings could mainly be related to the persistent presence of hierarchical governance models at the institutional level which affects organisational efficiency (Maassen, & Stensaker, [2019](#)) as described in the literature review. In addition, as declared by Manca et al. ([2018](#)), "[t]oday, collaboration does not occur only within clearly defined

organisational boundaries” (p. 526); it is needed to create synergies between professionals, overcome difficulties, coordinate the roles, and generate a cohesive and complementary set of provisions (MacNaughton et al., [2013](#)).

Manca et al. ([2018](#)) also specified that besides physical facilities, collaborative workspaces involve other areas such as (i) information and communication technologies; (ii) human resources and work practices that contribute to outlining the performances, communication, and flexibility to collaborate across workgroups; and (iii) organisational culture and structure impacting team performance (pp. 527-528).

Moreover, collaborative workspaces identify “a combination of non-conventional layouts, facilities, technologies and work practices that aim to sustain knowledge work performance and innovation by providing an attractive, smart and value-reflecting workplace that aids collaboration, operational flexibility and cultural change” (Manca et al., [2018](#), p. 528). Besides, since “[t]he workplace environment that is set in place impacts employee morale, productivity and engagement – both positively and negatively” (Chandrasekar, [2011](#), p. 2), the aim should be to have and improve a positive workplace “for the individuals, the teams, the projects and ultimately for the organization itself” (Davis & Cable, [2014](#), p. 3). Because creating a fearless workplace is a crucial aspect in promoting psychological safety within organisations and this continuously evolving process ensures that individuals are motivated with their jobs (Edmondson, [2019](#)).

My findings suggest that if there was no real team spirit, the ‘divide’ was more pronounced. According to the team’s models (Tuckman, [1965](#); Lombardo & Eichinger, [1995](#); LaFasto, [2001](#); Lencioni [2002](#)), teams allow organisations to achieve their goals due to the collaborative relationship between individuals. Hazi ([2019](#)) complemented these models by stating that high levels of team spirit create in team members a sense of belonging and enables the achievement of “goals more effectively, sustain organizational cohesion, and allows

employees to satisfy their social needs” (p. 11). It encourages social bonding and enables members to go beyond their own tasks because they are engaged in common goals (Hazi, [2019](#)).

Based on Fapohunda’s suggestion ([2013](#)), in the absence of teams, an institution moves forward thanks to individual efforts. However, with team building, “workgroups evolve into cohesive units and share expectations for accomplishing group tasks added to trust and support for one another and respect for individual differences” (Fapohunda, [2013](#), p. 2). There is no best way to create, cultivate and boost highly effective teams. Accordingly, the major components of efficient teams should be: (i) clarity of expectations and objectives; (ii) perspective; (iii) dedication; (iv) capability; (v) contract; (vi) resources; (vii) power; (viii) cooperation; (ix) communication; (x) creative improvement; (xi) responsibility and accountability; (xii) harmonisation; and (xiii) cultural change (Fapohunda, [2013](#), pp. 5-9).

Equally important were the results within the EMJMD consortiums. As in the institutions, if team spirit was not optimal, for instance, there was a lack of appraisal of colleagues’ contributions, unclear roles and responsibilities, issues when one openly admitted weaknesses and mistakes, and the sense of the ‘divide’ was more pronounced among respondents. Consequently, it is possible to affirm that to avoid a division among staff members in mixed groups, it is fundamental that individuals connect their selves in close relationship with colleagues with sympathy, common understanding, and esteem (Ramarajan & Reid, [2020](#)).

Furthermore, in 2017, Shawn Burke et al. ([2017](#)) highlighted the effort needed to create and maintain the ideal conditions for a team with members with different cultural backgrounds, as is the case of an EMJMD. “While cultural diversity can provide synergies, research has shown that it can also lead to process loss as members attempt to navigate differences in attitudes, beliefs, and values that often remain hidden under the surface and impact team interaction” (Shawn Burke et al. [2017](#), p. 185). Nevertheless, these authors also mentioned that when

culturally diverse teams learn how to overcome the differences, research has shown that in the long term they do better than homogeneous teams (Shawn Burke et al., [2017](#)).

Last but not least, it is worth noting that although the analysis did not reveal statistically significant results on Job Satisfaction, the majority of respondents involved in the EMJMDs studied were satisfied with their job, regardless of their role and affiliation. My results complement the scientific literature on this matter where it is demonstrated that a strong link between job satisfaction and effective dedication entails a supportive and rewarding work environment by enhancing organisational commitment, which is essential for achieving high-level performance and overall efficiency (Trivellas & Santouridis, [2016](#)), leaving no room for staff divisions.

5.7 Concluding Remarks

It is possible to affirm that for professional staff, academics, and blended professionals participating in this study, Team Effectiveness plays a crucial role in developing and achieving the pre-established goals of an international project such as an EMJMD. Nonetheless, as illustrated in the literature review, high performing teams take time to evolve and mature, and they usually pass through the different stages of development as described in Tuckman's model to reach optimal performance: (i) forming; (ii) storming; (iii) norming and (iv) performing (Tuckman, [1965](#)).

The presented results suggest that a lack of a consolidated team spirit might have contributed to the awareness of the historical 'divide' in both settings (higher education institutions and EMJMD consortiums). This result could indicate that working in an EMJMD improves professional relationships and could be implemented as a good practice model to reduce the division between staff categories. Consequently, helping personnel working in higher

education institutions create a positive workplace in which all members promote team spirit will undoubtedly increase the potential of having a better collaboration.

Although these are preliminary findings which need to be further investigated, they provide valuable indications of Team Effectiveness in the context of an EMJMD *Third Space* settings. The implementation of the following phase of this study, the qualitative methodology with the use of semi-structured interviews which are described in the following chapter, helped me obtain more accurate information of how the experience of working in an EMJMD could impact a broad spectrum of settings at the institutional level. Even more, the statistical interpretation of the data collected via the questionnaires will be “linked to the qualitative research question” (Antonius, [2003](#), p. 30), for a qualitative interpretation of the numerical results (Antonius, [2003](#)) allowing me to provide more robust conclusions.

CHAPTER SIX: RICH NARRATIVES EMERGE FROM STAFF VOICES

6.1 Introduction

To explore the results of the quantitative phase in more depth, I conducted 28 semi-structured interviews with a sub-sample of professional staff ($n = 13$), academics ($n = 7$), and blended professionals ($n = 8$) from 14 different EMJMDs. I formulated the questions based on the analysis of the quantitative phase where it was possible to elicit information regarding the essence of the collaboration among staff categories within each institution and among partners. This information nourished the interviews which, in turn, allowed me to explore, in greater depth, the nature of the relationships between staff within the *Third Space* established by the EMJMDs. Similarly to the quantitative phase, the area of expertise of the individuals involved in the interviews was diverse, encompassing disciplines ranging from chemistry to policy, engineering, art and many others.

Several topics emerged from the collected data which were categorised into three main themes with various subthemes. The first theme delves deeply into the peculiarities of an EMJMD, and the way participants perceive them. The second outlines the characteristics of the higher education institutions offering these Master's degrees, and in some instances, highlights differences between institutions and EMJMDs. The final theme delineates the personal and interpersonal impacts that these degrees have on the individuals involved. All the themes together underline the importance of creating a supportive atmosphere that boosts tolerance, understanding, facilitates communication and empowers people by acknowledging their work.

6.2 Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Participants were selected for interviews based on their availability following the quantitative phase. Out of the initial pool of 133 individuals, 81 mentioned their willingness to be interviewed. Of the 81 individuals available, 28 (34.57%) were recruited based on their job roles

and gender, encompassing academics, professional staff, and blended professionals. This selection aimed to achieve a balanced representation across these three groups and the distribution by gender and role can be found in Table 6.1.

Table 6.1 – Distribution by Gender and Role During the Qualitative Phase

<i>Role</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>Total</i>
Professional staff	9	4	13
Academics	3	4	7
Blended professionals	4	4	8
TOTAL	16	12	28

6.3 Data Collection: Interview Protocol and Implementation Procedure

As previously mentioned, the interview protocol was grounded in the results of the previous statistical phase of the study and comprised questions related to Collaborative Mindset, Team Effectiveness and Job Satisfaction, the three dimensions composing this research's Conceptual Framework (Figure 3.4). The questions were planned and structured to be interlinked, ensuring the acquisition of comprehensive information aimed to form a complete picture of the research topic (Rubin & Rubin, [2012](#)).

The qualitative data was collected between 20 May and 25 July 2022 with no prior testing because it was a follow-up to the quantitative phase. My interview protocol was reviewed and validated by two experts in the field of internationalisation in higher education. During their review, they considered the responses I had already received, the research questions, and the topics that needed to be addressed. Those individuals who completed the questionnaire during the quantitative phase and confirmed their willingness to participate in the interviews in the qualitative phase received the consent form ([Appendix G](#) – Consent Form). All interviews were conducted online (using Zoom) and lasted approximately 40-60 minutes. Before starting the interview, I ensured the receipt of the signed consent form and briefed the participants again about the research topic and the interview duration. Moreover, I reaffirmed the guarantee of

anonymity, mentioned the possibility of concluding the interview in advance if the participants decided to do so, and asked permission to record the interview. In addition, participants were informed that while there were structured questions, they would have time to share additional comments or insights at the end of the interview.

The interviews were recorded (audiovisually) and transcribed verbatim employing a voice-to-text transcription software (specifically, Otter.ai) (See [Appendix H](#) – Transcript Example). Additionally, each transcription subsequently underwent a meticulous manual review. “Member checking, also known as participant or respondent validation” (Birt et al., [2016](#), p. 1802), was completed before the analysis phase, i.e., participants received the transcript of their respective interviews and had the opportunity to review, approve, and, if required, make any necessary corrections to the content. Member checking was a crucial step in my research to enhance my findings’ credibility, validity, precision, and reliability. By providing participants with their transcripts, I ensured their perspectives were appreciated and accurately represented. Furthermore, allowing them to verify whether their viewpoints and experiences were correctly described strengthened the rigour of my results. Additionally, as previously explained, my role in the EMJMDs setting was not neutral; hence, this technique helped prevent my personal biases and assumptions from producing inaccuracies, misrepresentations, or ambiguities.

6.4 Qualitative Analysis Method: Thematic Analysis

Since qualitative data analysis involves a sequential process, it necessitates different steps to get from the specific to the general, and the process encompasses various levels of analysis (Creswell & Creswell, [2018](#)). Within this process, Thematic Analysis was the method selected to analyse the qualitative data gathered for my study because it “is a method for identifying, analysing and reporting patterns (themes) within data” (Braun & Clarke, [2006](#), p. 79). Even if scholars as Guest et al. ([2012](#)) have stated that in Thematic Analysis it can happen that data contradicts each other

or there is diversity between the qualitative and quantitative data sets (Guest et al., [2012](#)), they also described it as an effective method for summarising the particulars or significance of a textual data collection because it “situates the coding process in the realm of evidences rather than ideas” (Guest et al., [2012](#), p. 75).

While doing the Thematic Analysis, as a first step, I embedded the Coding Levels described by Hahn in [2011](#) (Table 6.2) within the Thematic Analysis phases recommended by Braun and Clarke ([2006](#)), which are described in Table 6.3.

Table 6.2 – Code Levels

Level	Type of coding
Level 1	Initial/Open Coding
Level 2	Focused Coding/Category development
Level 3	Axial/Thematic Coding
Level 4	Theoretical concepts

Source: Hahn ([2011](#), p. 6)

Table 6.3 – Thematic Analysis

Step	Phase
Step 1	Familiarising with the data
Step 2	Generating initial codes
Step 3	Searching for themes
Step 4	Reviewing themes
Step 5	Defining and naming themes
Step 6	Producing the report

Source: Braun and Clarke ([2006](#), p. 87)

The different phases of this process are described in Figure 6.1. The interviews were copied and pasted into a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and divided into three categories: professional staff, academics, and blended professionals. Afterwards, I followed the analytical steps suggested by Braun and Clarke ([2006](#)) as described below. Initially, I coded all the transcriptions manually and in a second phase with the support of software, Atlas.ti.

Phase 1 – Familiarising with the data. During this step, all interview transcriptions were accurately reviewed to verify the overall data integrity. This preliminary exploration offered a broad understanding of the information and allowed me to grasp its comprehensive significance

Figure 6.1 – Thematic Analysis Process for this Research Study

Source: Created by the author with information retrieved from Hahn (2011, p. 6) and Braun and Clarke (2006, p. 87)

(Creswell & Creswell, [2018](#)). This was done by reading and re-reading the transcripts and writing initial ideas (Braun & Clarke, [2006](#)).

Phase 2 – Generating initial codes: Initial/Open Coding. Despite the many definitions in terms of codes and coding ([Appendix I](#) – Codes and Coding definitions), there is a common understanding of the importance of this process because it allows the researcher to generate notions and concepts from raw data by discovering and organising all the ideas hidden within the data (Given, [2008](#)). Coding can be explained as the interpretation of data, which includes the naming of concepts, as well as the explanation and discussion in more detail, and the result of this process is a list of terms and an explanatory text (Böhm, [2004](#)). Similarly, it is also recognised that coding is an active process; thus, the coding frame (which contains the most crucial ideas) evolves and undergoes refinement in the subsequent stages of the analysis (Given, [2008](#)). The initial coding was done during the early labelling stage and consisted of highlighting relevant chunks of data and collating them into a word or a short sentence (i.e., a code) in the margins of the text (Rossman & Rallis, [2017](#)).

In this phase, I employed an inductive approach to extract the most meaningful features from the entire data set, there was not a pre-existing coding frame because it was a data-driven Thematic Analysis (Braun & Clarke, [2006](#)). This means that the emergence and discovery of codes, categories, and themes came directly from the data (Patton, [2002](#); Charmaz, [2006](#); Creswell & Creswell, [2018](#)) because, as stated by Hatch ([2002](#)), an inductive analysis goes from the details to the general. It “is a search for patterns of meaning in data so that general statements about phenomena under investigation can be made” (Hatch, [2002](#), p. 161). Some codes were provisional (Charmaz, [2006](#)), and the types of codes used in this phase were mainly descriptive, often nouns that provided an inventory of topics which afterwards were categorised (Saldaña, [2013](#)).

Phase 3 – Focused Coding/ Category development. While copying the initial coding within Atlas.ti, I re-examined the codes and included new ones or deleted others. Initial/open codes were confirmed and transcribed into the software, new codes emerged and were added, and others were excluded or modified. During the process, those excerpts with mumbled responses or misunderstandings about the questions were also coded because even if they seemed poor at the beginning, they made sense later (Guest et al., [2012](#)). In so doing, I also paid attention to avoid never-ending recoding because, as stated by Braun and Clarke ([2006](#)), “coding data and generating themes could go on *ad infinitum*” (p. 92). During the first coding phase, the number of codes created was 301, and the number of transcript excerpts assigned to those codes was 584. It was also possible to start grouping similar ones into a smaller number of categories with comparable patterns or characteristics (Given, [2008](#); Saldaña, [2013](#)). This means the codes were revised “to tell a story or communicate conclusions drawn from the data” (Given, [2008](#), p. 85).

Phase 4 – Searching for themes: Axial/Thematic Coding. Since coding is only the initial step toward make sense to the data, an even more rigorous analysis and interpretation was performed during successive phases and similar code categories were combined to develop themes (Creswell, [2002](#)), gathering all relevant data to each potential theme (Braun & Clarke, [2006](#)), and examining in depth one category at a time. This is called axial coding (Given, [2008](#)). As stated by Ryan and Bernard ([2003](#)), themes are intangible concepts that link expressions found in writings, pictures and others, and they defined them as “the conceptual linking of expressions, it is clear that there are many ways in which expressions can be linked to abstract constructs” (Ryan & Bernard, [2003](#), p. 88). Identifying themes is a highly interpretative effort (Guest et al, [2012](#)). Consequently, since the open coding was reviewed to identify refined themes in the data (Hahn, [2011](#)), following Guest et al. ([2012](#)) and Braun and Clarke’s ([2006](#)) suggestions, I went over the Research Questions to define the

most relevant themes that could help me to address these queries, because the 'keyness' of a theme relies on this ability (Braun & Clarke, [2006](#)). From the different techniques proposed to identify themes, the following were used: (i) repetition, if a topic appeared recurrently (Ryan & Bernard, [2003](#); Guest et al., [2012](#)); (ii) similarities and differences found while comparing text (Guest et al., [2012](#)); and (iii) missing data for those topics that did not provide specific evidence and their absence was therefore relevant (Guest et al., [2012](#)).

Phase 5 – Reviewing, defining and naming themes: Since the coding process is used to make sense of the data, connecting and interrelating themes is fundamental (Creswell, [2002](#)). This selective coding (or integration of themes) was done in this phase. Associations and relations among the selected themes were reviewed (Given, [2008](#)) by further analysis to refine each theme and generate clear definitions and names for each (Braun & Clarke, [2006](#)). While reviewing the themes' characteristics, how the themes and subthemes were related (Saldaña, [2013](#)) was also explored. In doing so, final checking of the connections between the themes and the coded excerpts (first level), as well as the complete data set (second level), was done, allowing me to create a Thematic Map of the analysis (Braun & Clarke, [2006](#)), as shown in Figure 6.2.

Phase 6 – Producing the report: Since this final phase represents the last opportunity for analysis, the most relevant quotes related to the Research Questions and literature were selected and further analysed to draw inferences and produce the report (Braun & Clarke, [2006](#)) or as in my case, write the findings. From the very beginning, excerpts which could adequately illustrate the final themes and provide the answers to the research questions were highlighted. This was done because, as Guest et al. ([2012](#)) stated, verbatim quotes play a crucial role in qualitative research, as they convey the participants' perspectives and link specific facts to the researcher's

Figure 6.2 – Thematic Map

Source: Author's own work

interpretation. These authors also emphasised this idea by saying, “They [quotes] are the foundation upon which good qualitative data analysis is based” and “[t]he beautiful thing about quotes is that their veracity is difficult to criticize” (Guest et al., [2012](#), p. 95). During this process, the following statement was considered to avoid missing relevant information: “What is difficult when beginning to move from analysis, which can be quite ordered and structured, towards interpretation, which is messy, is the necessity of managing multiple meanings and (sometimes) competing ideas and views that emerge in data” (Savin-Baden & Major, [2023](#), p. 452).

6.5 Emerging Themes

As shown in Figure 6.2, three key themes were defined as they encompassed the essential information required to describe the primary characteristics of the EMJMDs. Furthermore, these

themes enabled me to respond in-depth to the study's Research Questions. In the subsequent sections, these selected themes and their corresponding subthemes are introduced and accompanied by the most pertinent quotations that corroborate the findings.

6.5.1 Theme 1 – Distinctive Elements of Erasmus Mundus Joint Master Degrees

EMJMDs represent a distinctive endeavour within the scene of joint programmes. Consortiums can be composed of a few or several institutions, presenting, in this way, a vast landscape of different approaches. The multifaceted nature of EMJMDs often lead to conflicts as some universities need help to adapt their roles and procedures to this new reality. Numerous aspects contribute to the distinctiveness of these degrees; the most pertinent ones are described within this theme. Additionally, subthemes are also presented and described, and although each one is explained separately, they are all interconnected, as shown in Figure 6.3.

Figure 6.3 – Theme 1: Distinctive Elements of EMJMDs

Source: Author's own work

Subtheme 1: Unravelling the Singular Nature of EMJMDs.

Participants mentioned several aspects related to the EMJMDs' singularity. Their unique nature facilitated a close interaction among staff members aiming to achieve their primary goal: a successful programme. The most distinctive EMJMD elements are explained in this subtheme.

Multicultural academic experience. Any EMJMD can be considered a truly enriching multicultural space: A distinctive trait of the EMJMD is that it encompasses a highly diverse student body composed of individuals from all over the world. Luxury (academic) highlighted the profound impact of the EMJMDs by stating:

So, this Erasmus Mundus programme is very satisfactory. But it's also something that is very rewarding that you can collaborate across institutions. I think that's one of the reasons, but I think the major reason is probably in the international classroom. So, the opportunity to teach students in my case, I teach students from around 35 to 40, different nationalities. So, it's a very dynamic. Diverse, diverse, and enriching your classroom to enter.

Attracting the best students worldwide creates a classroom that is a melting pot for both students and staff. Scientific literature has demonstrated that studying abroad provides a statistically significant, although limited, change towards a more intercultural mindset (Terzuolo, [2018](#)) if a reflecting process takes place (Tarchi et al., [2018](#)). Although the reflective exercises do not constantly occur in an EMJMD, it is impossible to deny at least the richness of this type of environment.

Collaborative synergies among higher education institutions. While developing and managing an EMJMD, it is crucial to create valid collaborative interactions among institutions to identify partner strengths and weaknesses as well as shared research interests. This is obtained via

continuous communication, open discussions, and commitment between professional staff and academics, which can create a sense of community from the very beginning of the project. For a consortium, it is key to addressing collective issues and making decisions as a cohesive group while fostering unity. In addition, openness, flexibility, adaptability, and willingness are needed to accommodate local contexts while prioritising the success of the programme and the students. Kai (professional staff) highlighted the collaborative effort required for success, saying: “[W]e discuss the whole process as, as the institutions involved seems like one university in the end [...] But we do that together with many, many meetings, many, many discussions and changes along the way of course.” Scholarly literature confirms Kai’s assertion because as underlined by Veles et al. (2018), institutional partnerships take time and determination to be developed and maintained as sustainable collaborations (Veles et al., 2018).

EMJMDs can be considered small-scale entities. Even those consortiums with several partners can be considered relatively small settings. The team in each institution is frequently composed of the Local Director/Coordinator, one or two professional staff members and professors teaching the specific courses, as declared by Ainsley (professional staff): “So, you have to think that we have really small teams; I mean, we've got our director and me. And then the professors could be like six people, yes, working Erasmus Mundus programme, okay? So, they are not really big”. This unique, small-scale environment fosters a more personalised relationship with a close working dynamic among team members. It creates a sense of belonging, camaraderie and exclusivity, fostering a feeling of importance and satisfaction in being part of this community.

Scientific literature also described the advantages of small higher education institutions. In accordance with Schubert and Yang (2016), smaller institutions are more flexible and tend to adjust to changes better, which facilitates speedier reform implementation and decision-making.

In addition, there is less administrative burden, and a sense of community prevails, fostering the development of closer ties between the individuals (Schubert & Yang, [2016](#)).

Working in an EMJMD is an additional role. Usually, individuals working in EMJMDs hold multifaceted positions encompassing two or more primary responsibilities. This means that the EMJMD's role is a "part-time" job. Consequently, dual or multiple commitments can lead to a sense of being overwhelmed, given the breadth of responsibilities and the complexity of their roles. Ash (professional staff) described the workload by stating:

Sometimes I'm a bit overloaded because I'm not only working for the consortium. I am also an administrative assistant for all the departments, and I only have a part-time job, and the other half-time is for a laboratory [...] Because it's only one part of my job, I have to work with all the students of our department, the Erasmus Mundus, but also all students, from regular masters, the academics and the researchers and so on.

Academics found themselves in the same situation as mentioned by Flannery (academic):

I think these are such different creatures. All of us had similar positions at university really quite similar. And so, most of us were like, we're all academics in different disciplines, and dealing with this programme on top of our teaching or research or other things.

While many participants found their job in the EMJMDs to be rewarding, it was challenging for both professional staff and academics to manage the workload related to part-time employment or additional tasks. Most of the academic literature on workload in higher education focuses on the excessive workload, the burden of bureaucratic practices, and their impact on personal well-being and work-life conflicts from the academic point of view (Pace et al., [2021](#)). There is a need for more studies on this topic to understand its effect on the lives of professional staff.

Tailored and complex administrative procedures: The unique features of the EMJMDs, such as the distribution of scholarships following the European Commission guidelines, the visa procedures for more than one country, two mandatory mobility periods and many others, distinguish these programmes from conventional exchange experiences in regular Bachelor's or Master's degrees. This implies particular application periods, divergence in enrolment rules, different tuition fees and graduation periods, and so on, and requires close collaboration within and across institutions. Echo (professional staff) expressed the challenge of convincing colleagues within faculties or universities of these discrepancies, mentioning:

And because our kind of programmes are always the odd one out, with different rules for enrolment, for paying for tuition fees, for graduation, for everything, it takes a lot of time to convince the colleagues in the faculty or in the university that we are different, but we want to cooperate.

For this reason, as described in the literature review, Obst et al. (2011) underlined that many EMJMDs employ additional staff to manage these programmes correctly.

Feelings of Isolation. Being part of an EMJMD made some respondents feel isolated compared to the rest of the institution. This isolation creates a distinct identity and a feeling of exclusion within the larger university context, which sometimes entails a lack of institutional support. Kelcey (blended professional) reflected on this sense of isolation, declaring:

Within my institution, I mean, when we started this programme, we felt a bit lonely. It's the first master Erasmus Mundus coordinated by [*institution's name*]. So, nobody had the expertise, or nobody knew what to do. So, the support was, like, scarce, we could say, no? We've had to do everything by ourselves. And still, now, I think we feel like an island. Because they feel as we have a project manager that we can hire from the programme.

The university staff is less involved with the evaluation of the documents and applications system. It's like, we have to do everything ourselves.

As a result, EMJMDs are often seen as independent structures, with the programme's team undertaking extensive responsibilities, implementing better procedures, being persistent in self-reliance, and having an autonomous management nature while simultaneously considering the institutional requirements. These feelings of isolation perceived by respondents can be comparable with the feelings described by Weissmann (2013) about students completing a joint honours degree when they felt excluded from the institutional structures and regulations because they were attending different programmes that did not fit into regular schemes.

Protected and secure environment. Within these entities, the vast majority of studied EMJMD respondents reported a culture of open communication, the freedom to express ideas, and respectful treatment, which reflects a Collaborative Mindset. This fosters an atmosphere where everyone feels comfortable voicing their thoughts, even when expressing frustration or criticism, as described by Sutton (blended professional): “And this is our goal to create, like, a nice working environment for everybody to feel like, okay, and to feel good to be part of the project.” Nevertheless, for a few participants, that was not the case in their consortiums, as voiced by Echo (professional staff):

Well, I already mentioned that the gap between directors and coordinators, at least in some instances. So that it's a bit more frustrating that you are not always valued.

Although we take on the brunt of the work, that's not always seen. And communication is not always as good.

My findings related to the importance of a safe environment at work are confirmed by scientific literature. Bamford and Moschini (2024) mentioned the importance of the confidence that appears

in an individual through the development of the sense of being part of the team. This reinforces Edmondson's (2019) declaration about the value of achieving psychological safety in a team because it contrasts negative experiences in which there are communication issues and mistrust.

Mundus Spirit or the Erasmus Mundus Family. The sense of belonging is a hallmark of the EMJMDs studied, setting them apart from traditional university programmes. A common goal unites these communities in which staff constantly support each other. The small scale of EMJMDs and their relative interdependence and open communication atmosphere also led participants to view themselves as part of a family united by a shared commitment to a successful degree. Terms like "Mundus Spirit" and "Mundus Family" describe these strong bonds. Reflecting on this unique camaraderie, Reef (academic) expressed:

Yeah, yeah. We call it the Mundus Spirit with the students and with the staff, you know, and there is a sense of belonging of, we are a separate thing within the university. And within the department, and yeah, we actually call it that. So, I think there is a very special sense of belonging that is separate from the rest.

Existing studies confirm these findings by underlining the importance of belongingness.

According to Chan (2016), within organisations belongingness plays a crucial role in fostering the psychological well-being of employees, contributing to their satisfaction and engagement. In higher education institutions, appreciative leadership positively impacts individual's belongingness (Ali & Ahmad, 2019; Raza et al., 2020), but more specifically, the relationship dimension with the supervisor as described by Azmy (2019). For this reason, respondents in this study felt appreciated, supported, involved, and valued by the academics leading the degrees. This in turn, creates a strong sense of belonging as described by Cockshaw and Shochet (2010). While many interviewees expressed a strong sense of belonging to the

consortium, at the same time some of them felt isolated at the institutional level due to lack of recognition and support.

Significant impact on the students' lives. The transformative impact on Mundus students, many of whom come from diverse backgrounds and difficult situations, is particularly significant due to a life-changing experience. An EMJMD has a direct influence on participants' lives, their academic journey, their growth, and subsequent achievements. For many respondents, it was gratifying to help students achieve their dreams and contribute to their personal and professional growth. Rigbe (blended professional) highlighted this aspect expressing: "And I mean, the difference that you make in the life of a Mundus student is typically bigger. I mean, you know, we have students who had never seen an airplane in their life who were writing the motivation letter on a typewriter." Accordingly, the most recent report from the European Commission confirmed that due to the enhanced learning and teaching experience, the international cooperation activities, and the improved administrative procedures, EMJMDs provide an outstanding academic experience for all students and higher education institutions involved (European Commission et al., [2024](#)).

A Profoundly Positive Experience. It is noteworthy that even if respondents described challenges, participation in these programmes was marked by individuals' distinct sense of satisfaction. This unique experience is characterised by encountering different learning traditions in a dynamic, culturally diverse environment. It offers an enriching exposure to an international classroom and the opportunity to collaborate across institutions. Reflecting on the satisfaction derived from EMJMDs, Taran (academic) expressed: "In principle, Erasmus Mundus, I can't imagine a professional or professor or academic who wouldn't experience this special kind of satisfaction precisely because of the encounter with the whole world."

In these particular settings, professional staff can use their versatile skill sets, allowing them to navigate various tasks simultaneously and manage the programme's multifaceted nature, encompassing financial matters, academic challenges, and administrative responsibilities. For this reason, EMJMDs can also be considered innovators for the European Higher Education Area in terms of an original joint curriculum design, facing accreditation processes, creating administrative procedures, and recruitment strategies while putting together different services across partner institutions (European Commission et al., [2024](#)).

The benefits of an EMJMD go beyond the “opportunities for the academic institutions to enhance their visibility on the international education market” (Guillerme, [2014](#), p. 103). The value of EMJMDs was evident for respondents due to – amongst others – the collaboration developed between staff and the overall unique, enriching, and diverse experience. Likewise, it fosters a culture of mutual support, dedication and trust among staff. Allen et al. ([2021](#)) described belonging as a dynamic emotion shaped by four interconnected elements – skills and abilities, opportunities, motivation, and perceptions – which reinforce each other and influence the environments in which individuals are situated. These elements all came forward in the interviews. Respondents had adaptable skill sets, were motivated to achieve a common goal and saw an opportunity to enhance personal and professional aspects of their lives through these degrees.

Subtheme 2: EMJMDs Foster Special Interprofessional Collaborations.

Working in an EMJMD improved the collaboration between academics and professional staff participating in this study, fostering clear Team Effectiveness mechanisms. The following quote by Raine (professional staff) clearly describes the type of collaboration within the EMJMDs: “So,

I think the, the Mundus programme is particularly unique, and the collaborative work between admin and academic is core to the consortium.”

Unlike the typical professional staff-academic interactions where there could be a division between these two groups, within most of the studied EMJMDs staff seem to work together seamlessly. “[H]ere, we really do depend on each other”, said Quest (blended professional), when discussing collaboration, while Kelcey (blended professional) stated: “We trust a lot of our administrators.” The interdependence between administrative and academic tasks goes beyond the traditional degrees, as declared by Ash (professional staff): “We all know that we can count on ourselves on the same level.” Consequently, each staff member actively contributes to the degree’s success, excellence and sustainability because every individual’s contribution is valued. Hence, it creates a space where expertise is recognised regardless of the staff member’s position, as confirmed by Blythe (professional staff): “I feel that we’re, we’re all equals there is no distinction between oh, you’re just an academic, or you’re the professor, you decide.”

This mutual respect, trust and acknowledgement of each other’s roles and responsibilities described by participants foster a sense of unity and shared purposes and confirm their Collaborative Mindset. Several studies have consistently highlighted the critical role that effective collaboration plays. Moreover, the findings of this study complement what was stated by Pham and Tanner ([2015](#)) in terms of the value of collaboration between academics and library staff when it comes to improving teaching and learning and promoting creative curricula innovation. These elements are always required at the institutional level, but are even more fundamental to ensure the excellence expected in any EMJMD.

Shared research interests and flexible administrative procedures ensure the programme’s quality and growth. This is obtained via continuous communication, open discussions, and

commitment between professional staff and academics, which help to maintain and reinforce Team Effectiveness. Kai (professional staff) described the type of synergies in the following way: “We have to be very open to change everything every year, if it needs towards the success of the students and the programme.”

Subtheme 3: Enhancing Positive Communication.

Effective consortium communication fostered a respectful environment, enhancing teamwork and a problem-solving attitude. Frequent meetings and open discussions ensured that everyone’s opinions were valued, contributing to a family-like atmosphere which was previously described as a feature of the studied EMJMDs. According to Solo (professional staff): “So, in the consortium, I think we do communicate very well with each other. I think the communication is effective and respectful. Because we work together on one project, and that’s yeah, that’s our product that we, we put together.”

This dynamic communication approach facilitated efficient decision-making and solution-oriented discussions. Besides, open communication channels enabled honest conversations about programme improvements and their challenges, underlining the significance of respect, honesty, and mutual support, as Blythe (professional staff), emphasised:

The ability to communicate well and take into account everybody’s needs and feelings and support each other. And yeah, make sure that everybody is okay. And that if someone’s struggling, that he's not left alone and that we can work together to achieve goals together.

This positive atmosphere reinforces existing scholarly literature regarding the significance of effective communication in organisational settings and highlights its role in promoting cohesion,

productivity, and overall success. According to Saputra (2021), effective communication creates a positive work environment that fosters teamwork and collaboration. Besides, “[c]ommunication skills can be improved by increasing self-confidence” (Saputra, 2021, p. 65), which is aligned with Men and Yue’s (2019) observation about employees who feel heard, valued, and empowered through open and equal communication and then experience positive emotions such as happiness, pride, appreciation, and affection.

Subtheme 4: Strong Team Spirit Values.

Consortium partners were selected based not only on academic quality and research interest but also on individuals’ commitment to creating a cohesive group to achieve common goals: the programme’s quality and success. The accomplishment was attributed to a shared sense of value and respect among members, irrespective of their roles. This egalitarian approach promotes an open exchange of ideas and fosters an atmosphere where every opinion is considered valid, as declared by Blythe (professional staff):

I think, and our consortium has really managed to keep that spirit throughout the existence of the project, that yeah, we can all contribute and all give our input, and there is no idea that’s better than the other. And we can all express our concerns if we have some or share how we feel.

Besides, disagreements and weaknesses are addressed collectively as a shared responsibility, facilitating effective problem-solving and decision-making and promoting constant improvement. Additionally, social interactions, such as in-person meetings and shared experiences, cultivate a sense of community, as Luxury (academic) echoed in the following testimonial: “So, I think the whole programme is very much rooted in teamwork. I mean, I think it couldn't happen without

these different capacities from the different institutions. So, I think without the teamwork, the programme will really die.”

Furthermore, as underlined by Mattessich and Johnson (2018), for organisations, collaboration is a partnership formed by two or more organisations to achieve shared goals, characterised by commitment, jointly developed structures, shared responsibility, mutual authority, accountability, and resource and reward sharing. This collaboration necessitates thorough planning and clear communication channels, since it entails increased risk due to the contribution of individual resources and reputations (Mattessich & Johnson, 2018). These statements precisely describe the type of teamwork partners and staff develop within an EMJMD and the importance of their team was a common finding during both quantitative and qualitative phases of my study. For this reason, the main success of the observed consortiums is a strong Collaborative Mindset which in turn reinforces Team Effectiveness.

Subtheme 5: Roles: The Importance of One’s Identity.

The interdisciplinary nature and the relatively small size of the EMJMDs facilitate a cohesive working environment where staff roles are distinctly defined and well-understood. This contrasts with more extensive university settings where recognition and familiarity among colleagues can be challenging and administrative roles may be undervalued. For this reason, as declared by Dale (academic): “I think that for administrative people to work in the consortium could be much more pleasant or also with more recognised, yes.”

Clarity also increases value and appreciation for all contributions, creating an environment where everyone’s expertise is acknowledged. Rigbe (blended professional) confirmed this by underlining: “And I think we know each other’s expertise areas, and, and have

a lot of respect for each other's professional level. So, I think in that way, it's very easy to acknowledge each other.”

Working on a team requires “understanding not only one's role but also the role of other professionals” (Atwal & Caldwell, [2006](#), p. 359) because the absence of role clarity may cause individual and institutional frustration and failure to achieve the expected goals (Radhakrishnan, [2018](#)). Moreover, identity work may have profound individual and collective implications (Brown, [2015](#)) because job relationships also outline our working personalities (Jenkins, [2014](#)).

Academic studies focusing on job titles in higher education in general are limited, although the subject has been investigated considering professional staff situation (Melling, [2019](#)). For instance, a study developed by Sun et al. ([2022](#)) revealed that individuals with a solid professional identity show elevated work engagement and career satisfaction levels.

6.5.2 Theme 2 – Universities: Key Features and Traits

Information related to the intricate mechanisms within the higher education institutions participating in this study are described in Theme 2 (Figure 6.4). Participants shared their insights on both the difficulties and positive aspects giving the possibility to underline differences and similarities between the institutional settings and the EMJMDs' *Third Space*.

Subtheme 1: Navigating Organisational Complexity.

Participants described structural issues, procedural obstacles, and difficulties arising from interactions among staff. Recurrent topics were:

Communication Challenges. Participants highlighted difficulties in communication, as mentioned by Reef (academic):

I think sometimes sort of having clear guidelines on communication so that we're all aware of all the things that we need to be aware of, and that are related to our job, that would, that would make things better.

Figure 6.4 – Theme 2: Universities: Key Features and Traits

Source: Author's own work

As described in academic literature, effective communication is essential to any organisation's success because if there is a hostile relationship with one another, individuals will be unable to work efficiently and will negatively impact the organisation's profitability, productivity, and goodwill (Sapungan et al., [2019](#)). In addition, as declared by Md Yusof and Rahmat ([2020](#)), when there are communication barriers (environmental or personal), the communication flow is affected, which, in turn, affects the organisation as a whole.

Bureaucracy and Administrative Burden. Several interviewees expressed frustration with bureaucratic processes, paperwork, and an increasing administrative load. In addition, academics feel burdened by administrative tasks that they believe should not be their responsibility, as described by Sutton (blended professional):

Because sometimes people from academia are frustrated about the increasing number of like bureaucratic burden. And they think they should, they shouldn't deal with that. That should be the job of administrative people. And people from the administration sometimes could get frustrated from the fact that academics are not usually like, the most precise in their paperwork.

Although the standardisation, routinisation and rules typical to a bureaucratic system are needed in today's higher education institutions, it is essential to prevent the loss of the human aspect of education, which includes broadening students' experience and development of their skills and knowledge (Skipper, [2018](#)). For this reason, as underscored by Skipper ([2018](#)), the time devoted by academics to bureaucratic tasks prevents a more scientific interaction with the students, which limits the student's educational experience. Therefore, institutions should evaluate this aspect while creating different systems and regulations.

Institutional Structure and Understanding. The mismatch between institutional managerial structures and academic settings creates several challenges due to the lack of understanding. Greer (professional staff) emphasised this situation by stating:

I would say it's two really different worlds. And maybe it's difficult for an academic to understand what an administrative person has to do out. Yeah, I see that the everyday they just don't understand that. When you say, do that task that it can take... It's not

difficult, but it can take a lot of time, because of this, and that. So, there's the kind of practical details that we are, you know, it's like, it's too much for them to understand.

Lack of Recognition of Administrative Work: Interviewees expressed concerns about the perceived lack of recognition and value for administrative work within higher education institutions because the importance of professional staff may not be fully understood or appreciated regardless of their expertise and knowledge, as described by Ainsley (professional staff): “So, you know, I mean, you're just, you're just an administrative, and sometimes they told you, come on, you're just an administrative.” This concern was confirmed by Taran (academic), who highlighted: “I would say that much, much needed to be done in order to, to bring visibility to the value of administrative staff.”

Whitchurch ([2008a](#)) stated that the binary situation between professional staff and academics is no longer clear-cut. Besides, even though professional staff have long been perceived as invisible actors (Hunter et al., [2018](#)), things are now changing. Therefore, institutional strategies such as comprehensive internationalisation are needed because higher education institutions need to recognise the distinct yet equally crucial roles fulfilled by professional staff and academics as collaborative partners not only in the internationalisation process (Hunter et al., [2018](#)) but in the entire educational experience.

Institutional Size and Flexibility. The size of the institution plays a role in the flexibility of administrative processes. Larger institutions may face more challenges in establishing close bonds and collaboration synergies. In this regard, Garnet (blended professional) mentioned: “[A]t the institutional level, I don't see it because if you manage such numbers of students, professors, tasks, and so on, it's, it's really complicated to establish these close bonds and collaboration synergies.” The statement is confirmed by the academic literature, as demonstrated by Schubert

and Yan (2016), who declared that larger higher education institutions have more difficulties adapting to changes because they rely on rigid bureaucratic procedures. This is frequently linked to a less flexible structure and many specific procedures.

Resource Allocation and Funding. The availability of resources, both in terms of personnel and funding, was identified as a critical factor in the efficiency of administrative processes. Bellamy (academic) underlined this situation by affirming: “They told me that there is not enough personnel, but I don’t know. So, it’s true that they try to help me and ask if we have something to delegate, but it’s not enough.” Once again, scholars have indicated that specific procedures, such as resource allocation, are more efficient in smaller higher education institutions than in larger ones due to the reduced bureaucratic hurdles (Schubert & Yan, 2016).

Resistance to Change. Established rigid organisations with inflexible bureaucratic processes can delay the adaptation of more efficient methods. Dale (academic) stated: “What I think is that maybe people can be afraid to speak clearly. Not because they are ... I mean, because they are a little bit afraid to change.” Scientific research on resistance to change confirms Dale’s excerpt and reveals other factors such as the organisational structure, fear of the unknown, threats to power or influence, habit, inconvenience or loss of freedom, economic implications, and lack – or obsolete – knowledge and skills (Yılmaz & Kılıçoğlu 2013).

Need for Clear Roles and Responsibilities. Mutual understanding of the importance of each role is crucial for effective collaboration. At the institutional level, there is still a lot of work to be done and this was mentioned by Dale (academic):

So, in the university, you might have some administrative people ... and ... whose role is not very well recognised. Otherwise, it could be fundamental for example. In the consortium, it is not the case because I mean, it is a much smaller, so everybody now very

well, other people. And so, it is very clear, also administrative people what, what they are doing.

Understanding the role of an individual within an organisation plays a crucial effect on that individual's behaviour. Therefore, as confirmed by Martinez et al. (2008), "the misapplication of a job title to a work role/ title-bearer likely will result in a shift in perceived value, because job titles intrinsically imply value" (p. 23). Moreover, it has also been demonstrated that professional identity and career satisfaction have a positive relationship (Sun et al., 2022), which means it is crucial in higher education institutions to understand the different levels and expertise of professional staff.

The challenges outlined stem from a complex culture influenced by external forces in establishing innovative dynamics and situations within the higher education institutional environment (Chandler, 2011) and bureaucratic procedures, which have increased due to higher education institutions' financial transition (Finkielsztein & Wagner, 2023). The role of leadership is crucial to guarantee values aimed at fostering trust and collaboration and improving performance and satisfaction (Islamy et al., 2020). Ideally, a more distributed leadership with more interactions (Doyle & Brady, 2018) could facilitate effective communication, enhancing staff performance (Marlow et al., 2018). Additionally, strategies for additional institutional support in terms of rewards and resource allocation are needed, because when employees express satisfaction with the rewards they receive at work, it is generally correlated with feelings of competence, autonomy, and connection to their tasks (Thibault Landry & Whillans, 2018). Besides, it is fundamental to promote the recognition of the role of the different staff categories as key players in the successful achievement of the institution's performance objectives.

Subtheme 2: Reassessing the Historical Divide

Despite variations, the professional staff-academic ‘divide’ seems to persist at the institutional level. Challenges previously described, such as bureaucratic complexities, hierarchical dynamics, lack of recognition and administrative burdens, contribute to reinforce the division among staff categories.

Hence, the dichotomy between innovative thinking from the academic side and the administrative need for practicality appears as a critical tension point, as expressed by Oakley (academic): “[t]he administration asks many things that academicians feel are superfluous and unnecessary. And then there are like two reactions, or they don’t fill what they’re supposed to fill. Or they just saturate the administration.” However, participants shared different views on the ‘divide’. For some, there was no distinction between academics and professional staff within their institution. This is the case of Kai (professional staff), who declared:

So academic people and admin people have ... We’ve been working together, most of the team has been working together for many years now. So, we have a very good and solid relationship. But yes, unfortunately, there are some departments here at the university as a whole that it’s not at all like that. And of course, academic prevails for the decision making that admin sometimes cannot.

On the contrary, the majority acknowledged a more precise division, with academics often driving innovation while professional staff were perceived only as the support workforce. The influence of institutional culture, hierarchical traditions, individual personalities, and even national systems add complexity to this ‘divide’. The following quote by Ainsley (professional staff) highlights this challenge:

And you’ll realise that there are several countries and several organisations that they don’t have the chance just to, you know, to give their opinion or too, if there is any problem

that they are going to be punished publicly or they know, I mean, that they are not going to have any, any help from the, from the academics or from the director.

Similarly, Finley (blended professional) affirmed: “I think institution-wise, outside of this consortium and programme, there’s a much bigger ‘divide’, you know, there’s the admin people; we don’t necessarily see them that much. They do amazing things, and we value them, but there’s a lot less interaction.”

Participants also noted the influence of certain personal traits in either reinforcing or undermining this division. The following quotes offer an illustration of this aspect, underlining its various components and implications. Ainsley declared (professional staff):

I mean, there are scholars and scholars, and you know, there are professors and professors. Some have some quiet, you know, easy-going and, and they look for this type of dialogue between different, you know, that type of profile in the work area, and others are super hierarchical.

Likewise, Blythe (professional staff) also mentioned:

It also depends on the people you work with. I find you know, in previous generations, the university model was different. The administrators were here too, I don’t want to say serve, but it was almost the case, like just doing the administrative support. [...] So yeah, it’s starting to change. But I feel there’s still a barrier between the two worlds. And I think it also depends on the discipline your work in.

In complex environments such as higher education institutions, individuals with different hierarchical positions interact continuously, shaping their relationships based on their status, significantly impacting the way in which crucial information is communicated (Sutcliffe et al., [2004](#)) and consequently the effectiveness of any type of interaction and collaboration. Even

more, when describing higher education institutions' challenges, an interviewee mentioned that academia and administration are two different worlds. This is confirmed by Bess and Dee (2014), who stated that each group has divergent philosophies and contrasting belief systems.

The vast majority of participants declared that within the institutions, complex interactions between these two groups were evident due to misunderstandings and a failure to grasp each other's responsibilities and pressures, as described by Caldwell (2022a). Unfortunately, the 'divide' fragments the organisation structure and restricts opportunities for staff interaction and communication, collaboration, and knowledge sharing (Duane & Corcoran, 2018), which, as already mentioned, are key factors for a successful relationship. Consequently, there is a need for a supportive environment that encourages communication and empowers employees so that they feel connected with the institution (Corcoran & Duane, 2019), avoiding a dominant culture that supports individualistic, competitive, and hierarchical approaches to work (Newell & Bain, 2020).

Subtheme 3: Reviewing Collaborative Mechanisms.

In parallel, participants also reported constructive experiences in both institutional and consortium settings. Solo's comment (professional staff) is an example of this experience: "I would say that, that we have been working with a Collaborative Mindset, both in the university and also in the consortium as well." In addition, Dale (academic) reinforced this perception by declaring:

So, I think that usually people have a good attitude, and I am happy with my collaborations, both in the consortium and also inside my department. Of course, sometimes it's not easy, because you may have a different point of view. I think that's quite normal. We are human beings, so and also different stories.

Collaboration between different departments and stakeholders as well as effective communication and cooperation among staff members were vital for streamlining processes and enhancing institutional effectiveness, as declared by Atlas (professional staff):

Yeah, maybe it is because we have to solve a lot of issues at the different levels of universities. And we have to solve, for example, joint diploma, for example, changes in diploma supplement changes in the application, and we have to solve it with a different people with different departments of the university.

Additionally, the importance of collaboration remained crucial to promote institutional excellence as explained by Ash (professional staff): “I could say that politics in our department is well-being and respect for all of them. For all of us. Each people have something to do. And each [person] is important if we want the job well done.” Such collaborations not only promoted efficiency but also contributed to a positive work environment. Sutton (blended professional) illustrated this aspect by affirming: “So, I think we could see definitely also the improvement there, at least in regarding the administration, we are involved, at the institutional level. So, I think there definitely could be a positive experience.”

Despite common challenges and the need to align EMJMDs’ complex administrative procedures mentioned in Theme 1, in many cases it was possible to collaborate adequately at the institutional level. The vast literature on collaboration reinforces the findings of this study by highlighting that collaborations cannot happen without mutual trust and respect of the parties involved, and for this reason, establishing relationships over time is essential (Pham & Tanner, [2015](#)). By working together seamlessly with the different services across the institutions, it was ensured that students received comprehensive support and that administrative processes were efficiently managed, ultimately contributing to the EMJMD’s success. In line with Fapohunda’s

declaration (see Chapter Five), this was possible due to individuals who had the needed experience, had adequate problem-solving abilities, and were action oriented (Fapohunda, [2013](#)).

6.5.3 Theme 3 – Inside Out: Personal and Interpersonal Dynamics

As explained in Theme 1, Distinctive Elements of EMJMDs, the vast majority of respondents highlighted that working in these programmes constituted a secondary job. This situation implies that individuals operated concurrently in two distinct environments and needed to adapt from one setting to the other depending on the role assigned to them. Positive and negative outcomes – presented in this last theme – derived from this experience (Figure 6.5).

Figure 6.5 – Theme 3: Inside Out: Personal and Interpersonal Dynamics

Source: Author's own work

Subtheme 1: Fulfilment and Contentment.

Satisfaction within the *Third Space* of EMJMDs encompasses various dimensions, reflecting participants' engagement in their roles. They expressed satisfaction with the diverse tasks they were undertaking, ranging from administrative responsibilities to academic collaborations, and finding fulfilment in the programme's multifaceted nature. On this regard, Taran's opinion (an academic) was the following:

This is a really incredible experience and very motivating [...] And also, it's an opportunity to develop research-wise, even if it is an educational programme. But extensive contacts with academics and colleagues worldwide and the possibility of involving them in the Master's programme. And actually, possibly even to develop new networks. Not, not only in countries but also on continents.

In addition, participants emphasised that satisfaction positively impacted their willingness to engage and surmount challenges collectively, regardless of the obstacles they may encounter as specified by Raine (professional staff):

Because I think the more you are satisfied and happy in your job, the more you're willing to go the extra mile. So like, even when you're asked to do something terrible as part of the consortium, you're like, yeah, no problem.

Moreover, they emphasised the significance of personal motivation and the rewarding experiences offered by EMJMD programmes, such as international encounters and opportunities for professional development. The following quote by Koda (professional staff) exemplifies this feeling:

Oh, I think in general, I can say I'm, I'm very satisfied. Although of course, I also see the issues that there might be at the institutional level sometimes in the way indeed, feedback

or, or rewards are being set up. Very much. And then I'm talking about my personal motivation comes from, from, from within is a belief in the values that are connected to internationalisation.

Similarly, Greer (professional staff) expressed:

But I like the job in itself, because it's very varied, you know, you have a lot of different tasks. And a lot of different... how can I see people I'm in relation with, it can be students, it can be colleagues at [university], it can be the other university, sometimes professors, can be embassies.

Despite dealing with demanding workloads and navigating various challenges, participants clearly expressed feelings of fulfilment and enthusiasm for their respective jobs. Luxury (academic) related the experience as follows:

I think, my job satisfaction is very high. If it's like from zero to 10, with 10 being the highest, I think it's nine or even 10. So, I'm very, very happy with my job. And especially the part of my job, which, which has to do with this Mundus programme. So, this Erasmus Mundus programme is very satisfactory. [...] It's kind of a ... it's a challenging thing. But it's also something that is very rewarding that you can collaborate across institutions.

The vast majority of participants in this study were satisfied with their jobs despite the workload, and this was clear in the findings both during the quantitative and qualitative phases. The academic literature underscores that work environment, advancement prospects, and participation in decision-making processes are all highly significant aspects for employees in the higher education sector (Ramasamy & Renganathan, [2017](#); Szromek, [2020](#)). Likewise, knowledge sharing (Islamy et al., [2020](#)) and compensation influence job satisfaction, which is pivotal for

efficiency and work quality within academia (Szromek, [2020](#)). Previous research has also shown that emotional intelligence and job satisfaction play crucial roles in employee engagement, making them critical factors in cultivating a more engaged workforce (Meradios & Alcantara, [2023](#)). Finally, job satisfaction mediates service quality in higher education and organisational commitment among academics and professional staff (Trivellas & Santouridis, [2016](#)). Even if some job satisfaction enhancers such as career advancement and a manageable workload were absent, it is clear that within the EMJMD the fulfilment was significantly influenced by the work atmosphere and the acknowledgment participants receive.

Subtheme 2: Balancing Workload Effectively.

Managing an EMJMD entails a complex array of responsibilities and challenges that often result in an overwhelming workload. Flannery (academic) described these circumstances as follows:

Because I was always, we were all pressed for time, for different reasons. So, as I mentioned, the administrative staff, it was on top of what they were already doing, and many of them were totally over worked. And for me, it was always on top of what I was supposed to do to ... you know, advance.

The demands of the programme, particularly during intensive periods, pose significant problems for individuals balancing various roles and commitments, as mentioned by Raine (professional staff):

So the application process, I think, was the one. It's super interesting because you get to see this, like a very holistic application of the applicant, and you really get to know whom they are going through it. But because of it's because you have to do it in short window of a month. You have to do that kind of full time with your academic for like two to

three weeks to make, and then you have to come together, and you have to do the ranking and shortlisting together. That time pressure on it was quite intense.

The concentrated workload impacted individuals differently. It potentially led to stress and diminished the ability to maintain a healthy work-life balance, as underlined by Quest (professional staff) when mentioning: “Uhm... It’s definitely a challenge to have to work weird hours. To be available, like 7/24. And, by summers, we have a summer course as well.” Similarly, for academics it was extremely onerous, not allowing them to engage in research activities. The following quote from Flannery (academic) illustrates the situation: “And this took so many hours every week and every month that it took away from my mind the publication output.”

Other’s perceptions regarding the intrinsic value of an EMJMD varied depending on individuals and on occasions were related to the workload, as stated by Darby (blended professional): “The others might just say, well, it’s fine that we have it. And it sounds good, but it’s more work for us.” Hence, it was also highlighted the need for additional support in navigating the workload, because frequently – as stated by Sutton (blended professional) – the feeling was: “Like lack of enough administrative manpower, which could kind of like, be enough for dealing with this administrative burden.”

Lastly, there was a recurring theme in terms of a lack of financial rewards for the extra hours invested in the programme, a sentiment echoed by all staff categories. In this regard, Kai (professional staff) mentioned:

Sometimes we cannot just forget that we worked too hard to get this and sometimes the rewarding mechanism, not, not feeling happy and proud of what we do but also of course, there’s the financial aspect that needs to evolve also, and sometimes it doesn’t happen as often and as easily as it should be.

As for teaching commitments, participants coordinating an EMJMD also struggled, as declared by Kelcey (blended professional): “So, as I said, I mean, we don’t get a discount on teaching hours. I mean, very little discount. So, I still have a lot of teaching, a lot of research and a lot of managing.”

Workload was a recurring issue among participants due to the nature of these programmes and their part-time jobs. However, in spite of challenges, participants demonstrate a strong commitment and fulfilment derived from contributing to the Master’s success.

It is worth mentioning that some previous scientific studies use only job satisfaction to measure the well-being of individuals without considering its proven multidimensionality, such as engagement (Pelly, [2023](#)), policies, workload, and training opportunities which influence – in an interconnected way – the well-being of both staff and students (Brewster et al., [2022](#)). For this reason, workload distribution is critical in mitigating burnout and promoting well-being. Research consistently demonstrates that excessive workloads and unclear or conflicting role expectations can result in negative work experiences and affect work engagement (Clarke, [2015](#); Curran & Prottas, [2017](#)). Similarly, for academics, a supportive work environment is vital in counteracting the adverse impacts of workload on job satisfaction (Janib et al., [2022](#)), as is the case of academics involved in EMJMDs.

Subtheme 3: Understanding Frustration Triggers.

Frequently, higher education institution systems pose significant issues, including rigidity and inefficiency due to their large scale, hindering the implementation of necessary updates and improvements, as mentioned by Atlas (professional staff): “I’m working in some rigid system. And I see some procedures could be done much easier to refresh them, etc. But it is so slow to

put some new inputs in this huge rigid system.” To complicate this even more, EMJMDs are programmes with precise and different requirements, making them much more difficult to implement in such bureaucratised environments. Oakley (academic) described this situation by mentioning: “Then, of course, the academicians feel that they are not listened to. Because it’s yeah, what we are imposed as the programme is not fitting the reality of where we belong.”

Academic staff, despite their dedication to fulfilling multifaceted roles encompassing teaching, research, and administrative duties, often encounter an inevitable sense of being overwhelmed and frustrated, as declared by Rigbe (blended professional):

And, you know, this is so much. It’s so different from any other programme. And I feel like a lot of people who have never been involved in this don’t know, they just see in your CV. [Name] does this for like, [number] years [...] I do institutionally not feel very much appreciated in this role.

Likewise, Kelcey (blended professional) mentioned the following: “But as I said, I’m also doing research and doing other things. So, I feel a bit overwhelmed that I cannot work efficiently in all the aspects I’m working on.” Professional staff, on their side, described a sense of frustration due to different aspects. They are mainly related to hierarchical issues, lack of acknowledgment, the ‘divide’, financial compensation and professional development. In this sense, Ainsley (professional staff) underlined:

Or when you find, yeah, I mean, when you find like, some hierarchical procedures, that there is no way to save on escape from that. [...] Or when you see like, those hierarchical relationships among your colleagues, and you see that, yeah, when people are suffering because of that, yeah. It’s like, okay, because there are like, people that you see that it’s

like that they are super frustrated, and that the, the result of the job is not going well, because that person is not feeling okay.

Equally, Blythe (professional staff) described the difficulties by affirming: “So sometimes, it can be a bit frustrating because I feel that I’m not really understood in the difficulties that I face. So, this can be a bit difficult,” and Royal (professional staff) said: “But I’m not even sure if there’s a bigger financial reward or a bigger appreciation reward, so that is not really there.”

The frustration triggers stated by participants are mainly related to the complexity of the institutions described in Theme 2 (Universities: Key Features and Traits), the ‘divide’ and the overload situation. These topics resonate with existing literature, which underscores the challenges within universities related to bureaucratic and hierarchical schemes that diminish the agility and responsiveness of staff members. Additionally, hierarchical structures, such as those based on professional roles or length of experience, can prevent the open and assertive communication needed for successfully overcoming mistakes or errors (Sutcliffe et al., [2004](#)). In essence, the bureaucratic structure of higher education institutions generates a conflict between the objectives of education and the administrative principles, resulting in a less enriching experience (Skipper, [2018](#)), and the hierarchical organisational culture impedes staff interaction, collaboration, and knowledge sharing (Corcoran & Duane, [2019](#)) which are also consequences of the ‘divide’.

Subtheme 4: Individuals Shape Relationships Dynamics.

Individual differences play a significant role in shaping the dynamics of interpersonal relationships. Factors such as communication styles, emotional engagement, and personal attitudes towards work impact how individuals interact with their peers. These personal

tendencies contribute to varying levels of cohesion among staff members, as highlighted by Ash (professional staff):

Because I think that that depends on the person. I tried to have good contact with all colleagues, not only by mail, but I tried to have contact with them through Teams, for example. And I have realised that it helps a lot to speak with a person and it's more efficiently, even by telephone.

Similarly, close relationships between professional staff and academics are fostered in environments where there is open communication and mutual understanding of each other's roles. Hayden (professional staff) elaborated this idea by stating: "This is because we realised that every person has a specific role in the implementation of the programme and the professors they recognise and value our work, and vice versa."

Beyond individual traits, the organisational context also shapes interpersonal dynamics within academic institutions. Hence, hierarchical structures and institutional cultures can affect effective collaboration, creating miscommunications and disparities, as described by Ainsley (professional staff): "So it depends really with whom you are working, I think that is related with the years of experience that they could have in these international projects. And I think that also is linked to the culture of the institution." Additionally, the role of leadership in creating inclusive environments which promote shared ownership and open communication is key. Koda (professional staff) emphasised this aspect by underlining: "Yeah, in the consortium, I think it very much depends on the individual leadership styles of the academics that are responsible for the department."

Understanding personal and organisational factors is essential for developing positive working relationships. Although professional staff have different relationships with academics

depending on whom they work with, in what capacity, how they work and how they communicate with each other (Caldwell, [2022a](#)), trust in senior management impacts global workplace outcomes, including affective commitment, turnover intention, and job satisfaction (Bakay, [2015](#)).

Besides, establishing mutual trust and respect over time is essential for maintaining productive collaborations (Pham & Tanner, [2015](#)). In professional environments, cultivating deeper connections benefits individuals because it enables them to obtain support, when necessary (House, [2018](#)), as is the case for respondents who described positive collaboration at the consortium and institutional levels. Interpersonal relations can flourish in certain circumstances, and if robust enough, they have the potential to overcome the more difficult organisational conditions and boost or decrease service quality, with repercussions at both individual and institutional levels (Gibbs & Kharouf, [2022](#)).

6.6 Concluding Remarks

The qualitative analysis findings complemented those from the quantitative analysis in Chapter Five. They indicate that the benefits of the studied EMJMDs go beyond just enhancing the visibility of the higher education institutions involved in the international education market. They are considered a unique, enriching, and diverse life-changing experience for people involved in this study.

Despite workload challenges, participants demonstrate a solid commitment to contributing to the success of EMJMDs, underscoring the importance of Team Effectiveness in the work environment. These mechanisms are a valuable example of productive interprofessional

collaboration within a *Third Space* setting, promoting a culture of mutual support, dedication, and trust among staff to achieve a common goal.

The impact of the collaborative dynamics within the EMJMDs studied is highly relevant since they provide the needed mechanisms to overcome the ‘divide’ between professional staff and academics. It establishes a supportive environment that encourages communication, empowers participants, fosters mutual understanding and promotes recognition of all participants’ contributions. These efforts are essential for a more productive work environment, which, in turn, is indispensable to encourage and achieve institutional success.

Regarding higher education institutions, my findings highlight that collaboration at the institutional level still needs to be strengthened by dismantling hierarchies and recognising the indispensable roles played by professional staff, academics, and blended professional. Moreover, it accentuates the importance of relationship-building over time because cultivating deeper connections among staff members would help to overcome organisational challenges and enhance service quality. With the extensive information gathered during the data collection and these findings, I addressed this study’s Research Questions, which are discussed in the following chapter.

CHAPTER SEVEN: DISCUSSION

7.1 Introduction

As described in the literature review, over the past few decades tensions have existed between the two primary staff groups working within higher education institutions (professional staff and academics) due to – amongst other issues – the increased bureaucratisation of universities (Finkielsztein & Wagner, [2023](#)), economic pressures (Shepherd, [2018](#)), and the professionalisation in higher education (Sebalj et al., [2012](#)). Simultaneously, *Third Spaces* appeared and promoted the flourishing of blended professionals, individuals with valuable skill sets in both academic and administrative domains. By closely examining the collaborative dynamics within the EMJMDs' *Third Space* my research findings offer a deeper scientific insight of the professional dynamics within such degrees, starting from the viewpoint of the staff involved in their design, management and implementation. This disclosure provides a new perspective on these Master's degrees and allows for the confirmation and enrichment of previous studies and, in certain cases, some counter-evidence.

My results show how different dynamics of collaboration within EMJMDs are highly interconnected and heavily influence each other. For example, collaboration and team effectiveness are two sides of the same coin and have some features in common. Similarly, frustration triggers, organisational complexity, and workload balance are all related to the individual's job dimension. Despite the fact that my analysis discusses the themes that emerged independently, it is important to repeat that naturally these themes intersect and overlap. In this chapter, I focus more in-depth on such intersections, offering a comprehensive examination of the results by comparing my findings with prior literature and identifying similarities, connections or differences that lead to the conclusions of the study. In parallel, when possible, I associate the

results with good practices from other scientific areas, in those cases in which they can also be applied in the educational field.

I have divided the chapter into four main sections reflecting the themes that emerged in the qualitative analysis and my Research Questions. The first section describes all the aspects related to the EMJMDs, their unique characteristics, and the way in which the divide is overcome. The second section presents the results at the institutional level and the differences between the institutions and the EMJMDs. The third section explains the respondents' perceptions and the contrast between their happiness of being part of this community and, at the same time, some causes of frustration. In the last section of the chapter, I move on to discuss how the findings obtained helped me to address the two Research Questions and sub questions of my research.

7.2 Identifying Distinctive Elements of EMJMDs

The EMJMD offers unique features that set it apart from other joint programmes or international degrees. These include a genuinely multicultural setting, a small but supportive environment, and a close-knit community with a common goal. These features enhance the learning experience and foster a strong sense of belonging among students and staff.

7.2.1 Spotlighting Exclusive Traits

Complex international projects like the EMJMDs operate successfully with effective mixed teams. Due to their singularities (small culturally diverse entities with intricate administrative processes), they can be considered odd and problematic programmes within universities, as declared by Oakley (academic): "Having an Erasmus Mundus is problematic." For this reason,

sometimes, those working on EMJMDs perceive a sense of loneliness. However, this perception of being “socially isolated even when among other people” (Cacioppo & Cacioppo, [2018](#), p. 426) does not prevent consortiums from creating cohesive teams. Moreover, recent scientific literature related to the examination of staff relationships in higher education has suggested that smaller environments foster a collaborative environment because of their limited professional staff and academic staff numbers (Syno et al., [2023](#)).

These teams provide a sense of belonging to involved staff as their collective effort used to navigate challenges, define shared goals, and foster a culture of mutual support, dedication and trust explains the EMJMDs’ “family” perception. Previous studies echo these findings since individuals associate belonging with being accepted, included, understood, welcomed, liked, and appreciated because belonging is an essential human need, and its absence can profoundly and negatively affect an individual’s life (Allen, [2021](#)). This indicates that a positive professional experience influences trust which, in turn, fosters interprofessional collaboration in the same way of mutual respect as it indicates an understanding and acknowledgment of how diverse professionals in a team complement each other’s contributions and rely on each other (San Martín-Rodríguez et al., [2005](#)).

7.2.2 EMJMDs Nurture Unique Collaborations

Acknowledging individual diversity and cultivating a collaborative, tolerant, and respectful culture are essential in building trust and reciprocity, which enhances staff motivation and dedication (Gibbs & Kharouf, [2022](#)). Therefore, in such a complex setting as an EMJMD, collaboration is key to fostering openness, flexibility, adaptability and willingness to accommodate different cultural contexts. Several authors indicated that building favourable conditions becomes more

challenging when teams have diverse cultures because although cultural diversity can bring benefits, it may also create difficulties as team members navigate differences in attitudes, beliefs, and values, impacting teamwork (Shawn Burke et al., [2017](#)). Manca et al. ([2018](#)) specifically stated: “multidisciplinary innovation groups might face additional challenges due to the existing culture and structures” (Manca et al., [2018](#), p. 527).

Likewise, Mattessich and Johnson ([2018](#)) suggested that collaborating across cultures presents a multifaceted challenge and prompted people to consider the influence of culture on our collaborative efforts, raising questions about skills and perspectives to guarantee the effectiveness, fairness, and significance of our work in cross-cultural settings. On the contrary, the findings of this study showed that in the EMJMD consortiums involved, there was an innate disposition to take advantage of these differences as part of the richness of the learning environment. Hence, my results are aligned with Shawn Burke et al. ([2017](#)) since, as explained in Chapter Five, these authors noted that studies have demonstrated that over time, culturally diverse teams outperform when they are able to work through their differences, which is the case of the EMJMDs studied.

7.2.3 Fostering Positive Communication

Existing research indicates that effective communication, including open dialogue and attentive listening, is essential for promoting shared understanding among team members and enhancing the exchange of information (San Martín-Rodríguez et al., [2005](#)). Spitzberg ([2000](#)) affirmed that defining good communication is a complex and ambiguous task. Still, he also suggested that “if a communicator can achieve preferred objectives in a manner that is perceived as legitimate in the context by those concerned, it is likely to be communication of relatively high quality” (Spitzberg,

[2000](#), p. 109). In addition, communication is part of the so-called key soft skills or “21st Century Skills” identified as the “4Cs” (creativity, critical thinking, communication, and collaboration) and plays a significant role in today’s education and work environment (Thornhill-Miller et al., [2023](#)). Hence, good communication is critical within organisations to coordinating activities, understanding roles and responsibilities, sharing information, building trust and acceptance, creating social relationships (Udin et al., [2019](#); Halim & Razak, [2014](#)) and improving performance since it facilitates obtaining information for task completion (Marlow et al., [2018](#)). On the contrary, it is also proven that when incomplete information is communicated, or it arrives in an inappropriate moment and way, it affects task development (Sutcliffe et al., [2004](#)).

My findings within the EMJMDs studied are consistent with previous research. Interviewees described effective communication at the consortium and personal levels, and they felt comfortable and valued when sharing ideas and promoting solutions. These feelings are affirmed in previous studies when it is stated that communication and interpersonal problem-solving skills positively contribute to social self-efficacy perception (Erozkan, [2013](#)).

In addition to the communication during formal meetings, an essential contributor to a cohesive group within the EMJMD involved was the social interactions developed. These gatherings allowed more informal communication. The academic literature echoes this finding, as Morgan et al. ([2015](#), p. 1228) indicated: “most important and tangible element of successful interprofessional collaboration is the importance of constant opportunity for frequent, shared informal communication.”

Respondents in my study frequently mentioned the problems caused by a lack of communication because it led to misunderstandings, decreased collaboration, and a general sense of frustration among team members, ultimately hindering the overall productivity and

effectiveness required. By contrast, effective communication was seen as a crucial factor in fostering a cohesive and collaborative work environment, enhancing mutual understanding, and contributing to the EMJMD's success. This highlights the significant impact that communication can have on performance and the importance of addressing barriers to improve team dynamics and outcomes.

7.2.4 The Significance of Identity

Even if interviewees also described challenges, participation in EMJMDs was marked by individuals' distinctive sense of satisfaction. Additionally, professional staff described the sense of feeling valued and that their expertise, skills and contributions were recognised. These outcomes are aligned with previous studies on relationships between staff, where factors such as job roles, recognition, and interpersonal interactions with academics contribute to how professional staff perceive their professional identity (Caldwell, [2022b](#)). Under this perspective, in [2014](#) Lewis highlighted the importance of job titles and their role in creating, shaping, and maintaining an identity for the role holders and their colleagues. Even more, when a title matches associated responsibilities, professionals have stronger identities, promote collaboration, and improve their performance (Miscenko & Day, [2016](#)).

Conversely, although job titles are used to recognise people even outside work, they can also cause stress if they do not show what employees do (Grant et al., [2014](#); Morales & Lambert, [2013](#)). Besides, when people assume roles, they complete activities associated with their roles, and other tasks may not be known (Radhakrishnan, [2018](#)). This is the case of EMJMDs developed for the first time in a university. It is common to have blurred responsibilities within this *Third Space*,

allowing professional staff to flourish by using their versatile skill set to navigate various tasks simultaneously and receive the recognition they deserve.

7.2.5 Embracing Strong Team Spirit

All the above elements come together to facilitate Team Effectiveness within the consortiums. Most participants defined trust, respect, and recognition as things they particularly appreciated. Staff knowledge and experience were valued, as Asencio and DeChurch ([2017](#)) described when organisations learned to see the wealth of bringing together teams to grasp each member's expertise and achieve better results. The academic literature on creating effective teams (Adamik, [2010](#)) and Interprofessional Collaboration confirm these findings. In [2022](#), Khan et al. provided a list of foundational attributes of Team Effectiveness related to Interprofessional Collaboration, and they are compared in Table 7.1 with the research findings from the mixed teams within the studied EMJMDs' *Third Space*.

My findings on Team Effectiveness are consistent with other studies that indicated that in many types of organisations and corporations working in teams is the norm to succeed. Currently, teams are more important than ever in most professional areas. From the military, the aerospace and aviation industries, to healthcare, businesses, and educational institutions because successful team spirit generates knowledge, reduces mistakes, fosters creativity, improves output, boosts job happiness, and guarantees success (von Davier et al., [2017](#)).

7.2.6 Overcoming the 'Divide'

The most evident outcome of the effective collaboration and Team Effectiveness observed in the majority of the EMJMDs studied is that the 'divide' was overcome. Despite issues such as the

Table 7.1 – Comparison of Team Effectiveness enablers in Interprofessional Collaboration and EMJMDs

<i>Interprofessional Collaboration traits</i>	<i>EMJMDs findings</i>
Set of goals and shared collaborative actions (van Dongen et al., 2017)	Common goal: successful Master’s degree
Steer collaborative endeavours (van Dongen et al., 2017)	Protected and secure environment: “Mundus Family”
Communication between providers (Morgan et al., 2015)	Effective communication
Trusting relations (McDonald et al., 2012)	Trust between staff members
Respect between team members (McDonald et al., 2012)	Respect for each other
Interdependency between providers (Nancarrow et al., 2013)	Staff members rely on each other
Role understanding (Nancarrow et al., 2013)	Role validation
Unique contributions from each member (Nancarrow et al., 2013)	All contributions are welcome
Shared authority and leadership support (Mulvale et al., 2016)	Lack of hierarchical attitude
All team members are involved to guarantee alignment and diminish conflict (Chong et al., 2013 ; D’Amour et al., 2005).	Staff members are involved in meetings for decision-making and problem-solving

Sources: Khan et al. ([2022](#)); Riskiyana et al. ([2018](#)); van Dongen et al. ([2017](#)); Morgan et al. ([2015](#)); McDonald et al. ([2012](#)); Nancarrow et al. ([2013](#)); Mulvale et al. ([2016](#)); Chong et al. ([2013](#)) and D’Amour et al. ([2005](#)).

sense of loneliness due to the inherent features of the programmes that make them difficult to understand within larger institutions, or a lack of consideration regarding the workload needed to make these programmes succeed, participants managed to surpass the ‘divide’.

The staff involved created a sense of community capable of overcoming any obstacle, including differences between staff categories. Consequently, in those cases, recognising all members’ skills, knowledge, and expertise was equally valued, regardless of their roles and positions. This helped the consortiums to work together towards the same goal.

While the vast majority of participants agreed that the ‘divide’ had been overcome, a few respondents mentioned that it was still present within their consortium. In these cases, professional staff mentioned that their role became evident to academics only upon direct interaction. The following quote from Hyden (professional staff) speaks eloquently about this feeling: “I think that if a professor, an academic staff is not involved in the European project, they can’t know how important the administrative staff can be in this writing part, and in the management part.” Besides, in a few cases, hierarchical approaches were present, with academics having more power (Wheeldon et al., [2023](#)), leading to role conflicts and communication failures (Sutcliffe et al., [2004](#)). These cases give evidence that even today, the ‘divide’ exists, harming people involved in these dynamics, diminishing the quality of the working environment and potentially reducing outcomes and results.

Nevertheless, it is fundamental to keep in mind that the ‘divide’ is not only due to organisational limitations, but also because of the pronounced disparity in the respective worldviews of these two groups (Bess & Dee, [2014](#)). Consequently, it is essential to create mechanisms where staff members can share their experiences, express their opinions on this sensitive and understudied topic, and create collaborative opportunities that bring academics and professional staff together. As declared by Bess and Dee ([2014](#)), forms of communication in higher education institutions need to be reviewed to allow academics and professional staff to share their deep-rooted, different viewpoints and principles (Bess & Dee, [2014](#)). In this way, working closely with a common goal will potentially create other spaces in which it is possible to enhance collaboration. More specifically, when higher education institutions implement new communication procedures, promoting an open discussion between academics and professional

staff (Bess & Dee, [2014](#)), as is the case of the EMIMDs' *Third Space* settings, it is possible to find solutions on topics that affect all.

Under this lens, Brewster et al. ([2022](#)) described how the student experience increased due to positive academics and professional staff collaboration. According to these authors, there is an interdependence between the well-being of staff and students grounded in the understanding that staff must maintain high levels of well-being to support student needs effectively (Brewster et al., [2022](#)). Something similar can be described at the EMJMD level, i.e., students perceived these programmes as positive experiences, and professional staff involved in them had the same perception.

Borrowing once again some concepts from the health environment, it is possible to affirm that limitations to Team Effectiveness within Interprofessional Collaboration are similar as when the 'divide' was perceived in the consortiums studied. In [2008](#), Xyrichis and Lowton stated that when team processes and team structure, including "team premises; team size and composition; organisational support; team meetings; clear goals and objectives; and audit" (Xyrichis & Lowton, [2008](#), p.140) are not well established, Interprofessional Collaboration is negatively affected. The complicated dynamics of Interprofessional Collaboration highlights that even if teamwork is an effective approach to achieving objectives, various obstacles could impede its full potential. Almost a decade later, Moncatar et al. ([2021](#)) reinforced this statement and listed some obstacles, which are presented in Figure 7.1. The figure shows three groups of common barriers: (i) individual principles (distrust and disrespect, narrow-mindedness, lack of familiarity with roles); (ii) Organisational limitations (staff shortages, economic constraints, logistical hurdles); and (iii) siloed systems culture (autonomous work) (Moncatar et al., [2021](#)).

Figure 7.1 – Barriers to Team Effectiveness

Source: Adapted from Moncatar ([2021](#))

The unique EMJMD environments foster a more personalised relationship with a close working dynamic among different staff categories. They create a sense of belonging, fostering a feeling of importance and satisfaction of being part of an exclusive community. This sense of community is only possible when there is a solid working relationship between academics and professional staff (Duane & Corcoran, [2018](#)).

Furthermore, for some professional staff, working in an EMJMD's *Third Space* was like working in a safe atmosphere compared to their work at the institutional level. This is due to the fact that they felt comfortable within an environment where they were secure enough to voice their concerns, ask questions, or share ideas; i.e., they perceived the consortium, as described by Edmondson ([2019](#)), as a psychologically safe environment (Edmondson, [2019](#)).

7.3 Core Attributes of Universities

Likewise, participants also provided insights into the institutional settings, highlighting key differences between the two environments. While hierarchical structures and bureaucratic elements were more prevalent within institutions, it's noteworthy that some respondents also described positive collaborative atmospheres.

7.3.1 Addressing the Complexity of Higher Education Institutions

Several challenges within the studied higher education institutions were identified in this study, and it was possible to observe differences between the EMJMDs' *Third Space* settings studied and the institutions involved. Factors such as ineffective communication, bureaucracy, and a lack of clear roles and recognition seem to create a less favourable environment, and participants noted this difference by emphasising a more positive atmosphere and feelings while working within the consortium rather than at the institutional level. As underlined by Bray and Williams (2017), there is an organisational and affective commitment when there is positive communication, creating a more symbiotic relationship between staff to overcome different challenges. The importance of communication has been underlined in the previous sections as a critical element in Team Effectiveness and Collaborative Mindset, which, in turn, facilitates the recognition of all team members' roles, responsibilities, and achievements. Consequently, when academics, blended professionals and professional staff experience satisfaction with their work environments it fosters positive relationships and the institution becomes more productive (Florenthal & Tolstikov-Mast, 2012).

While higher education institutions have made significant steps in achieving collective goals over the past few decades and are now widely recognised as key contributors to wealth

creation and economic prosperity (McCaffery, [2019](#)), there remains substantial room for improvement in terms of organisational culture. The culture within any organisation evolves over time and is shaped by various factors such as its structure, hierarchy, and management's attitudes and behaviours (Duane & Corcoran, [2018](#)). Hence, promoting and implementing changes to improve and create a better environment is fundamental.

An interesting working model from Lean Management based on the principles of business and manufacturing (Toyota Production System – TPS) was presented by Maciag in [2019](#) as a model that could be aligned well with the unique nature of higher education. According to the author, the lean concept relies on a consensus developed from the bottom-up by participants involved in the processes. It concentrates on elements such as trust, commitment, knowledge sharing, transparency, collaboration, and empowerment, among other things. It can be defined as a unified integrated model derived from collective learning and emphasises a human-centred approach, prioritising individuals (Maciag, [2019](#)). Although Lean Management has different foundations, it depends on both human and institutional aspects; it could be useful to extract those elements that are also relevant to higher education to foster positive changes within the institutions' organisational culture.

In a previous study, Wincel and Kull ([2013](#)) declared that lean principles rotate around three “P”s: (i) Purpose, which entails aligning everyone with the same vision, values, and mission; (ii) People to achieve mutual prosperity; and (iii) Processes to identify issues and engage people at all levels to formulate solutions. Additionally, Wincel and Kull ([2013](#)) integrated a fourth “P” for problem-solving. In this way, the “PDCA” cycle (Plan, Do, Check, Act) can be used to improve further. These principles could be implemented at the institutional level because, in line with

former research, findings show that organisational culture is critical in shaping the relationship between staff categories.

7.3.2 The 'Divide' – A Persistent Problem to be Tackled

Organisational culture is also present in studies related to the 'divide' because it plays a pivotal role in either exacerbating or mitigating its presence. Duane and Corcoran (2018) stated in their study that at the institutional level the 'divide' is often caused by the organisational culture and the structure. Apart from the many reasons already described in the literature review which cause the division between staff categories, Bess and Dee (2014) also mentioned that the philosophical principles that underlie the daily practices of academics and professional staff, even if these principles are explicitly recognised or function at a subconscious level, can shape the way staff communicate.

Even more, the divisions between these divergent viewpoints are frequently regarded as inherently irreconcilable due to their incompatible interactions (Bess & Dee, 2014).

On the contrary, the benefits when this division is not present have been described in the previous chapter. In individuals, the benefits are loyalty, behavioural change, flexibility, recognition and rewards. Instead, for the organisation the benefits are intellectual capital, new knowledge, cultural change, the dissolution of boundaries, and the promotion of communication (Duane & Corcoran, 2018). In this study, the described positive effects mentioned by these authors were found within most EMJMD consortiums, but not always at the institutional level.

Consequently, while there was an equal relationship between academics and professional staff within the consortiums, at the institutional level signs of hierarchical structures, lack of recognition, and power imbalances were present. To address these issues, Duane and Corcoran

(2018) also mentioned that the first step to embracing a transformational culture is that management recognises the presence of the division and the negative aspects of the organisational culture.

Previous scientific research findings suggest that when provided with suitable collaboration opportunities, professional staff and academics engage in collaboration and communication (Duane & Corcoran, 2018), as was the case with the EMJMD consortiums. While at the institutional level, professional staff often felt as described by some scholars: “comparatively impotent or largely invisible, in spite of the contributions they make to their institutions” (Gray, 2015, p. 546), and with no recognition of their pivotal role as indispensable players in the daily operations of academic institutions (Bacelar-Nicolau et al., 2023). This is also an unfortunate consequence of the academic literature’s recurrent ideas about professional staff. For example, Gray (2015) listed the most common topics related to professional staff in the scientific literature: The *Third Space* and beyond, costly bureaucracy, managerialism and others. Few studies address other issues such as the career challenges, workload conditions, personal expectations, or the different categories within this staff group, making the knowledge in the field scarce and offering new research areas to complement the current body of literature focused exclusively on academic staff.

Florenthal and Tolstikov-Mast (2012) also specified that the organisational culture within a higher education institution shapes the educational journey of its students, and fostering a robust sense of community among staff is pivotal for cultivating this positive organisational culture. Establishing this sense of community depends on building strong working relationships between academics and professional staff. Therefore, management faces the decision of either

facilitating meaningful collaboration between staff or maintaining a division that serves neither the students nor the institution (Florenthal & Tolstikov-Mast, [2012](#))

Additionally, previous scientific studies show that organisational structure and size can emerge as obstacles to collaboration and knowledge exchange (Corcoran & Duane, [2019](#)). EMJMDs, as described by participants, are small settings facilitating close interaction, decision-making, and problem-solving among different staff categories. However, physical distance exacerbates the existing 'divide' (Syno et al., [2023](#)), and it was also observed at some institutions where academics and professional staff are even located in different buildings. Finally, power dynamics, organisational perspectives, and the concept of academic freedom contribute to the widening of this division (Finkielsztein & Wagner, [2023](#)). They were also mentioned by some participants when describing the hierarchical relationship, the complex administrative procedures and the lack of understanding between academics and professional staff.

7.3.3 Effective Collaboration on an Institutional Scale

Regardless of the institutional intricacies, many participants mentioned that it was possible to collaborate properly with departments or units to develop tailored administrative procedures for the EMJMDs. Even if each staff category had its established traditions, roles, and work methods (Pham & Tanner, [2015](#)), it was possible to solve problems that were beyond the degree to which the expertise of other colleagues was key. Issues related to the diploma, quality assurance, and admissions procedures were frequently managed with the support of the central units.

These results can be compared with previous research where it was demonstrated that in certain areas, similar positive interactions occur. This is the case, for example, between academics and librarians (Pham & Tanner, [2015](#)). Their collaboration includes developing student learning

skills, integrating information literacy and research skills into the curriculum, as well as teaching, tutoring, and participating in research projects. Such collaborations exemplify how educational outcomes can be enhanced by leveraging resources, expertise, and innovative approaches (Pham & Tanner, [2015](#)).

Although there is a scarcity of research on team collaboration within higher education learning and teaching, Newell and Bain ([2020](#)) conducted a study and measured the key factors for effective collaboration within the specific context of programme design and implementation. Some of the factors included were working together to solve problems, less hierarchical models, enhancing abilities and refining procedures (Newell & Bain, [2020](#)). My findings are consistent with such study because the factors described by these authors are similar to my findings and were also stated by many of the respondents as the vehicles for Team Effectiveness. For example, some respondents mentioned the importance of discussing together issues related to admissions or potential mobility paths to find a common solution for these procedures. While solving these problems, both staff categories have the same possibility to voice their opinions without hierarchical attitudes and, consequently, there was a common responsibility for the decisions taken. Similarly, it was also observed that the absence of respect, lack of understanding or insufficient recognition of the contributions made by other staff members represents a substantial obstacle to effective collaboration (San Martín-Rodríguez et al., [2005](#)).

7.4 Exploring Personal and Interpersonal Dynamics

As previously noted, many participants, both academics and professional staff, were engaged in an EMJMD on a part-time basis. Consequently, their primary responsibilities were typically carried out alongside the additional tasks assigned by the consortium. This led to an increased

workload and responsibilities, requiring individuals to navigate between two different settings at the same time – the institution and the EMJMD consortium. This adaptation necessitated adjustments in their roles, expertise, and behaviour and led to inevitable comparisons between the two environments.

7.4.1 The Satisfaction and Happiness of Consortium Membership

The fulfilment described by this study's participants reinforces and echoes the job satisfaction enablers presented in previous research that shows how the contentment of employees in their roles and their level of engagement are pivotal for the overall success of an organisation. As described by Bray and Williams (2017), high organisational commitment produces three primary advantages: (i) enhanced productivity (Azmy, 2019); (ii) reduced turnover and organisational stability (Takawira et al., 2014); and (iii) employee loyalty (Abror et al., 2020).

Aspects such as autonomy and, mainly, relations at work are the ones that give meaningfulness to individuals (Nikolova & Cnossen, 2020). Moreover, previous studies also underscored the correlation between recognition and job satisfaction, highlighting the pivotal role of institutional policies and practices in cultivating a supportive work environment. “The benefit of employees feeling valued is often commitment”, declared Bray and Williams (2017, p. 489), underlining the significance of the work atmosphere, social dynamics and workplace settings (Majid et al., 2020). This is reflected in the responses of most of the professional staff involved in EMJMDs. Even if the vital role that professional staff play in the general efficiency and efficacy of higher education institutions is frequently disregarded in the literature on education (Bacelar-Nicolau et al., 2023), they felt recognised and valued for their skills, knowledge and expertise

while working in a consortium. Unfortunately, this was not always the case while performing their jobs at the institutional level, so there is still a lot to be done in this regard.

As mentioned by de Jong and del Junco (2023), depending on their educational and professional backgrounds as well as their roles and responsibilities, professional staff interact with academics, institutional leadership, and other organisations, having a direct or indirect impact on knowledge development. In addition, through their involvement in academic practices and the development and implementation of strategies and policies (de Jong & del Junco, 2023) as is the case of international projects like EMJMDS, their knowledge can be requested and their expertise can be recognised.

For academics, instead, job satisfaction usually encompassed elements like salary, opportunities for advancement, job stability, and the nature of academic responsibilities (Chen, 2023). Respondents did not describe these factors as satisfaction triggers. On the contrary, they described a more human aspect, such as encountering students from all over the world, being part of their career development, and the networking opportunities for innovative research projects.

The strong association found in the academic sector between emotional commitment and Job Satisfaction has important implications. Those who are happy with their compensation, recognition, and opportunities for growth often develop a strong emotional connection and loyalty to their institution (Trivellas & Santouridis, 2016). Many academics working in the EMJMDS observed that there was no additional compensation, yet still their satisfaction of working in a project of excellence was extremely rewarding. Nevertheless, it is important to highlight that promoting job satisfaction through appropriate incentive programmes and clear career development paths is necessary since these can lead to increased commitment from academics and professional

staff (Trivellas & Santouridis, [2016](#)). This kind of engagement is essential to keeping talented staff members and creating a positive work environment that supports the university's goals and values (Trivellas & Santouridis, [2016](#)) and in the specific case of an EMJMD it is essential to maintain these projects alive with the appropriate staff members who have the know-how to implement them despite the multiple intrinsic challenges.

7.4.2 Managing the Distribution of Tasks to Maintain a Reasonable Workload

Even if almost all participants were satisfied, they felt overwhelmed due to the amount of work. As described by Curran and Prottas ([2017](#)), role overload is the perception that one is faced with excessive work or an overwhelming number of responsibilities to manage. Likewise, the perception of work roles significantly impacts satisfaction because ambiguous roles can result in overburdening, especially when reporting to multiple supervisors (Curran & Prottas, [2017](#)).

Participants of my study did not explicitly describe the problem of reporting to more than one supervisor. On the contrary, the issue that affected them the most was the amount of work because, as underlined by Trivellas and Santouridis ([2016](#)), when people perceive that the institution esteems their personal time and well-being, it increases their commitment and job satisfaction. Therefore, even if the excessive workload does not respect the special attention to well-being, positive aspects such as recognition, intercultural impact, and skills enhancement prevailed over the workload. Only one participant mentioned a change of job due to the challenges encountered and excessive workload. This means that for almost all of them, the satisfaction they encountered was so strong that they were able to overcome any problematic aspect of their jobs.

7.4.3 Deconstructing Frustration: Understanding its Causes and Solutions

Although fulfilment was described by the vast majority of participants, frustration was also mentioned. Since most participants noticed differences between the institution and the EMJMDs studied, being in the middle of these two environments was sometimes beneficial to overcome the issues and, in other cases, worsen the situation. For example, the bureaucratic aspects within the institutions certainly created additional challenges to solve, especially when specific tailored administrative procedures were required for the EMJMD.

Besides, as previously detailed, in hierarchical organisations interactions between academics and professional staff can be tense, mainly when faculty try to dictate professional staff workloads, and consequently professional staff often express sentiments of being undervalued and overlooked regarding their concerns (Florenthal & Tolstikov-Mast, [2012](#)). However, when an environment – such as an EMJMD – offers professional staff participation in decision-making, transparent communication of roles and responsibilities, and a fair rewards system, it can alleviate tensions (Florenthal & Tolstikov-Mast, [2012](#)), and professional staff appreciate the way their role is perceived and respected.

On the contrary, even if the literature describes that for academic sources of frustration are related to the diminishing emphasis placed on education in comparison to research, alongside the escalating overall workload (Pham & Tanner, [2015](#)), within the EMJMDs academics were frustrated by workload and mainly by bureaucracy. However, at the very same time they felt engaged for an enriching experience in terms of multiculturalism, teaching experience and the new research opportunities.

7.4.4 The Power of Individual Influence: Shaping Relationships

Participants also described a strong personal component within the staff relationships. Interpersonal relationships significantly impact service quality, affecting individual and organisational outcomes through the level of cooperation, trust, and reciprocity experienced among staff (Gibbs & Kharouf, [2022](#)). Consequently, depending on individuals' behaviours, personality traits, communication style, tolerance, and respect, relationships could be more empathetic and egalitarian or the opposite. According to House's statement, "Interpersonal relationships are a foundational tool for accomplishing objectives in any organizational context but play an even more important role in Higher Education environments than many others" (House, [2018](#), p. 173). Additionally, Marlow et al. ([2018](#)) suggested that the quality of communication is correlated with performance because it facilitates team members to obtain essential information for successful task completion.

Likewise, in line with the study of Ma and Montgomery ([2021](#)), interpersonal connections are crucial to building and maintaining sustainable partnerships in higher education. According to these authors, establishing profound human bonds that cultivate mutual comprehension, respect, and confidence among individuals involved in partnerships is vital. The involvement of individuals with their personal commitment and proactive engagement is the foundational element that binds prosperous partnerships (Ma & Montgomery, [2021](#)). The reflection of these authors on the type of relationship needed echoes the positive findings within the EMJMDs observed. Nevertheless, although positive interpersonal relationships are essential for individuals, where trust and empathy help foster a supportive environment (Bowen et al., [2018](#)), a few participants also mentioned that this was not always the case. Hence, when hierarchical attitudes were present, and power relationships appeared, tensions reinforced the 'divide' between

academics and professional staff, creating a less supportive environment, which was not the ideal collaborative setting.

As a final point, it is essential to highlight that outcomes related to internationalisation of higher education activities are multiple, complex and extensively studied. Conversely, knowledge about unforeseen outcomes need to be expanded (Raby & Kamyab, [2023](#)). Under this lens, the findings of this study could be seen as part of the Unintended Consequences of Internationalisation (UCI) framework and, more specifically, as part of the “unforeseen actions that are not anticipated” (Raby & Kamyab, [2023](#), p. 16). Overcoming the ‘divide’ is a positive unintended action of an EMJMD, which was not anticipated when these degrees were planned in 2004. Their main focus was mobility, excellence, cooperation and as part of the international education industry “a source of revenue and a means for enhanced reputation and soft power” (de Wit & Deca, [2020](#), p. 4). Nonetheless, the findings also make evident that the EMJMDs could go beyond their initial goals, since the human capital behind the scenes could provide invaluable insights for successful collaboration between staff categories.

Although participants mentioned that replicating the EMJMD consortiums’ good practices at the institutional level could be extremely challenging due to the differences in size and number of people involved, a first step could be done at a lower level as proposed by Garnet (blended professional): “But I think that this may be could be implemented, or could be applied in some way, like in a faculty level or department level.”

Figure 7.2 encapsulates the principal findings of this research. It illustrates the collaboration between academics and professional staff within higher education institutions, highlighting their distinct roles as two separate groups. One in front of the other, positioned on either side of a conceptual ‘divide’. Blended professionals appear in the middle of these two staff

Figure 7.2 – Overcoming the ‘divide’

Source: Author's own work

categories since individuals within this group have the capacity to work on both academic and administrative aspects. Within the context of the EMJMDs studied, this research reveals the emergence of a *Third Space*, characterised by the unique features already described. This *Third Space* serves as a connection between academics and professional staff where the specific attributes of EMJMDs facilitate collaboration enabling to transcend the traditional 'divide' and simplifying their work together.

7.5 The Role of the Theoretical Framework in Addressing the Research Questions

The Theoretical Framework and its three concepts (the ‘divide’, the *Third Space* and the Interprofessional Collaboration) were fundamental to offering the needed insights to reply to the Research Questions. Hence, to summarise the previously described findings, concise responses to the two guiding Research Questions of the study are presented in this final section of the chapter.

The first Research Question enquired about changes in the professional staff-academics collaboration dynamics with a particular focus on its characteristics and reasons behind the changes.

Research Question #1: To what extent does the experience of working in EMJMDs change the effectiveness of staff collaboration within and across the universities involved?

Sub questions:

- (i) What are the evolving characteristics of the professional staff-academics collaboration in EMJMDs?
- (ii) What are the key factors influencing these changes?

The first Research Question was replied to with the use of the Sunnybrook Framework (McLaney et al., [2018](#)), and the “Dispositional Contexts Associated with the professional staff-academics Relationships” (Del Favero & Bray, [2005](#)). They were extremely useful in verifying if the collaboration was functioning – or not – and if it had the commitment to define mutual objectives and shared responsibility, authority, and accountability for achievements with an equitable distribution of resources and rewards (Green & Johnson, [2015](#)).

It is possible to affirm that in the majority of the EMJMDs observed, the *Third Space* setting allowed different staff categories to work in close relationships and to collaborate effectively. Working in the consortiums facilitated academics, professional staff and blended professionals to have the connections needed to design a Master’s degree, implement it and make

it successful. The 'divide' was bridged by the unique characteristics of the EMJMDs and the people involved in them.

Unique characteristics such as a joint curriculum, joint diploma, joint admissions procedures and joint accreditation, a genuinely multicultural setting, and the guidelines provided by the European Commission – amongst other things – required a specific specialised and skilled mixed team to work closely to achieve a single goal: the success of their EMJMD. Participants described a strong sense of commitment and motivation, understanding the needs of the other category. They felt a supportive environment where sharing tasks and responsibilities was possible. This supportive atmosphere cultivated a sense of unity and purpose among participants, who work together with the accomplishment of their degree in mind. Previous research reinforces their perception because organisational culture has a significant influence on motivation and changes in that culture can have significant impacts on motivation levels (Duane & Corcoran, [2018](#)). In this case, the EMJMDs provided the participants with an environment in which they felt respected and acknowledged and consequently their motivation increased.

There are several key factors influencing the changes in the collaboration style. The jointness aspect of these Master's degrees and having a challenging goal undoubtedly enables the process. For this reason, the consortiums usually used appropriate communication methods, which, in turn, helped the collaboration among participants. Besides, the multicultural environment promoted flexibility and tolerance. The recognition of individual contributions delineated clear roles with a defined interdependence and non-hierarchical but egalitarian relationships where collaboration was based on trust, mutual respect, inclusive decision-making, and acknowledgement. Finally, the reduced size of the consortiums, as well as the frequent social gatherings, certainly reinforced the relationships among participants. Such principles create a

supportive setting that enhances Team Effectiveness and ensures the achievement of the collaborative work.

The second Research Question was related to the collaboration concept itself and the added value for people involved. *Research Question #2*: Is the experience of working in EMJMDs changing the understanding of staff collaboration?

Sub questions:

- (i) What is the added value of the collaboration within EMJMDs for the staff involved?
- (ii) How is this collaboration enhancing the recognition of the role and the work performed by professional staff?

Similarly, the three abovementioned concepts from the Theoretical Framework help to understand the perceptions of each category, to compare the problems of professional staff and academics, offering the possibility of diving deep into the interests and uncertainties within each role. For example, academics are interested in teaching and research and fear insecurity related to their academic careers (Caplow & McGee, [2001](#)), while professional staff are focused on effective administrative processes and organisational structure and suffer a lack of recognition for their work. By analysing these priorities and dynamics and the figure of blended professionals – which emerges from the concept of *Third Space* – it was possible to underscore the crucial role of each category within the institutions.

Additionally, the shared decision-making and the conflict resolution offered by the Sunnybrook Framework (McLaney et al., [2018](#)) were necessary to verify the existence of these dynamics within the studied EMJMDs, since these two aspects can also provide a positive or negative experience within collaborative mechanisms.

Most participants described a very positive experience, underlining that being part of the “Mundus Family” was something they especially valued because they felt an essential element of a broader community. The EMJMD enables the interaction between staff categories from two perspectives. The first was between the three staff categories to manage the different administrative processes (grant administration, joint aspects, admissions, curriculum design, social activities and much more). The second was with the student community of the programme to enhance the service and provide a high-quality teaching and learning experience. Furthermore, working in an EMJMD allows participants to understand the vast administrative procedures behind these degrees. Therefore, it offered the opportunity to realise that in all these processes, the presence and know-how of the different staff categories are fundamental to achieving the main goal after jointly completing tasks, submitting deliverables and reaching the desired milestones. On the contrary, collaboration is not fruitful in accomplishing such goals if there is a “division”, hierarchical positions, and power imbalance.

The added value for people involved has a twofold perspective. For professional staff, it was the opportunity to use and display their skill set and be acknowledged as experts in their field. For academics, it was the possibility to recognise the value of professional staff and to collaborate with colleagues from other countries and different educational systems, giving them the chance to explore new teaching methodologies and research opportunities. Consequently, respondents felt engaged, valued, and committed, providing the added value of loyalty towards the institutions to improve their international visibility with a leading and successful programme.

The role and work of professional staff were clearly recognised within most of the EMJMD *Third Spaces*. This made the consortiums’ community aware of the multiple vital roles professional staff can develop in terms of making possible specific academic ideas and, therefore,

the importance of involving them from the very beginning in the decision-making settings and in any other aspects of institutional life in which the expertise of different staff categories is required.

7.6 Concluding Remarks

While verifying the relationship between staff categories, their characteristics, how staff members felt about their collaboration, and whether the role of professional staff was duly recognised in the EMJMDs *Third Space*, the Research Questions of this study were addressed. The findings of this study highlight the importance of collaboration among different staff categories in higher education institutions to improve institutional outcomes and overcome the 'divide'. It is crucial to avoid individualistic models and hierarchical leadership to be able to promote teamwork and group problem-solving instead. This will help to foster an organisational culture where the knowledge and skills of all community members are equally recognised and integrated systematically throughout the institution.

CHAPTER EIGHT: CONCLUSIONS

8.1 Introduction

The classification of higher education staff into professional staff and academics oversimplifies higher education institutions' diverse responsibilities and does not acknowledge the different roles and connections between staff in delivering quality education with high academic standards. Moreover, due to their academic aspect, some of the complex administrative tasks performed by professional staff are frequently overlooked, often creating tensions and a dysfunctional relationship – a 'divide' – between them and academics. The 'divide' needs to be recognised, studied and understood because, on the one hand, it limits the opportunities for staff to collaborate and share knowledge and, on the other hand, it affects the student's educational experience.

My study underscores the importance of EMJMD *Third Space* environments, by uncovering valuable insights into the collaboration among diverse staff groups during the development of international projects and explores how to bridge the existing 'divide' between staff categories. EMJMDs are singular programmes where the learning activity is not just about high-quality academic achievements but a life-changing experience for those involved due to the rich cultural exchange and the forging of lifelong connections. It offers an enriching exposure to an international classroom and the opportunity to collaborate across institutions, expanding the possibilities for staff and institutions involved. Moreover, even if an EMJMD entails challenges and difficulties, participants usually described it as an extremely positive experience.

From the perspectives of the staff involved in this study, the inherent qualities of the EMJMDs create the ideal collaborative environment that transcends traditional hierarchies and job titles. The clear understanding of roles and responsibilities among professional staff,

academics, and blended professional fosters a sense of interdependence, where each member's contributions are essential to achieving the same goal: the degree's success. This interdependence requires effective communication channels, allowing for the open exchange of ideas, concerns, problem solutions and joint decisions. Furthermore, the shared purpose is further reinforced by recognising each staff member's unique expertise, the challenges in their respective domains, and the support required to face them. By embracing an egalitarian approach, EMJMD *Third Spaces* encourage staff to work together as colleagues, regardless of their formal job titles or academic backgrounds. This collaborative spirit fosters a sense of shared responsibility, where staff members actively support and learn from one another, ultimately enhancing the overall quality and impact of the programme.

This approach not only benefits the programme itself but also contributes to the professional growth and job satisfaction of the staff involved. The knowledge and best practices gathered from this study have the potential to positively influence various higher education institution scenarios, offering transferable insights applicable to a broad range of university contexts. It can also be considered an unexpected internationalisation outcome because their original goal did not involve improving relationships in mixed teams. Mixed teams provide a space for staff members to collaborate towards a shared objective, regardless of their job titles or educational backgrounds, crossing traditional barriers and hierarchies.

8.2 Expected Outcomes

This dissertation aimed to understand the nature of the collaborative relationship between professional staff, academics and blended professionals within an EMJMD's *Third Space*. Therefore, it was expected to find out that professional staff, blended professionals and academics were

considered peers working together in teams to make more effective contributions to the institutional activities. While undertaking this study, the intention was also to observe all sorts of shared values and intellectual drivers as well as a stability of commitments, mutual benefit and other factors that lead to different types of relationships. In parallel, while looking for the ideal model of collaboration used within the EMJMDs, it was helpful to identify who was “importing” this model to the EMJMDs and who was learning from it and seeking to “export” it into their system.

I hope that my dissertation has stimulated an open discussion about university work roles in terms of the added value of each staff member for the benefit of all. Furthermore, as the presence of professional staff in academic units is always needed, it is essential to create opportunities that enable them to fulfil their aspirations when their position can evolve into a blended job because this shift could benefit the institutional workforce.

Lastly, the data and results could enable future EMJMD consortiums and universities to review the staff collaboration developed within their *Third Spaces* and, if possible, implement best practices learned from this study. It is finally expected that this could support a change process by identifying the importance of a positive relationship between staff, encouraging openness in promoting collective values and complementary skills that go beyond stereotypes and negative definitions.

8.3 Audiences that Benefit from this Research

The most immediate audience of this study will be higher education institutions which could benefit from it in different ways. Firstly, by recognising the existence, importance and mechanisms of the *Third Space* in any academic environment other than EMJMDs, for example, the international office, alliances, research projects and others. Secondly, by implementing a revisited and upbeat version of

the ‘divide’ for the benefit of the whole institutional community. Lastly, by developing further research but also by implementing workshops and focus groups on overcoming the ‘divide’ difficulties in other institutional environments that entail – or do not – *Third Spaces*.

Researchers, practitioners and academics in the fields of higher education, psychology, internationalisation of higher education, and many others could also benefit from this study, which could help them better understand professionalisation in higher education, *Third Spaces*, and joint programmes. Moreover, the research and its methodology can be replicated in other institutional collaborative settings.

8.4 Reflection on My Study

Citing Bamford and Moschini ([2024](#)), my findings highlight the opportunities provided by the *Third Space* dimension in the context of higher education learning. As previously mentioned, working in an EMJMD is a life-changing experience for students and staff. However, the effect of these programmes on professional staff merits special attention. The vast majority of participants described their work at the consortiums as challenging, but the acknowledgement received, and the recognition of the importance of their roles, mitigated any difficulties. Even more, participants also mentioned a sense of belonging, and they felt protected and comfortable in voicing their opinions and ideas, making these spaces a safe working environment for them.

The findings that emerged within this study were a concrete, positive example of two essential topics in higher education. The first one is a real example of how to overcome the ‘divide’, which if present, harms the people involved, reduces the student experience, and diminishes institutional achievements. The second one is the recognition of the value, role and work of professional staff. Even if this staff category is not well defined, and even if there are

many terms to nominate this group due to the different specialisations, knowledge and expertise, it is possible to say that professional staff in higher education have not received enough attention in academic publications. Therefore, this study highlighted this staff category and underscored a setting where they are recognised, valued and, consequently, appreciated.

In terms of reflection, the study examined the EMJMDs themselves, their characteristics, strengths, and challenges from the point of view of staff involved in their creation and management. This is a unique perspective since these programmes have been created and studied to improve collaboration among institutions as providers of high-quality education, to attract the best talent worldwide, and bring visibility to the European Higher Education Area. This study demonstrated that these degrees go beyond the initial goals since they change and improve relationships between different staff groups. At the same time, it brings light to the 'divide', a topic present in the academic literature but not thoroughly discussed. The findings of my study help to propose different solutions to address such a 'divide' and the perspectives and experiences of those involved in dysfunctional relationships at work.

The evolution of staff working in universities is another topic that merits reflection, in other words, from the professionalisation of professional staff to the different roles an academic can have, especially while coordinating an EMJMD. At that specific moment, academics become blended professionals. Frequently, they do not realise this change, but at the same time, they start recognising the value of professional staff, the work they do, the different administrative roles and the need for straightforward procedures.

It is also essential to reflect on the critical role blended professionals have within a higher education institution. Often, they are mediators between professional staff and academics, and primarily working in blurred spaces that are not entirely understood at the institutional level.

Finally, it is crucial to consider the benefits that interdisciplinarity can bring to any research study and the enrichment provided by different disciplines to any studied topic.

8.5 What Makes this Study Unique? Contributions to scientific knowledge

This study contributed to scientific knowledge in five ways. The first contribution is the revelation of an unexplored *Third Space* setting, giving researchers and institutions the possibility to identify similar settings in which the relationship between professional staff and academics could have evolved. For this reason, since the research explored a *Third Space* in an international project, the original figure presented by Whitchurch in [2013](#) was revised to more explicitly incorporate the functions of the internationalisation of higher education (See [Appendix J](#) – Whitchurch’s *Third Space* Concept Revisited). For professional staff, I included the setting of an International Office where all the international agreements and procedures occur. For academics, I included participation in international teaching and research projects. In the middle is the *Third Space* related to the internationalisation of higher education, with a list of some of its most common and relevant activities.

The second contribution of my research is related to a new perspective on the Erasmus Mundus programmes because they go beyond their initial scope and offer a positive experience to a less studied staff category in academic research. The third contribution was providing a real concrete example of overcoming the ‘divide’, offering a Conceptual Framework that can be used in other settings to discover the relationships between professional staff and academics and the related findings may be of interest to enrich this study. The fourth and fifth contributions regard the unintended outcome of the EMJMDs and the interdisciplinary approaches, respectively, which were explained in previous sections.

8.6 Recommendations

The persistent division between professional staff and academics within higher education institutions remains a significant challenge, impacting staff engaged in this dynamic and blocking, in part, the institutions' performance. To tackle this issue and foster a harmonious and effective work environment, higher education institutions must prioritise initiatives aimed at bridging this gap and promoting collaboration across staff groups to develop a sense of shared purpose and collective success, emphasising the importance of diverse expertise to achieve objectives. Under this perspective, by valuing the know-how and insights of all staff members, institutions can enhance decision-making processes, promote innovation, and ultimately improve overall performance and outcomes.

It is also essential to have an open and safe environment in which everyone can express their thoughts about the 'divide' because, as stated by Corcoran and Duane (2019), both groups do not uniformly share the perception of a 'divide' and further research is needed to investigate the reasons behind this discrepancy. Consequently, providing a secure space in which it is possible to openly acknowledge diverse perspectives and share challenges to create better relationships based on understanding each other will foster a transparent discussion on the topic, aiming to find a better solution for all.

Based on the findings of my study, I recommend several strategies for fostering successful collaboration within mixed teams. These strategies aim to address the challenges in relationships between professional staff and academics at the institutional level, ultimately leading to long-term improvements. Initially, these recommendations can be implemented at the departmental level, and once they are effectively established, they can be expanded to the institutional level. The strategies are organised into four categories: (i) Institutional Culture and Team Dynamics; (ii) Communication

and Transparency; (iii) Accountability and Decision-Making; and (iv) Knowledge Exchange and Professional Development. Table 8.1 presents a detailed breakdown of these strategies.

Table 8.1 – Strategies for Successful Collaboration in Mixed Teams

Institutional Culture & Team Dynamics	Communication & Transparency
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Define teamwork together to discuss the main features it should have during the different collaborative activities, such as communication, respect, trust, recognition, shared responsibilities, decision-making, and so on. (ii) Foster the establishment of projects that encompass a diversity of actors, which also means a variety of abilities, ideas, and degrees of competence (Veles, 2020). (iii) Acknowledge mixed teams that exemplify outstanding collaboration by providing rewards or incentives since positive reinforcement can incentivise others. (iv) Promote flexible procedures to assist staff in efficiently managing their workloads and supporting each other. (v) Foster a culture where all staff members, regardless of their role, feel valued, respected, and appreciated for their contributions. (vi) Organise team-building activities with all staff categories. (vii) Openly ask directors, deans, and management to demonstrate and encourage collaboration across staff categories and departments. (viii) Rethink the university's <i>Third Space</i> settings as places where professional staff categories can come together to work, build relationships, and engage in joint innovative academic activities (Veles & Danaher, 2024). (ix) Include staff collaboration as part of institutional operations. (x) Normalise professional staff and academic collaboration regardless of any type of boundary (Veles 2024) to develop an institutional Collaborative Mindset. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Create and maintain updated communication channels where staff can access and verify procedures, policies, and best practices. (ii) Organise regular meetings where all staff is informed about projects, goals, and challenges, leaving space for questions and answers. (iii) Offer the possibility of discussing sensitive topics such as the 'divide' to gather all staff categories' opinions and find solutions to overcome it. (iv) Use surveys to gather suggestions and input from all staff at different levels. (v) Promote open discussions where diverse viewpoints can be explored, and disagreements can be addressed constructively.
Accountability & Decision-Making	Exchange of Knowledge & Professional Development
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Create unified and clear goals involving all staff categories. (ii) Establish policies and procedures for making decisions and assigning specific roles and responsibilities to each staff category. (iii) Empower professional staff to make decisions within a well-defined framework, allowing each one to lead in their areas of expertise. (iv) View the various issues to be addressed comprehensively by including the different staff categories in conversations related to academic and administrative topics. (v) Include, when possible, also students in the conversation since they are the ones who experience the different actions developed by a higher education institution. (vi) Utilise analytics and data-driven tools to assess staff collaboration, student outcomes, and institutional effectiveness. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Facilitate the understanding of different roles within the institution to increase knowledge exchange and foster mutual appreciation for each other's contributions. (ii) Offer regular training to all staff on leadership, research collaboration, and innovation in teaching. (iii) Provide opportunities for all staff to increase their professional knowledge. This might include internal or external courses, staff mobility, job shadowing, and other activities. (iv) Organise cross-training programmes to help staff gain skills and understanding of others and the needs of their departments and units. (v) Teach directors, deans and management how to bridge divides and promote cross-team collaboration. (vi) Increase awareness of <i>Third Space</i> collaborations and establish <i>Third Space</i> settings as gathering places for professional staff and academics. (vii) Recognising professional staff as credible sources of knowledge (Blanco, 2024) is essential to encourage a culture of collaboration and continuous improvement within higher education institutions.

To ensure the long-term sustainability of the strategies mentioned above and their impact on institutional outcomes, it is essential to establish structured mechanisms for regularly assessing the implementation of actions. This can be achieved through recurring meetings, forming cross-functional committees, and developing inter-departmental integrated groups comprising professional staff, academics, and blended professionals. These structures will systematically monitor the progress of ongoing collaboration, the state of the art of continuous communication and gather meaningful feedback from staff to identify new challenges. By actively incorporating this input, higher education institutions can refine strategies, enhance engagement, and drive continuous improvement across departments, units and all the different levels.

While implementing good practices learned from the EMJMDs can offer valuable solutions in the long term, it is also key to try to bridge the current long-standing divides between professional staff and academics. The first step in addressing this challenge is creating awareness. This can be achieved by establishing spaces for open dialogue—aligned with the Communication & Transparency strategy (Table 8.1)—where all stakeholders can freely share their perspectives, concerns, feelings and experiences. Understanding the negative impact of this ‘divide’ and the harm it causes to individuals and institutional outcomes is crucial for driving meaningful change. By fostering non-hierarchical discussions, institutions can encourage diverse viewpoints, collaboratively design solutions, and implement targeted actions, as suggested in this research.

On a broader scale, a concrete recommendation is to disseminate the findings of my EMJMDs study through academic publications, institutional policies, and international projects. These initiatives could take different approaches, such as promoting the adoption of good practices across higher education institutions or developing and refining the strategies derived from this research. Additionally, as highlighted in my literature review, research on professional

staff remains limited. Hence, expanding studies across different countries and institutional contexts to analyse the evolving roles, expertise, challenges, and contributions of professional staff and emerging blended professionals would significantly enhance knowledge in higher education. Comparative studies—analogue to the Changing Academic Profession (CAP) project—could provide a much-needed perspective on the administrative side of higher education institutions. Such research would not only redefine professional roles and expertise but also highlight their critical contributions, serving as a natural complement to existing studies on the academic profession.

8.7 Best Practices vs. Reality: Adapting EMJMDs Strategies to New Settings

Although results confirmed the initial assumptions of my study and provided a foundation for proposing collaborative strategies for future implementation, it is crucial to acknowledge the potential limitations of replicating the good practices observed in the EMJMDs across different institutional settings without a flexible and context-sensitive approach, which considers the specific needs, constraints, and capacities of each staff member in a higher education institution. Each institution operates within a unique framework influenced by its organisational structure, governance model, funding mechanisms, and cultural dynamics. Factors such as institutional priorities, academic traditions, resistance to change, varying levels of administrative autonomy, and existing power dynamics between professional staff and academics may affect the feasibility and effectiveness of the strategies proposed in this study.

In addition, in certain institutions—as also observed in the EMJMDs studied—due to cultural or facilities reasons, professional staff and academics usually work in an isolated manner

and are overloaded, which means each category faces different problems and has other priorities. Academics on their side often face challenges due to a lack of strong incentives for collaboration, the burden of administrative tasks, and academic structures that prioritise individual achievements over collective success. Moreover, rigid institutional policies and a lack of flexibility make it difficult for academics to adapt to new teaching methods, research approaches, and cross-disciplinary initiatives. On the administrative side, lengthy procedures, lack of personnel and bureaucratic delays in decision-making slow down critical processes, making it challenging to implement new policies, respond to emerging needs or align academics, students, and leadership. The result is miscommunication, conflicting priorities, and fragmented institutional goals.

While the EMJMDs offer a successful interdisciplinary and international collaboration model, their specific context— characterised by dedicated funding, clear programmatic structures, and strong external partnerships—may not be easily transferable to institutions with more rigid or fragmented operational frameworks. Unless it is first addressed, the lack of flexibility prevents the institutions from adapting to changing educational demands and innovative practices. These challenges require a cultural shift towards greater collaboration, improved communication, and institutional support that encourages interdisciplinary engagement. Consequently, further research and pilot implementations could help assess how the strategies proposed in my research can be modified and scaled to ensure their relevance and sustainability in diverse academic environments.

8.8 Suggestions for Future Research

Future research could complement the current results and offer a different perspective on the subject matter, for example, by incorporating other consortiums and doing comparative studies among the various countries participating in EMJMDs or by exploring the results and focusing

on variables such as gender, professional role, or academic discipline. Many other *Third Spaces* are likely to be present within higher education institutions but have not yet been fully explored. Consequently, similar studies might yield valuable insights into whether the Conceptual Framework created for this study has a comparable explanatory power to other similar unexplored settings.

These unexplored settings include international research projects where academics and professional staff from various countries can collaborate, forming unique spaces that transcend traditional structural boundaries. Inter-institutional alliances between universities in different regions or countries also create *Third Spaces*, requiring addressing cultural differences and administrative challenges to foster collaborative practices among staff groups. Furthermore, units offering international and global services, such as those involved in student recruitment, exchange or study abroad programmes, function as *Third Spaces* by bringing together diverse staff and engaging with stakeholders worldwide. Additionally, virtual and digital spaces, like online courses and collaborative platforms, are emerging as key *Third Spaces* in higher education, requiring the interaction of professional staff and academics as they provide and support individuals' studies globally. These examples showcase the diverse range of *Third Spaces* within universities, highlighting the potential of professional staff-academic collaboration in innovation and its impact on these dynamic environments.

Another critical outcome to continue researching is the organisational culture in higher education institutions regarding staff categories. It is fundamental to highlight each individual's role and value as an equal partner in this intricate environment. Existing research has extensively studied the academic role, examining career transformation, challenges, and expectations from various perspectives. However, there is a significant gap in the literature when it comes to

understanding the experiences and contributions of professional staff and blended professionals. These individuals comprise a large portion of the workforce within universities, yet their roles and impact remain understudied. Hence, it is crucial to delve deeper into several aspects. For example, the professionalisation pathways, training opportunities, and career development prospects available to professional staff and blended professionals. This can show how these roles are evolving and being recognised within the university context.

Examining the different categories that exist within professional staff and blended professionals' roles can also help uncover their potential and skill sets, and the challenges faced in their roles can provide valuable insights into their experiences and the value they bring to the institution. This knowledge can inform strategies for better supporting and empowering this staff categories. In addition, highlighting the tangible contributions and impact of professional staff and blended professionals on the overall functioning and success of the university is crucial for recognising their value as equal partners. This might also help to openly discuss with academics the existence of the 'divide' and the problems it brings to foster a more supportive, egalitarian work environment and an inclusive organisational culture that values the diverse roles and expertise within the institution.

By prioritising research in these areas, it will be possible to better understand the university as a complex, interconnected system where all staff categories play a vital role. This knowledge can support the development of policies and organisational cultures that support and empower all university community members, ultimately enhancing the institution's ability to fulfil its mission and provide the students with a remarkable educational experience.

Last but not least, it is crucial to emphasise the significance of the EMJMDs to the European Commission and beyond in terms of awareness of their impact on the individuals

behind the scenes, specifically on professional staff, to fully understand their experiences and effects within these international programmes. There is an opportunity to explore further and highlight the role, experiences and contributions of professional staff within the EMJMD ecosystem, as current studies and information are limited compared to the coverage of institutions, academics and students.

8.9 Concluding Remarks

This study contributed to a broader conversation regarding enhancing the internal dynamics of higher education institutions to promote increased efficiency and innovation. This was done by investigating the relationship between professional staff and academics while developing international partnerships, which are at the core of the EMJMDs. EMJMDs are challenging environments with unique dynamics where there is a diversification of the administrative and academic functions, but both staff groups work simultaneously for the success of their joint project. These Master's degrees represent an unexplored *Third Space* in which a new collaborative setting is established at the institutional level that differs from others in which the common staff division is still present.

With a mixed-methods approach, this study explored the complexities of EMJMDs, offering a significant understanding from the perspective of staff steering these programmes. While prior studies have predominantly focused on different aspects of the EMJMDs, such as student experiences, mobility impacts, employability, institutional visibility, and prestige, this study took an original perspective. Specifically, it gave voice to the staff working behind the scenes to study the collaborative *Third Space* that appears within these degrees and their

perspectives related to their working experience and the impact it has on their personal and professional lives.

The findings revealed a positive collaborative relationship among staff categories. By marking a significant shift in the dynamics of the historical staff division because within the majority of EMJMDs studied, it was possible to overcome the 'divide'. The critical success factors behind this accomplishment were the features of the functional mixed teams working in these consortiums. Collaboration, improved communication, mutual understanding, recognition of contributions, role awareness, sense of belonging, trust and much more create a protected environment for participants where respect is the fundamental pillar for encouraging positive dynamics and nurturing healthy relationships. By fostering this type of collaborative relationship, participants in this study demonstrated that they have not only improved the working relationship within EMJMDs, but also set a precedent for bridging historical gaps between administration and academia.

The study underscored the transformative impact that a solid Team Effectiveness and a common objective (a successful EMJMD) can have on breaking down silos and encouraging a more harmonious collaborative relationship. It highlights the potential for positive change within the *Third Space* created by international projects, emphasising the power of shared goals, mutual recognition, respect, trust and a safe working environment in reshaping dysfunctional dynamics.

Since overcoming the 'divide' was not part of the objectives of the EMJMDs when they were designed and launched in 2004, this result can be considered an unexpected internationalisation outcome, highlighting the importance of grasping all the singularities related to these degrees. Moreover, since the EMJMDs are considered projects because they receive funding from the European Union and are managed and monitored, taking into consideration a

starting and an ending point, as with any other collaborative project, two different things can happen when it comes to an end. Partners involved may maintain their working relationship, expanding upon the initial cooperation that brought them together, or they may decide to pursue separate endeavours. In most cases, consortiums reapply for a further financial period because EMJMDs are expensive to implement and manage due to the specific characteristics of these degrees. Some consortiums have received funds during different funding cycles, but this is not the case for all.

Nevertheless, as declared by Goulet et al. (2003), regardless of the path forward, the individuals who participated in these projects have undergone personal and professional growth as a result of their involvement. This is the case of professional staff, academics and blended professionals involved in any EMJMD. Because questioning and challenging established hierarchies and binary ways of thinking transforms alternative knowledge into something entirely new (Veles, 2024), and working on international projects – such as an EMJMD *Third Space* – encourages dialogue and the development of a democratic atmosphere (Bamford & Moschini, 2024). The transformative experience and the knowledge obtained will allow staff involved to replicate good practices in other settings because they have changed their way of thinking and can transport their experience to new spaces which offer new possibilities (Veles, 2024), creating the groundwork for productive collaboration among different staff categories at the institutional level.

CHAPTER NINE: MY PERSONAL JOURNEY

9.1 Research Interest and Choice of Topic

Academic curiosity in various aspects of internationalisation of higher education and mainly on transnational partnerships and joint programmes, as well as professional experience – started more than fifteen years ago – stimulated my interest in exploring the uniqueness of EMJMDs. Additionally, during my professional career, I have worked both as an academic and then as a professional staff member and blended professional in institutions where the academic values were deeply embedded as the only operational guidelines, experiencing the challenges of those working in hierarchical institutions. For this reason, and since EMJMDs are good examples of advanced collaboration among institutions and staff professionals, I wanted to explore the essence of the interaction among professional staff and academics within these programmes to verify if they had a specific teamwork engagement which could help them to overcome the ‘divide’, offering a more egalitarian relationship.

Although this was a complex area of research because it addressed sensitive subjects such as hierarchies between staff categories, the acknowledgement of colleagues’ work, and decision-making rights, it provides new knowledge related to how EMJMDs deal with mixed teams. Even more, since current research on these degrees is mainly focused on the achievements from the students’ experience point of view and the institutional visibility, retrieving information regarding mixed staff teams’ good practices enriches the literature related to EMJMDs and joint programmes in general. Furthermore, it provides practical lessons for higher education institutions about professional staff and academic collaboration and how bridging the differences between staff categories is possible.

At the beginning of my PhD journey, it was impossible to carry out this research project in the university I was affiliated with because it did not have any EMJMD. Then, using my network in other institutions and with the information retrieved from websites, I assembled an appropriate group of participants for my research. However, this situation has changed over the

past few years, and I currently manage an EMJMD. This career change enriched and exponentially complemented my research, profoundly affecting my understanding of these Master's degrees.

9.2 Past, Present and Future

In the past four years, during my PhD journey, I experienced several significant issues and changes. These include a transition in my career, relocating to a different country, leaving my home, family crises, and dealing with the challenges brought on by a global pandemic. However, despite all the problems I encountered, my primary goal of finishing my doctoral studies was always forefront in my mind.

I have had a long career in the field of internationalisation of higher education and have always been involved in developing international academic programmes. Thus, my main research interest has been to understand the impact and potential of these degrees. Therefore, with my former experience in mind, I developed a research proposal for the Centre for Higher Education Internationalisation (CHEI). Initially, I was focused on understanding how these programmes influenced the development of global competencies in students. However, thanks to the brilliant intuition of one my supervisors, Dr. Fiona Hunter, I came across a significant body of literature related to the *Third Space*. This brought me to discover that I was part of the staff category called blended professionals and that the 'divide' between academics and professional staff has been often discussed in the academic literature as a harmful situation. Then, I realised how this topic resonated with my personal and professional experiences, given that I have always worked in hierarchical institutions. It soon became my passion because I discovered that the difficulties I experienced were common for other staff members as well, who usually do not have a voice in academic research. Hence, giving them a voice motivated me to embark on this new approach using the specific setting of the joint programmes, in which I had already emerged professionally. Consequently, understanding how the staff collaboration works within the EMJMDs' *Third Space* to

guarantee the success of these programmes and discover the evolution of the historical division became pivotal to giving the voice to the “invisible ones”.

This focus was extremely challenging because it occurred at the beginning of the pandemic with the well-known repercussions it had in mobility programmes around the world, and as already explained, EMJMDs are based on student mobility. Hence, finding consortiums available to participate seemed to me an impossible task. That is why I cannot be grateful enough to the consortiums that agreed to participate in my research. Without those wonderful individuals, this study would not exist.

Throughout my PhD trajectory, I maintained two distinct identities: first, as a scholar practitioner at CHEI and second, in my day-to-day role working in the internationalisation of higher education. The dual nature of my experience, balancing academic research with professional responsibilities, presented unique difficulties and remarkable growth opportunities. As a scholar practitioner, I was able to deeply immerse myself in the investigation within my field, allowing me to obtain a unique perspective from the inside of my study topic, reinforcing the findings and contributing to new insights. Even more, my ongoing work in the sector allowed me to apply the theoretical frameworks and empirical findings from my research in real-world settings. This synergy between the academic and the practical has been invaluable, enabling me to bridge the gap between theory and practice and to generate a study that is both academically rigorous and professionally relevant.

Therefore, the opportunity to start working in an EMJMD in another European country completed my research. Beyond the inherent challenges of relocating to a new country and integrating into a new academic environment, this experience has had a profound impact on the quality and depth of my research. The unique perceptions and perspectives gained from this experience allowed me to approach my research from a different angle, leading to a more nuanced and comprehensive understanding of the topic.

Even if being an insider researcher presupposes both advantages and pitfalls, in my case, my understanding about my topic changed and the results were extremely enriched because of this

involvement, as I came to understand more clearly the responses and feelings of the interviewees, both academics and professional staff. Many of the insights within the findings reflect the knowledge and expertise acquired during the last year of this journey while I was in the inner circle of a consortium.

Now, it is even more evident to me that EMJMDs are really like a privileged club. I understood more the expressions “Mundus Family” and “Mundus Spirit”. I can now clearly see the considerable effort made by each single staff member involved in them for their success. Whether they are professional staff, academics, or blended professionals their common goal is the success of their programme, and they do their best to achieve it even if they have different mental structures, ways of work and priorities. For this reason, within the EMJMDs studied, their relationship allowed them to bridge the ‘divide’. However, I also realised that in terms of staff involved, the ‘divide’ is a problem that affects all categories, and all people involved suffer from it, not only professional staff. Mainly because at the basis, there is a lack of understanding of the other profession’s needs and roles. It is not only a power imbalance or hierarchies. It goes far beyond that because the various categories, unless they have a common goal or project, work in silos. Each category, both professional staff and academics, focuses exclusively on its own needs without listening to the counterpart.

Through my doctoral studies, I developed my research capability and grew in confidence as a researcher. My writing skills and writing style also developed considerably. Moreover, the experience of balancing different roles and responsibilities has strengthened my time management skills, my ability to prioritise, and my capacity for self-reflection. Even more, through writing the thesis, I feel that I started to develop a niche area of research interest. This has had a significant impact on my own career development, giving me renewed encouragement and a sense of personal agency to continue advancing in new projects in which it is possible to enhance the relationship among staff groups. I truly believe that my study can be a door opener to find other *Third Spaces* and promote a less hierarchical relationship for the benefit of all.

Completing my research at CHEI at Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore was a dream before starting this journey, and now it is finally becoming a reality. Being part of this community and having the opportunity to engage in close conversations with the founding scholars of the internationalisation of higher education is more than an honour for me – it is a privilege that I am deeply grateful for. Throughout my time at CHEI, I have been constantly inspired by the intellectual curiosity and passion of my colleagues, and I have been fortunate enough to learn from some of the most brilliant minds in the field. I can confidently say that this journey has not only enriched my academic and professional knowledge but has also profoundly shaped my personal growth and development. The Centre's emphasis on fostering a sense of community and belonging has created a space where I have felt seen, heard, protected and valued, and I have been inspired by the kindness, empathy, and academic generosity of pioneering researchers and colleagues.

Finally, as I near the completion of my doctoral programme, I am immensely thankful for precisely where I am. The lessons I have learned, the skills I have acquired, and the resilience I have cultivated will undoubtedly continue to serve me well in the next chapter of my career and life.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A: Factors Influencing the 'Divide'

Factor	Description	Author(s)
Historical Evolution	Post-WWII Expansion: The post-World War II era played a significant role in the establishment higher education institutions with a distinct focus on promoting economic advancement on both a national and regional scale.	Young & Pinheiro, 2022
	Modern University Governance: The governance structures of universities have evolved, with professional staff taking on more managerial roles.	Middlehurst, 2010 Anderson, 2008
Bureaucratisation	As universities have grown in size and complexity, there has been a corresponding increase in administrative tasks and responsibilities. Bureaucratic expansion has led to a greater reliance on professional staff to manage various aspects, from budgeting to compliance with regulations. The intensification of administrative functions, characterised by the introduction of novel administrative procedures, lead to an increased need for professional staff. This adaptation was in response to regulatory mandates as well as the changes and complexities in higher education.	Coccia, 2009
Accountability and Quality Assurance	A new economy: States needed to reshape connections by pressuring institutions to enhance their accountability, efficiency, and productivity while optimising the utilisation of public resources. The growing number of regulations and accountability measures lead to increased administrative supervision which in turn can be perceived by academics as an intrusion on their autonomy and academic freedom.	Alexander, 2000
Autonomy	Academic autonomy has shifted from a traditional focus on self-governance and freedom to a nuanced understanding that integrates autonomy with accountability. This evolution indicates a shift in university governance from internal control and freedom towards a balanced consideration of external stakeholder expectations.	Maassen et al., 2017
Changing Societal Expectations	In the 1990s, the role of higher education expanded beyond traditional academic pursuits. There was a transformation in the function of the nation-state from manpower planning to strategic planning. Simultaneously, there was an expectation for higher education to contribute to the improvement of economic competitiveness on a global scale, demonstrating measurable outcomes in preparation to the economic development.	Buckner, 2017
Economic Pressures	Funding Challenges: Increased competition for resources, have forced universities to adopt a business approach. As a result, it is perceived that managerialism prioritises administrative objectives over academic principles, diminishing the authority and influence of academics. Besides, academics may feel that professional staff is more interested in cutting costs and increasing revenue than in supporting academic excellence, while professional staff may feel that academics do not understand the institutions' financial constraints.	Kok et al., 2010 Shepherd, 2018
Entrepreneurial University	Entrepreneurship predominantly involves commercialising higher education institutions, which boost institutional revenue but has a different interpretation regarding the universities mission and the academics' roles and identities. Additionally, disputes over resource allocation, can create tensions between academics and professional staff. The managerial approaches to university governance, often referred to as managerialism have contributed to a perception that professional staff are more focused on efficiency, metrics, and outcomes, while academics prioritise intellectual pursuits.	Uslu et al., 2019 Shepherd, 2018
Professionalisation in higher education	An essential component of the broader organisational change within higher education institutions is the shift in the current staffing profiles as well as the number of professional staff working in universities.	Croucher & Woelert, 2022
Globalisation and Competition	Globalisation of higher education: As global markets expanded, the connection between economic growth and capacity to obtain and apply scientific, technical, and economic knowledge proliferated. Consequently, competition on a global scale with a focus on rankings, reputation, and international partnerships increased, and professional staff with high skills set start to be more involved in strategic decisions. However, the greater focus on financial sustainability, competition for resources, and accountability measures have led to a more corporate and business-oriented approach which can sometimes clash with the more traditional academic values of teaching and research.	Siddiqui, 2014 Bess & Dee, 2014

Appendix B: Most Frequently Cited Team Models

Model	Characteristics
Tuckman (1965) <i>Stages of Group Development (FSNP)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Forming - Storming - Norming - Performing - Adjourning
Rubin, et al. (1977) <i>GRPI Model of Team Effectiveness</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Goals - Roles - Processes - Interpersonal Relationships
Katzenbach and Smith (1994) <i>Model focusing on Team Basics</i>	Goals are related to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collective Work-products - Personal Grow - Performance Results
Lombardo and Eichinger (1995) <i>T7 Model of Team Effectiveness</i>	Five internal team factors: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Thrust - Trust - Talent - Teaming Skills - Task Skills Two external team factors: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Team-Leader Fit - Team Support from the Organisation
LaFasto and Larson (2001) <i>Model Five dynamics of teamwork and collaboration</i>	Initial element: the team member Four necessary behaviours for team members: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Openness - Supportiveness - An action orientation - Positive personal style
Lencioni (2002)	Dysfunctions related to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Trust - Unfiltered disagreements - Commitment to decisions and plans - Support - Team results
Hackman (2002)	A team is effective when it has the following conditions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It is a real team with a team task, boundaries, assigned authority, and stability - It has a compelling direction with clear, challenging goals - It has an enabling structure - It operates within a supportive organisational context - It has an expert coach

Appendix C: Sunnybrook's Core Competencies and Behaviours

Core competencies and associated behaviours	
<p>Values & Ethics Transparency, openness and readiness to collaborate while inclusivity is a must and every team member's viewpoint is respected and valued.</p> <p>Behaviours:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Positive discussions about other roles and professions -Safe environment in which everyone can speak -Consideration of values, ethics and rules from all 	<p>Communication Mutual understanding in communication across different roles and professions by developing tools and processes, and using various methods to improve information exchange within and between teams.</p> <p>Behaviours:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Establishes procedures for timely information exchange -Identifies which members need particular information and ensures they receive it -Utilises clear and common language, avoiding jargon and acronyms and providing explanations and checks for comprehension
<p>Conflict Resolution Collaborate to address expected or ongoing conflicts with effective interventions, generating multiple solutions.</p> <p>Behaviours:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Identifies and proactively resolves conflicts within and between teams -Open to listen diverse opinions and ideas from various roles and professions -Addresses challenging issues through discussion and reaches mutually agreed-upon solutions 	<p>Reflection Learn from past experiences, focusing on process and performance, identifying strengths and areas for improvement, and attempting to optimise interactions while considering their impact.</p> <p>Behaviours:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Allocates time for continuous reflection -Creates processes and tools to facilitate reflection -Recognises successes and areas for improvement, celebrating achievements and creating strategies accordingly -Evaluates collective performance
<p>Role Clarification Every member understands each other's role, responsibilities, expertise and considering how roles depend on each other avoiding redundancy.</p> <p>Behaviours:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Communicate roles and scope of practice Seek understanding of other members' roles -Acknowledge of limitations and consult with each other appropriately, considering knowledge and skills 	<p>Shared Decision Making Collaborative decisions to determine suitable actions and if needed, designate who will make final decisions and who is responsible for specific tasks.</p> <p>Behaviours:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Develop and plans aligned with priorities -Set goals across various roles and professions -Identify and assign accountability for all aspects, especially in areas of role overlap

Source: Adapted from McInaney et al. (2018, pp.3-6)

Appendix D: Online Questionnaire

[Questionnaire's landing page]

Dear participant,

Many thanks for your time in responding to this questionnaire.

My name is Maria-Elvira Prieto, and I am a doctoral student at the Centre for Higher Education Internationalisation (CHEI) at the Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore (UCSC). My research focuses on the collaborative relationship that is developed between academic and administrative (AA) staff while developing an international project such as an Erasmus Mundus Joint Master Degree (EMJMD). Your participation will help to understand that type of collaboration.

The questionnaire you are about to respond contains five different parts, and it will take you around 20 minutes to complete. In the first part, I will ask you about your personal and academic background. The other parts contain questions related to your perception about your collaboration within the team and your feelings related to job satisfaction.

I guarantee that everything you answer will be made completely anonymous: confidentiality of the data collected will be my absolute priority, and the information you provide will not be shared with third parties. This questionnaire's ethical clearance was obtained by successfully meeting the UCSC criteria *[Date & Protocol number]*; however, if you do not feel comfortable with any of the survey items, you are not obliged to answer and can choose to stop at any point. However, please submit the questionnaire by the **15th of May 2021**.

My email addresses are at the bottom: do not hesitate to ask any questions before, during or after replying to the questionnaire. If you are interested in the results at the end of the project, please leave your email address in the space provided, and I will be happy to share them with you. If you do not wish to participate but, you are nevertheless interested in hearing more about the results, please contact me by email.

Individual responses will not be disclosed or shared with any person working in your institution. Your answers will be kept strictly confidential and will not be used to identify you or any of your responses. Only your anonymised answers could be used in research outputs (e.g., articles, conference papers, or presentations) and the data will be stored for ten years for this purpose.

Once again, many thanks for your time and the support given to my doctoral studies.

Sincerely,

Maria-Elvira Prieto
mepintz@hotmail.com
maria.prieto@unicatt.it

- By accessing this survey, I confirm that I have read the information sheet; I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the study, and I have received satisfactory answers to these questions, and any additional details requested. I understand my answers will be stored and encrypted for ten years unless I request this cannot be done; I understand that I may withdraw from the study without penalty at any time by advising the researchers of this decision; I understand my data will be anonymously used for scientific publications.

The following questions are about your background and your demographic characteristics. The purpose of this information is only to describe the group of respondents.

What is the name of your institution?	
How would you characterise your institution?	University _____ University of applied sciences _____ Other (please specify) _____
Which is the size of the institution?	Small (less than 5,000 students) _____ Medium (5,000-15,000 students) _____ Large (above15,000 students) _____
What is your job title?	
Which of the following options correspond to your type of role at your institution?	Academic* _____ Administrative** _____ Blended professional*** _____ Other (please specify) _____
How many years have you been working in Higher Education?	
How many years have you been working in your current institution'?	
How many years have you been working in your current role?	
What the highest level of diploma you have received?	Secondary school _____ Bachelor _____ Master _____ Doctorate _____
Could you specify your gender?	Female _____ Male _____ I do not know _____ I prefer not to disclose it _____
What is your year of birth?	
What is your country of birth?	_____
Please state your citizenship(s)	_____ _____ _____

* Academic: "[P]ersonnel who hold an academic rank with such titles as professor, associate professor, assistant professor, instructor, lecturer, or the equivalent of any of these academic ranks. The category includes personnel with other titles, (e.g., dean, director, associate dean, assistant dean, chair or head of department), if their principal activity is instruction or research" (UIS / OECD / EUROSTAT, [2002](#), p.43).

**Administrative: People who have a predominantly administrative role in nature and supporting academic work (Szekeres, [2004](#)).

*** Blended: Professionals spanning administrative and academic domains (Whitchurch, [2009](#)).

Please, before responding, take into consideration the following recommendations:

1. Read the **statements carefully**.
2. Note that there is no right or wrong answer; you are asked to indicate **your personal opinion**.
3. Remember that you should provide an opinion in two different settings: in **your institution and the Erasmus Mundus consortium**.

This section assesses the Collaborative Mindset (CM)

1. Do you agree or disagree with the following statements regarding your abilities to collaborate with colleagues within your institution and the consortium?		In my institution						Within the consortium					
		Strongly agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly disagree	n.a.	Strongly agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly disagree	n.a.
1	I share information with others easily												
2	I publicly acknowledge the efforts of other team members												
3	I am comfortable moving between the leader and follower role												
4	All my tasks in a team project are done on time												
5	I voice my ideas about how the administrative and academic relationship could work better												
6	I listen and value the opinions of others												
7	I exchange opinions to solve problems												
8	I take into consideration my colleagues' roles when asking support in new tasks												
9	I support colleagues if needed												
10	I take into consideration my colleagues' workload before requesting their support												

2. Do you agree or disagree with the following statements related to collaborative conditions in your institution and in the consortium?		In my institution					
		Strongly agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly disagree	n.a.
1	There are standard operating procedures (rules, policies, forms) to coordinate the activities						
2	The success of the collaboration is evaluated						
3	In the meetings, key decisions are taken for the effective functioning of the programme and the consortium						
4	Team member tasks are well coordinated						
5	Efforts are made to improve services and procedures on an ongoing basis						
6	Staff are able to resolve different ways of working						
7	Staff share information freely to strengthen the EMJMD						
8	The team celebrates joint successes						

Within the consortium						
Strongly agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly disagree	n.a.	

3. Do you agree or disagree with the following statements regarding the relationship between administrative and academic staff members in your institution and within the consortium?		In my institution					
		Strongly agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly disagree	n.a.
1	Academic and administrative have good relations						
2	Social events including both academic and administrative staff take place						
3	Committees including both academic and administrative staff working together are helpful						
4	Academic and administrative staff depend on each other in everyday work-related activities						
5	There is mutual respect between academic and administrative staff members						

Within the consortium						
Strongly agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly disagree	n.a.	

This section assesses the Team Effectiveness (TE)

4. Do you agree or disagree regarding the following statements related to the goals and leadership in your institution and the consortium?		In my institution						Within the consortium					
		Strongly agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly disagree	n.a.	Strongly agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly disagree	n.a.
1	The purpose of the EMJMD is widely understood												
2	Constructive feedback is given regularly to the team by the director of the EMJMD												
3	The EMJMD director(s) is(are) open to new ideas from all team members												
4	The team evaluates its work continuously to improve the effectiveness												
5	The EMJMD director(s) promote(s) teamwork												
6	The EMJMD director(s) guides the team to promote progress												
7	The EMJMD leadership supports team members' self-development												
8	The EMJMD Director(s) are approachable												

5. Do you agree or disagree with the following statements regarding the team functioning in your institution and in the consortium?		In my institution						Within the consortium					
		Strongly agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly disagree	n.a.	Strongly agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly disagree	n.a.
1	During meetings, people feel comfortable in expressing their views												
2	The team is always searching for ways to improve the EMJMD												
3	The team values the contributions of colleagues												
4	All colleagues are given an opportunity to speak during meetings												
5	There is a commitment to performing to the best within the team												

This section assesses Job Satisfaction (JS)

7. Do you agree or disagree with the following statements regarding your job motivation in the institution and the consortium?		In my institution					
		Strongly agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly disagree	n.a.
1	My efforts are rewarded the way they should be						
2	All colleagues value my contributions						
3	The job gives me a sense of accomplishment						
4	I have a say in decisions that affect my work						
5	There is a performance evaluation provides me with meaningful information about my job						
6	I feel that my knowledge and expertise are undervalued						
7	I feel frustrated and undermined at times						

Within the consortium						
Strongly agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly disagree		n.a.

8. Do you agree or disagree with the following statements regarding your role in your institution and within the consortium?		In my institution					
		Strongly agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly disagree	n.a.
1	I know in detail my role, goals and tasks						
2	Knowing the boundaries of my colleague's job is fundamental for a proper collaborative relationship						
3	Working with two or more groups, it is difficult because sometimes they operate in a different way						

Within the consortium						
Strongly agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly disagree		n.a.

4	I have to "feel my way" while doing my job								
5	I feel uncertain as to how my job is linked to the project								
6	I have the necessary time to complete my tasks								
7	I feel overloaded with extra responsibilities that are not part of my job								
8	The team needs more colleagues to be able to complete all the required tasks in due time								
9	More policies and guidelines are needed to perform the tasks properly								

9. Do you agree or disagree with the following statements related to institutional features that promote job satisfaction in your institution and within the consortium?		In my institution					
		Strongly agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly disagree	n.a.
1	Sometimes the work is harder because other people do not do their job properly						
2	The rewards for both administrative and academic staff are enough						
3	The team collaborate effectively with other academic and administrative units						
4	There are opportunities to take part in professional development training						
5	There are information, tools and resources needed to work effectively						
6	The programme demonstrates support for a diverse and multicultural workforce						

Within the consortium					
Strongly agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly disagree	n.a.

Open-ended questions

In what ways do you think working in an EMJMD has changed the relationship between academic and administrative staff?

A/

Do you have any additional comments or recommendations that could improve the relationship between academic and administrative staff?

A/

As I explained in the introduction, this questionnaire is part of the Phase 1 data collection. With the information retrieved from the preliminary analysis, a selected group of respondents will be contacted for a follow-up interview. If you are willing to participate, please tick in the box below and add your email address.

I am available for the follow-up interview.

Email _____

Thank you for your time!

Appendix E: Interview Protocol

Participant / Interviewee #

Date

Time

Role

Gender

Interview mode

Introduction

First of all, many thanks for your willingness to participate in this project and for being interviewed today. As you already know, I am studying the collaborative relationship between administrative, academic and blended professionals while developing an Erasmus Mundus Joint Master Degree (EMJMD). The study aims to understand if working on an international project has improved this relationship and helped reduce the historical 'divide' that commonly exists between these professionals. Under this perspective, you were selected for the interview because, during the survey, you had a solid position (positive or negative) related to this 'divide'. Therefore, this is the opportunity to elaborate more on this concept.

In this study, by "academic staff", I refer to all participants whose principal activity is instruction or research; by "professional staff", people who have a predominantly administrative role and facilitate the development of the academic work. Lastly, by "blended staff", those professionals who have the two previous roles, i.e., they have academic and administrative tasks.

To conclude, the purpose of the interview is to explore deeply the results obtained during the first Phase I (quantitative: online survey) of this research to understand better the enablers and obstacles of this type of relationship.

Before we start:

- The interview should last around one hour.
- Approval to record the interview: Can I record this interview?
- I have received your Consent Form signed. *(if not, please send it via email before/ after the interview)*

As you have seen in the Consent Form, responses will be confidential, and anonymity is ensured using pseudonyms/codes. You will be sent the transcription for verification, and if needed, the correction of the information transcribed is possible.

During the interview, I will cover the main three topics of this research study included in the online survey, i.e., Collaborative Mindset, Team Effectiveness and Job Satisfaction. I will explain to you these three concepts before the questions related to them. You will also have time to share your opinion and ask any questions that you may have.

One last thing, if during the interview, we have internet connection issues, we will reuse the same Zoom link.

Do you have any questions before we start? Should we proceed?

Thank you.

My initial question is:

1. **I know that you describe yourself like a _____, with the following job title/position _____.**
 FOLLOW-UP: *Could you elaborate more, i.e., which are some of your main duties?*⁹

2. **In the questionnaire, I asked about a Collaborative Mindset. Could you describe how you perceived these aspects in your institution and the consortium?**

3. **I also asked about Job Satisfaction. In terms of your job satisfaction, how do you feel?**
 PROBE: *What do you like best?*
 FOLLOW-UP: *Could you be more specific by giving some examples?*

 PROBE: *Anything you dislike about your job?*
 FOLLOW-UP: *Could you be more specific by giving some examples?*

4. **How do you think Job Satisfaction – or lack of it – affects the relationship among colleagues?**

5. **The online survey results flagged that Team Spirit. How does it work in your institution and the consortium?**

6. **What do you value about Team Spirit?**

7. **In which ways - if any - do you think the relationship between colleagues changes due to their work in an EMJMD?**
 FOLLOW-UP: *If yes: Why?*

8. **Do you see ways in which these new forms of relationships could become part of daily practice at an institutional level?**
 FOLLOW-UP: *Could you illustrate some examples?*

9. **Do you think the experience of working in an EMJMD provides members and the institutions with a better understanding of the role and importance of all colleagues?**
 FOLLOW-UP: *If yes: Why? - If not: Why not? - Could you illustrate some examples?*

10. **Do you think there is a way to improve/change the relationship between colleagues in the institution and the consortium?**
 FOLLOW-UP: *Could you illustrate some examples?*

⁹ (i) administrative tasks; (ii) teaching and instruction; (iii) research; (iv) leadership and management; and/or (v) third mission activities (external engagement, supporting the local/international society/community, fundraising, entrepreneurship, etc.)

Those are all the questions I have, but...

Is there anything you would like to ask or anything you would like to add to what you have already said before we finish the interview?

Thank you very much for your participation and time.

Appendix F: Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore's Ethics Committee Approval

FONDAZIONE POLICLINICO GEMELLI
 PROTOCOLLO UNICO

Tipologia Atti: in Uscita
 Prot. N. 0011382/21 - Del 28/03/2021
 .SEGRETARIA COMITATO ETICO

Gent.ma Dott.ssa Francesca FINOTELLO
 Centre for Higher Education Internationalisation (CHEI)

Gent.ma Dott.ssa Maria Elvira PRIETO
 Centre for Higher Education Internationalisation (CHEI)

UCSC Milano

Progetto: "Administrative and academic staff collaboration in the internationalisation of Erasmus Mundus Joint Master Degrees"

Gentilissime Dottoresse,

si comunica che il Comitato Etico, nella seduta del 25 febbraio 2021, ha valutato la documentazione pervenuta in data 16/02/2021 relativamente al progetto in oggetto. In particolare, è stata valutata la seguente documentazione:

1. Online Questionnaire;
2. Project Information;
3. Research Description Form;
4. Personal Data Protection Form;
5. Informed Consent form for participants

Ricevuti i chiarimenti richiesti con email del 04/03/2021 e l'abstract del progetto con email del 23/03/2021, codesto Comitato rilascia parere favorevole alla conduzione del progetto.

Il Presidente del Comitato Etico
 Prof.ssa Gigliola SICA

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be "Gigliola SICA", written over a horizontal line.

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SEDUTA TELEMATICA COMITATO ETICO DEL 25 FEBBRAIO 2021

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Appendix G: Consent Form

I, Maria-Elvira Prieto¹⁰, would like to thank you for dedicating your time as an interviewee in this research study whose topic is “Administrative and academic staff collaboration in the internationalisation of Erasmus Mundus Joint Master Degrees”.

By accepting this invitation, you will participate in an in-depth interview that asks a series of questions about the collaborative relationship between administrative, academic and blended professionals while developing an international project. The interview will be recorded and subsequently transcribed.

The interview will take approximately 45 to 60 minutes, and participation is entirely voluntary. You may refuse to participate or withdraw at any time without penalty. Although every effort will be made to prevent any discomfort, you also have the right to decline or skip any questions you prefer not to answer if you find them sensitive or upsetting.

In addition, confidentiality will be strictly maintained. After the interview is completed, it will be assigned an ID number/ pseudonym/anonymous code, replacing your name on all interview documents. Identifying details will be separated as well as the informed consent form from the interview contents. Any research findings will be presented only in statistical summaries and anonymous quotes that use pseudonyms. If needed, only my supervisors will have access to the interviews.

If anything about the study or your participation is unclear, or if you have questions, you may contact me by email at mepintz@hotmail.com. I will gladly reply to all your doubts.

Agreement to Participate:

I, _____ (*participant's full name & surname*), declare that I have received detailed information about the study and a copy of this Consent Form to keep it for my records.

Participant's Signature: _____

Date: _____

¹⁰ 2nd-year PhD student at the Centre for Higher Education Internationalisation at Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, Via Carducci 28/30, 20123 Milan, Italy.

Appendix H: Transcript Example

Research Project: Interview 19

Date	27/06/2022
Time	10.00
Role	Professional Staff
Gender	Female
Interview mode	Zoom video call

SUMMARY KEYWORDS

consortium, coordinators, people, university, academics, colleagues, institution, faculty, bit, professional staff, role, valued, programmes, categories, meetings, students, director, difficult, interview, related

SPEAKERS

- Maria-Elvira Prieto (Researcher)
- Interviewee 19 (Participant)

Researcher 00:07

I'm here. Okay. So, once again, thank you so much for being here with me. Before we start the interview, [*coughing*] sorry, I will give you a brief introduction about my research. So you can refresh your mind, and if you have questions, please feel free to interrupt.

Interviewee 19 00:33

Yes.

Researcher 00:34

Okay. So, my research is related to the collaboration, the collaborative relationship between academics and administrative staff while developing an international project, such as an Erasmus Mundus Joint Master's degree. The reason behind this topic is based on several things. First, my research, my PhD, is in the internationalisation of higher education. Second, during my professional experience, I have been working as a professor, and now I work in the administration, but it could be kind of a blended professional; I will explain a bit about that. So, let's say I have experienced the good and bad of both roles. So that's another reason. And also, the literature shows that there is a historical division between these two categories, meaning professional staff and academics. And I would like to verify if an international project that put together people from different backgrounds, which is one of the aims of the internationalisation of higher education, could help better collaborate. Okay?

Interviewee 19 02:01

Yeah.

Researcher 02:02

So those are the reasons. By academic staff in this research, I mean those colleagues that work in training and research. Administrative staff are those colleagues who facilitate the academic part or have other types of duties. For example, projects, for example, fundraising, and other things that

are not strictly related to academia. And blended professionals are those that have both hats. Meaning they are academics but can have administrative tasks or professional staff with some academic tasks. So those are the three categories. During the survey, I asked about three different factors, which are Collaborative Mindset, Team Effectiveness, and Job Satisfaction. Why? Because for this research, these three topics are the components of a good collaborative relationship. So, during this interview, I am going to ask you something about these three topics. However, I will explain to you the meaning of these three topics before I pose the question so we are on the same page. Everything is going to be confidential; your name is not going to appear anywhere; you are going to be assigned a number. But if you feel uncomfortable about something, or if you prefer not to reply to something, please let me know. Okay? The other thing is that if by any chance we lose the connection, then we use the same link; we just try again with the same. Okay?

Interviewee 19 04:01

Okay.

Researcher 04:02

Well, that was the introduction. Do you have any questions?

Interviewee 19 04:08

Not so far. I'll just wait till your questions come. And maybe if I want you to elaborate, I'm gonna ask you.

Researcher 04:15

Perfect.

Interviewee 19 04:16

I'll just close the door. Close the window, because there's something going on here. So, hang on.

Researcher 04:23

Yes, sure!

Interviewee 19 04:29

Ok, this is better.

Researcher 04:32

So, my first question is very simple. It is related to your job. Which is your job? In which of the three categories are you placed?

Interviewee 19 04:43

I think administrative. I am the programme coordinator of [name]. Oh, one of the programme coordinators. Because my colleague, who started out as an assistant is sort of moving towards sort of a more equal and balanced relationship.

Researcher 05:02

Okay.

Interviewee 19 05:03

In that sense, professional. And I'm also the study advisor for the [name] project.

Researcher 05:08

Perfect.

Interviewee 19 05:09

So, the [name] students, yeah.

Researcher 05:10

So, it is administrative.

Interviewee 19 05:12

That is administrative. Yeah.

Researcher 05:14

Excellent. In the questionnaire, as I mentioned before, I asked about Collaborative Mindset, okay? The Collaborative Mindset in this research is related to sharing information, listening to others, valuing colleagues' opinions and ideas, acknowledging colleagues' work, and respecting each other. When I say colleagues, I mean between academics and professional staff. Not only between academics or between professional staff but between the two categories. Besides, there are good procedures in place, that the needs of both categories are equally important and attended to. And finally, if there is the perception of a 'divide' or division between these two categories. How do you describe the Collaborative Mindset in your institution? And in the consortium?

Interviewee 19 06:18

You mean in general, or just for [name], because I have other responsibilities as well.

Researcher 06:23

I mean, in [name], but also in general, in your institution where you have other responsibilities.

Interviewee 19 06:30

Okay. Well in [name], so not the consortium. Because there is also different sort of dimensions in which I work.

Researcher 06:39

Okay.

Interviewee 19 06:40

Yeah.

Researcher 06:41

In the consortium. I am asking about the consortium.

Interviewee 19 06:46

Okay. Okay, that's clear that. But a large part of my work takes part in [name], which is also part of the consortium. So it is, that is a bit sort of difficult to distinguish between. On the whole? Well, we work together with the director of studies, who is very nice and very cooperative, and very aware of our needs and our input as well.

Researcher 07:13

Okay.

Interviewee 19 07:14

We also work together with, with the lecturers who teach the courses. Yes, and, and I think that also works quite well.

Researcher 07:25
Okay, perfect.

Interviewee 19 07:27

In the consortium, as a whole, I am a bit less positive. There is a bigger 'divide' between the coordinators on the one hand, and the directors, on the other hand.

Researcher 07:40
Okay.

Interviewee 19 07:41

And well, you interpret it, but I also have a feeling that this, this has to do with ... uhm ... how hierarchical national systems are. For example, in [*country*], it's really hierarchical. And the director there is ... I don't know ... she acts as if she is very ... that we're all equal. But she doesn't see it that way ... at least that's how I feel it. Uhhh ... so, it's a bit north-south maybe ... and east-west and northwest being the more ... you know, egalitarian. But it's, of course, also personal, you can't just sort of make these assumptions. So, that is for the consortium as a whole. And then sort of personal experiences. It is usually in this university the case that administrators are not valued as much as academic staff. And, and that was a very painful example of this. When we got together with the Consortium, and one of the faculty board members of this university addressed them and [*name*] went through a very bad and difficult period. But with a new team, we sort of really could restart the whole thing and, and we are doing quite well now. But this person from our own faculty board only addressed our Director of Studies and said, due to her, everything is okay again. Whereas my colleague and I actually had been bearing the brunt of that. And that was acutely painful. Although I knew I should, you know, be above that. It, it really it really hurt me. So, those perceptions are still all over the place. You probably heard those stories before.

Researcher 09:46
Yeah

Interviewee 19 09:47
Yeah, there you are.

Researcher 09:49

Yeah, the ... So, as I said before, unfortunately, the literature shows us that there is the 'divide' ... that there was a 'divide' time ago, but in certain situations, institutions, or regions, it is still there.

Interviewee 19 10:10

Yeah. Yeah. And, and it's also tied to persons because in the University [*name*], professors for example, very much have this blended role as you describe it.

Researcher 10:22
Probably they understand better. They understand this.

Interviewee 19 10:26

Yes, yes, yes. But, but, but some persons, and that's also the personal level. So, it's difficult to make generalisations based on that, But still, yeah.

Researcher 10:39

Excellent. During the interview, I also asked about ... during the survey; sorry, I also asked about Job Satisfaction, okay? Job Satisfaction for this research is related to career advancement, is related to rewards and motivation, if sometimes you feel that you are overloaded, if you receive constructive feedback, if you think that your knowledge and expertise are really valued, and if you enjoy your work. How do you feel about Job Satisfaction?

Interviewee 19 11:22

Some time ago, I took the decision to take on other responsibilities as well. Because I thought ... well, as I said, I started three years ago, and [name] was in a difficult situation, and we all together, we set it back up. And now that it's done, it becomes a bit boring. So, I thought, well, you know, I'm 61, so I'm going to work for another ... I don't know ... four years, and then I'll quit. So, I thought, okay, what am I going to do? I want to do some other stuff, as well. So, but that's also a personal consideration. And one of the ... one of the reasons for my decision was also that there's always so much work, and [name] students are ... I mean, they are very nice and very ultra very idealistic. But they're very sort of work intensive.

Researcher 12:22

Yeah, demanding ...

Interviewee 19 12:23

Yeah. Well, and with this Corona's thing, as a study advisor, I really had a lot of work and a lot of talking and a lot of organizing to do. I mean, I wasn't on my own there. But still, there was a lot of work, and we were all fairly overloaded. And at my age, I thought ... oh no, I do not want to do this anymore. I've been in this line of work, basically, for the past 30 years, working in internationalisation. And I was just getting bit fed up with that. But probably because I went from three days, I probably go back to two days now. And, and ... to try and find some sort of balance.

Researcher 13:05

Yeah true.

Interviewee 19 13:07

But um, well, I, I do feel valued apart from this horrible example I just mentioned. I mean, they asked me to take on this job, and everything was in such chaos here. So, they did recognize what I could do. And they were happy with me that is obvious. Well, I'm paid well for it. So that's also important. And of course, there are always students and people who are just, you know, inconsiderate, or whatever. But you'll find that everywhere

Researcher 13:37

Everywhere in any type of work.

Interviewee 19 13:41

Yeah, yeah. On the whole. And also, because I work so well with my direct colleagues. So, that our Director of Studies and my any other programme coordinator that is really that goes quite well. So, that yeah, yeah. And also, with the other coordinators in [name], that is, that is a great connection in the central office, there is now someone who you may have spoken to as well. And she is wonderful. We have a really good connection. She values what we do, we value what she does. And that also goes to the other coordinators on the whole, not all of them, but but on the whole. That is a very good and very important sort of work partnership.

Researcher 14:24

Yeah. Excellent. Excellent. And what is this thing that you like the most about your job?

Interviewee 19 14:33

Uhm ... I think talking to students and helping them on a one to one or sort of ... in small groups. That's always the nicest. And to really help them along and make them take the next step as it were...

Researcher 14:52

Good, good. And something that you don't like?

Interviewee 19 14:56

All the admin, pressure of work. But in a consortium with eight universities, the administrative processes are just awful.

Researcher 15:08

Yeah

Interviewee 19 15:09

That is one thing. But also, when you work in a consortium like this, you are in between the Consortium, and your own university and national legislation. So, we also have to fit in with the faculty and university regulations for as much as possible. And because our kind of programmes are always the odd one out, with different rules for enrollment, for paying for tuition fees, for graduation, for everything, it takes a lot of time to convince the colleagues in the faculty or in the university that we are different, but we you know, want to cooperate blah, blah. But then the next person comes along there, and you have to start all over again. For example. We are going over to a new electronic learning environment.

Researcher 16:03

Yeah.

Interviewee 19 16:04

Yeah. From, from "Nestor" to "Brightspace" or something. Well, my colleague is directly handling it, because he's systems I'm not. But we have been in touch with people who have to implement this at a very early stage. But still, that it turns out, they have forgotten us, because they also have to enroll colleagues from the consortium. So, people who haven't got University of [name] registration. Well, this is a detail, but it just shows you how difficult it is to get everyone on board to make sure that people know that our needs are a bit different.

Researcher 16:45

Yeah

Interviewee 19 16:46

We've got that on. We've got that, you know, rolling again. But it takes a lot of energy and a lot of time.

Researcher 16:53

Yeah, because there are so many details.

Interviewee 19 16:55

Yeah, exactly. Exactly. And everybody says, Oh, yes, we're very happy with your programme, blah, blah, blah. But then it comes down, you know, to people have to implement small details, and we're not aware of our programme, or we think, Oh, my God, what is this? This is, this is different from the others. So, we just leave it for a bit. Because they're also overburdened with other work, you know? That's ... so it's not because they're, they're sort of evil or...

Researcher 17:21

Or they don't want...

Interviewee 19 17:23

They are cooperative, but it just comes on top of it. And we are sort of the turning point there. And that makes it very difficult. Yeah.

Researcher 17:31

Yeah. I can imagine. Do you think that Job Satisfaction, or the lack of Job Satisfaction, affects the relationship between colleagues?

Interviewee 19 17:50

What it differs is what the source is. If the source is sort overall pressure of work, or impossible institutions to work with. It can bind colleagues together. And that affects, I think, in a positive way, your Job Satisfaction. It's, it's lovely to have a common enemy as it were. You see what I mean?

Researcher 18:14

Yeah, yeah.

Interviewee 19 18:18

And on the other hand, if the source of your dissatisfaction is that you are not valued, or that your voice is not heard, and that your direct colleagues are responsible, that, that is, that is different.

Researcher 18:32

Yeah. Yeah. There are many sources of not satisfaction in your job, no? As you just mentioned. Yeah.

Interviewee 19 18:40

And there are also personal things that really are not directly related to the job in hand, so...

Researcher 18:48

Yeah, that's true. Yeah. During the survey, for many participants, Team Spirit was the most important thing.

Interviewee 19 18:58

Yes. Well, yeah. Yeah. I completely agree with that.

Researcher 19:03

Exactly. Yeah. And for this research, Team Spirit is related to the freedom of expressing yourself during meetings, for example. The value that others give to your work, if there are clear roles and clear responsibilities within the team. If you can admit your weaknesses and your mistakes without being blamed.

Interviewee 19 19:32

Yeah.

Researcher 19:33

If there is a real concern about your well-being and the well-being of others, obviously. If when there is a problem, people try to find a good solution for all, and if people communicate respectfully. These are some of the characteristics of Team Spirit in my research. How do you see this in the consortium and, again, in your university?

Interviewee 19 20:07

I will start with my, with the university here, I think that is just a tick on almost all the items you mentioned. Maybe not ... Well, one thing that is a bit difficult because the Director of Studies is very much hands on hands on, which is also all over the place, sometimes. So, sometimes she just thinks that I'm supposed to do or, you know, so that, that is a bit ... every advantage sometimes has a disadvantage. And this is one of them. That sometimes tasks can, you know, get a bit blurred. But, I mean, that's always resolved. And, and I feel free to express myself. And I mean, getting, getting older like I am, you get much more secure, and much more people tend to listen to you more. So, I think that that is yeah, that's also, that also plays a role in that. Yeah. In, in the consortium ... Well, I already mentioned that the gap between directors and coordinators, at least in some instances. So that it's a bit more frustrating that you are not always valued. Although we take on the brunt of the work, that's not always seen. And communication is not always as good. So, that that is a bit less. But it's also a more complicated setting. And you don't see each other on a daily basis, only very occasionally.

Researcher 21:39

Yeah.

Interviewee 19 21:40

On-screen. So yeah...

Researcher 21:42

It's more difficult.

Interviewee 19 21:43

It is. Yeah. I mean, and I personally think that the consortium is too big ... to actually, you know ... really function well. Well, it does function, but it is difficult that there's so many problems.

Researcher 21:59

Yeah.

Interviewee 19 22:00

Practical obstacles. Yeah.

Researcher 22:02

Yes, because as you mentioned, they're [*number*] different countries, eight different institutions with different regulations and different everything.

Interviewee 19 22:14

Yeah, exactly. And that, I mean, how on earth they ever set it up is just, it's really a miracle. And that the programme is still running. And that and that ...

Researcher 22:25

For so many years.

Interviewee 19 22:27

Yeah. And, and that the European Commission hasn't shown it out and, and the students on the whole, I'm pretty happy. So, I don't know, if there are complaints? Justified complaints? But yeah, yeah. But yeah, some institutions are weaker than others very, very obviously. And that's organizational ... personal issues all come into play here. But there is a difference in the quality. And well, also the communication between partners. There is a sort of core group where we work well. And then there are, you know, university that really fall short of our standards.

Researcher 23:15

Yeah, I see. And what do you value about Team Spirit? You yourself?

Interviewee 19 23:24

Um, well. You mean, the team, the Team Spirit as I experienced it, in the university and in the consortium?

Researcher 23:33

Yes, in general?

Interviewee 19 23:35

Well, you are sort of part of a hole and cooperating with people is lovely. I really, I really enjoy that. I mean, yeah, I mean, I always sort of do lots of things with friends. And, you know, that's the same thing. And in, you know, the other job I hold here, that's, that's also true. So, yeah, if it just appeals to me, personally, I'm not. I mean, I can work on my own quite well, but, but certainly for, for hands on tasks, it's so much better to do it, you know, as a collective. Yeah.

Researcher 24:17

Yeah. Yeah. You mentioned that there is ... because this relates to the perception or how you just describe the Team Spirit within the consortium. There is a different type of Team Spirit within your consortium rather than in your institution. But however, do you think that within the consortium, there are good practices that could be related to the relationship between academics and professional staff, or do you think it is difficult to find good practices there?

Interviewee 19 25:02

No, no. I mean, I definitely think there are ... The coordinators meet like every ... well, four five, six weeks.

Researcher 25:13

Okay.

Interviewee 19 25:14

So, and well, and that is on, on Zoom or Google Meet. But we never meet with the directors apart from once a year at the intensive programme in [name]. But we didn't have that for two years. It was online. So. But, but next September, if all goes well, we will all go there and also have a joint meeting. And I've never had a joint meeting before because when I joined, like, nine months later COVID started. So, I never got there in the end. So yeah, I am curious to see how that works because communication is so important.

Researcher 26:05

Yeah, also because, as you just mentioned, the frequent meetings are between the coordinators.

Interviewee 19 26:14

Yeah, exactly.

Researcher 26:15

Which is administrative staff in your case, in many cases. So, it is completely different if the meeting also includes the academic staff?

Interviewee 19 26:27

Yeah.

Researcher 26:28

Because ... so, it's like there are two categories ... there is no ... yeah.

Interviewee 19 26:35

Yeah. But we also ... at the university level, we also have meetings with the teaching staff. At the beginning of each semester.

Researcher 26:45

Yeah, okay.

Interviewee 19 26:46

Or at the end of the previous semester, or whichever is more convenient. Or, for example, with all the thesis supervisors. But that's the director of studies and I sit in and well, we sort of conducted together, but she takes the lead. And I think that's also a good example of how you well, how you can work. I also coordinate the internships. And, and I'm, and I regularly meet with the internship supervisor, so the person's you know, supervising individual students and grading their internships and their reports. So, so that's also a good example of how you could work.

Researcher 27:30

Yeah. And from those ... let's say those collaborations with these supervisors and professors, apart from a good collaboration, is there anything that you could think it could be implemented in a broader way in your institution?

Interviewee 19 27:53

You mean, only in *[name]* or in the consortium?

Researcher 27:57

In the institution.

Interviewee 19 28:00

Yeah, I think so. But I think that already happens.

Researcher 28:03

Exactly. Yeah.

Interviewee 19 28:04

And I think that one important aspect here is that people who supervise thesis, and certainly people who supervise or teaching staff who supervise internships tend to be younger or more junior in any case. So, the distance between a junior lecturer and an admin staff is less big than between, you know, a professor, a proper professor.

Researcher 28:31

Yeah.

Interviewee 19 28:32

On the whole.

Researcher 28:33

Yeah, definitely.

Interviewee 19 28:34

Yeah. So, so I think it's also good to distinguish between ... we can say academic staff, or admin staff, as one category ... but you can also sort of ... there are some divisions there obviously ...

Researcher 28:50

Of course, of course. Do you think, in general, I'm not talking about the consortium or about your institution ... But do you think that in general, there is a way to improve the collaboration between a academics and administrative staff?

Interviewee 19 29:09

Well, I think because there is a lot of ... in these institutions, there are a lot of complaints from admin staff that they're overburdened, overlooked, not valued. And well, in my case, this, this is not so much the case. But suddenly younger staff or, you know, people working in sector in secretarial offices. Yeah, I'm not quite sure how to organize it because lots of it goes, you know, on personal ... at a personal level ... but how to institutionalize that. Yeah, well meetings people should be aware of each other's needs. Because the fact that admin people complain, does that mean that they're always right about their complaints? Or that they may not see the other side as well.

Researcher 30:15

Yeah, yeah. So at least to create the awareness, to open a discussion and to be able to discuss it.

Interviewee 19 30:25

Yeah, or to have, you know, meetings you know, on a fairly small scale, because big meetings never work in that case. Yes, low scale meetings ... between I don't know, people from one academic course, with the secretariat, you know? At that level, so it's ... yeah. I think that, that may help. But a lot of, a lot of that may already go on here, because we are in the Faculty of [name]. And there are lots of different departments. So, even if I've worked here for 30 years now, I don't know what's happening everywhere, obviously.

Researcher 31:06

Yeah, of course, of course. Do you think that in the consortium, or because of the possibility of having an Erasmus Mundus in your university, the role of each member is clear? And at your university, the importance of the role of academics and professional staff is well perceived? Because frequently is clear what a professor does. But sometimes, is not that clear the role of professional staff.

Interviewee 19 31:55

No, no, that is indeed a good point. Because at the beginning, I ... my role was compared to that of a coordinator, of a departmental coordinator. But it is different. Also, because I combine it with being a study advisor. And at first, their instinct was to sort of impose the faculty structure on the way that we work. Uh huh. And we've really had to argue a lot to tell them that this is not how it works here. But we have another Erasmus, we have two other Erasmus Mundus programmes in our university. Actually, you're probably aware of that.

Researcher 32:45

Yep

Interviewee 19 32:46

[*name*] and ...

Researcher 32:48

Yes, I know about [*name*]

Interviewee 19 32:51

Exactly. Yeah. And [*name*]

Researcher 32:57

Yeah, so that's the reason why. The institution has several Erasmus Mundus, not only one. So, maybe that could help to let people at the institutional level understand the importance of the role of the administrative people.

Interviewee 19 33:18

Well, we have just started that, that project. And well, I don't want to bluff, but it was me who initiated it, that within the faculty, we have four programmes. So, what we started to do is get together with the coordinators of, of these EM programmes once a month, and discuss, you know, common problems. Like the transfer to this new electronic learning environment. Problems with housing for our students.

Researcher 33:51

Yeah.

Interviewee 19 33:52

And we are now on the point, because housing is such a problem here, we are now on the point of involving also, our colleagues in the other faculties, because there's one in spatial science, one in medical science and one in science and engineering, I think. And we're going to write a joint letter to the, to the board of the university, and to plead for our students to get a sort of ... that they are prioritize when you know, the housing, help with housing. Because we are not a campus university. So, it's a complicated thing with, you know, the the housing market and what the university can do for them. So, but, but that we point out that our students are in a very difficult position, and that their needs to be prioritized. And I think that. that may work but the main thing is that we do this together, and sort of get a proper voice. But this will also include the directors, not because we ... all it's a matter of politics, you know?

Researcher 35:04

Yeah

Interviewee 19 35:05

The University Board. But yeah, that's what was the point of doing it. But as coordinators, it's, it's wonderful to share so many things.

Researcher 35:14

Yeah, yeah. But as you mentioned, in order to improve, first of all, the impact of what you're going to do, and second, to create awareness of the different roles an administrative person could have, we need to involve the academics because otherwise, they will keep on seeing us only as support staff.

Interviewee 19 35:42

Yeah. As one sort of amorphous group. I mean, some, some people don't know the difference between a coordinator, a secretary, a study advisor.

Researcher 35:55

Exactly.

Interviewee 19 35:56

And those roles are completely different. Yeah.

Researcher 35:59

Yes. So probably, that's something that I was also wondering if having Erasmus Mundus programmes within the institution could create that sort of awareness. It is not easy.

Interviewee 19 36:14

Well, it's in a way an opportunity because the programmes are different from the regular programmes. So, it could be a good opportunity to point out those roles better.

Researcher 36:31

Yeah. Yeah.

Interviewee 19 36:33

And also, to point out the interaction with the Consortium, and, and how that differs. We're a very simple example. In the faculty, I am called an educational coordinator or something. But within the consortium, I'm a Programme Coordinator. But if, but if I call myself a programme coordinator here, they misunderstand my role.

Researcher 37:02

Well, when you mention a professor, nobody misunderstands the role.

Interviewee 19 37:08

Not exactly. No, no, no, exactly. Yeah.

Researcher 37:12

So slowly, slowly, we need to get there in order to ... yeah, there are different roles, different categories. And we have different roles because there is also a different level of professionalisation. You know. Before, it was not like that because the support staff was mainly for clerical duties. And now it's not like that, you have administrative staff with research experience, PhDs, etc.

Interviewee 19 37:45

Exactly

Researcher 37:46

So, everybody is not the same.

Interviewee 19 37:49

Yeah, no, no...

Researcher 37:50

They need to start recognising that.

Interviewee 19 37:52

Yeah, yeah, that's absolutely true. I also worked as a lecturer myself for, for a few years. And so, so so that's, that also, of course, influences my perspective of academics. I feel much more at one with them, than, for example, a secretary who has just come from secretarial college.

Researcher 38:16

Yeah

Interviewee 19 38:17

Yeah, so so so there is a huge ...

Researcher 38:19

Work to do.

Interviewee 19 38:21

Yeah, yeah. Yes, that but that's, that's, well, there's so much credit. Grading. No, no, that's yeah. But there's so many different roles, such a big category and layering.

Researcher 38:34

Yeah, exactly.

Interviewee 19 38:35

As roles and positions.

Researcher 38:38

Yeah. Is there anything that you would like to change about the relationship between academics and professional staff in your institution? Although you already mentioned that it works kind of well, depending on the people depending on certain things, but you already mentioned that. It works, I think.

Interviewee 19 38:58

Yes, yes. I think yes, I think it works, but sort of mutual understanding would that I think that could be improved. And I suppose also the ... well, you know, professors are still viewed as little Emperor's in their kingdom and that fairly untouchable unless they do something really awful and damaging. And the university is sort of built like that. This is hierarchy. And it's very difficult to, to change that. If you go ... because in the [name], we also have a Polytechnics.

Researcher 39:46

Yes.

Interviewee 19 38:47

And they have a different status from sort of academic research universities, and in these Polytechnics admin staff are paid much better. And they have much more ... They're encouraged to do PhDs, for example. So, so there, there is much more possible there. There's much more freedom there. Whereas in our university, it's much more segregated. And I think that's also because of this ... well hierarchical build up.

Researcher 40:21

Yeah, sure. Sure. Well, those were all my questions.

Interviewee 19 40:27

Oh, really. But it's, but it's almost half the time! Have I been too brief in my answers?

Researcher 40:35

No, absolutely. It was perfect. I always put in two hours, one hour and a half, for the interview. But more or less always 45 minutes.

Interviewee 19 40:45

Yeah. Oh, so so it's okay.

Researcher 40:47

Yeah, yeah, yeah. Just because, as I said before, if we have internet issues, or if we need to restart again or something else.

Interviewee 19 40:56

Yeah, yeah, yeah

Researcher 40:58

So, I prefer to have a longer time slot or, you know?

Interviewee 19 41:03

That is very wise, I'm sure.

Researcher 41:06

But this is the normal timing. Is there anything that you want to add or to share with me that could be helpful for my research ... if you think?

Interviewee 19 41:18

Well, I can't think of anything just yet. I've pretty much said everything that came to mind when he asked you questions.

Researcher 41:26

Excellent

Interviewee 19 41:27

I just wish you every success with completing this.

Researcher 41:31

Thank you so much.

Interviewee 19 41:32

And well, I'm looking forward to reading your work. I hope you can in some way send it or...

Researcher 41:39

Of course!

Interviewee 19 41:40

Yeah.

Researcher 41:41

So, as I said before, now, I will start ... Well, I need to finalize first interviews, then I will start doing all the transcriptions. You will receive yours, so you can approve it or not. Or if you want to make changes, you're going to be able to do it. And after that, when I have all the interviews, then I will start the analysis in order to finalize in October 2023. At that point, I will share the final results and the thesis with the consortium, the director of the consortium, who was the first point of contact, and then specifically with the people that participated in the interviews.

Interviewee 19 42:30

Lovely, yeah, yeah. How many interviews have you still to do?

Researcher 42:36

Ten.

Interviewee 19 42:41

Okay, so you're more than halfway are about ... well almost.

Researcher 42:44

Yes. I will try to send you the transcription before the summer break. So, I don't know; I cannot ensure that because I'm trying. I will try.

Interviewee 19 42:59

I'm leaving on the 11th of July. So, I'm back on the first of August. So just on holidays tend to be a bit earlier than yours, I think. Yeah. But I will. I will read it when I find it and let you. Yeah.

Researcher 43:14

Perfect

Interviewee 19 43:15

Okay.

Researcher 43:16

Thank you so much for participating and for your time and collaboration.

Interviewee 19 43:22

Good luck with everything and, well, I enjoyed it too. So, it was a really it was a nice interview, I thought.

Researcher 43:28

Excellent. Thank you so much. I wish you all the best, and we will keep in touch.

Interviewee 19 43:33

Okay. Bye bye.

Researcher 43:36

Bye. Thank you. Bye bye.

Appendix I: Codes and Coding definitions

<i>Definition</i>	<i>Author(s)</i>	<i>Year & Page</i>
“Coding is the process of segmenting and labelling text to form descriptions and broad themes in the data”	Creswell	2002 , p. 244
“Coding means naming segments of data with a label that simultaneously categorizes, summarizes, and accounts for each piece of data”	Charmaz	2006 , p. 43
“Through coding, you <i>define</i> what is happening in the data and begin to grapple with what it means”	Charmaz	2006 , p. 46
“Coding consists of identifying potentially interesting events, features, phrases, behaviors, or stages of a process and distinguishing them with labels”	Given	2008 , p. 85
“[A] word or short phrase that captures and signals what is going on in a piece of data in a way that links it to some more general analysis issue”	Emerson et al.	2011 , p. 177
“Coding is the process of focusing a mass amount of free-form data with the goal of empirically illuminating answers to research questions. Coding moves in a stepwise fashion progressively from unsorted data to the development of more refined categories, themes, and concepts”	Hahn	2011 , p. 5
“Coding is indeed uncertain, since it is a matter, not simply of ‘discovering’ what is in the data, but, more creatively, of linking up specific events and observations to more general analytic categories and issues”	Emerson et al.	2011 , p. 184
“Coding is only the initial step toward an even more rigorous and evocative analysis and interpretation for a report”	Saldaña	2013 , p. 8
“Coding is <i>linking</i> rather than merely labelling. It leads you from the data to the idea and from the idea to all the data pertaining to that idea”	Richards and Morse	2013 , p. 154
“Coding is the strategy that moves data from diffuse and messy text to organized ideas about what is going on”	Richards and Morse	2013 , p. 167
“Code: Most often a researcher-generated word or short phrase that symbolically assigns a summative, salient, essence-capturing, and/or evocative attribute for a portion of language based or visual data”	Saldaña	2013 , p. 262

Appendix J: Whitchurch’s *Third Space* Concept Revisited

Source: Adapted from Whitchurch (2013, p.25)